

Annual Report

1963

The International Rice Research Institute
Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines

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ADMINISTRATION BUILDING

LABORATORY BUILDING

Contents

Board of Trustees	
Personnel	
Director's Introduction	
Varietal Improvement	
Variety testing and development 14, Breeding methods a techniques 18, Studies on lodging 22, Genetic studies 30.	
Plant Physiology	
Soil Chemistry	
Chemical kinetics of flooded soils 61, Electro-chemistry of flood soils 74, Ionic equilibria in flooded soils 81, Water regime flooded soils 83, Physiological diseases of rice 88.	
Soil Microbiology	
Agronomy	
Maximum yield experiment 91, Rotation crops and green manure 96, Fertilizers and their use 99, Weed control 100, Planting methods 104.	
Plant Pathology	
Rice blast 105, Virus diseases 113, Bacterial diseases of rice 11	
Entomology	
Varietal resistance to the stem borer 120, Chemical control of stem borers and other rice pests 128, Correlations between stem borer infestations and yield 134.	
Agricultural Engineering	
Machinery and wet land rice production 135, Irrigation water losses and use 141, Development of plant growth curves 142, Measure- ment of straw strength 145.	
Experimental Farm	
Chemistry	
Biochemistry 149, Cereal chemistry 153.	
Agricultural Economics	
Statistics	
Instruction 163, Studies of statistical problems 165.	
Office of Communication	
Library and Documentation Center	
Related Activities	
Visiting scientists 175, Regular and special seminars 176, Staff publications 178	
International Activities	
Training program 180, Research fellows 186, International con- ferences 187, Cooperative research 193, International travel 195.	

MEMBERS OF THE BOARD OF TRUSTEES at the annual meeting: (back row) Dr. Chandler, Prince Chakrabandhu, Dr. Moseman, Dr. Kihara, Dr. Shen; (front row) Secretary Gozon, Dr. Romulo, Dr. Hill, Dr. Garcia. Not present: Secretary Damle.

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[°] Resigned January, 1963
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ELYMAR V. VEA, B.S.A., Research Assistant
SONIA T. POBLETE, B.S.M. Tech., Laboratory Aide

*Left during year † Arrived during year

FREQUENT MEETINGS OF THE SENIOR STAFF facilitate inter-departmental coordination on research and related activities. Around the table (left to right), Miss Manalo, Dr. Jennings, Mr. Johnson, Dr. Vergara, Dr. Tanaka, Mr. Ramos, Dr. Ou, Dr. Ruttan, Dr. Ponnampemra, Dr. MacRae, Dr. Byrnes, Mr. Beachell, Dr. Akazawa, Dr. Oñate, Dr. Pathak, Mr. Salacup, Mr. Drilon, Dr. Chandler, and Dr. Wortman. Not present: Dr. Chang, Dr. Juliano, Dr. Moomaw.

Varietal Improvement

PETER R. JENNINGS, Ph.D., Plant Breeder
HENRY M. BEACHELL, M.S., Plant Breeder
FE-TZU CHANG, Ph.D., Geneticist
MERLIN T. HENDERSON, Ph.D., Visiting Scientist^o
ELISEO A. BARDENAS, B.S.A., Assistant Taxonomist
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OSCAR O. TAGUMPAY, B.S.A., Research Aide

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ORLANDO D. SANTOS, B.S.A., Assistant Field Superintendent
JUAN M. LAPIZ, B.S.A., Foreman
EUSTACIO U. RAMIREZ, B.S.A., Foreman

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CORAZON V. MENDOZA, Litt. B., Editorial Assistant
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FABIAN G. ESPINU, B.S.A., Statistical Aide

^oLeft during year

† Arrived during year

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SERENA R. ALBALADEJO, B.S.L.S., Order Librarian
PRISCILLA M. BAUTISTA, B.S.L.S., Indexer
ESTELA A. LOPEZ, B.S.L.S., Circulation Librarian
GLORIA S. QUIROS, A.B., B.S.L.S., Catalog Librarian
MILAGROS C. ZAMORA, A.B., Bibliographer (on leave)
JUKYU CHO, Ph.D., Translator (in Japan)
ETSUKO TAKEYOSHI, Assistant Translator (in Japan)
GREGORIO A. ARDALES, Binder

Food and Dormitory Services

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NENITA C. ESGUERRA, B.S.H.E., Assistant Manager
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IRENE G. DIAZ, B.S.H.E., Assistant Matron
MARCIANA V. CUYNO, B.S. Home Tech., Food Supervisor
ESTER P. NOVERO, B.S. Home Tech., Food Supervisor
AURORA T. VERGARA, B.S. Home Tech., Food Supervisor
JOSEFINA K. VILLEGAS, B.S. Home Tech., Food Supervisor
PRIMO D. RUZON, Chef

Building and Grounds

HERMENEGILDO G. NAVARRO, M.E., Superintendent of Property
ENRIQUE V. DIZON, B.S. Arch., Building Superintendent
RIZALINO T. DILAG, JR., B.S.A., Grounds Superintendent

THIS 16-ROOM WOMEN'S DORMITORY, completed in 1963, houses research scholars, research assistants, and members of the clerical staff.

FIELD CREW PREPARES QUARTER HECTARE PLOTS for the maximum yield and long-term rotation experiments in the area opposite Institute headquarters.

Director's Introduction

This report for 1963 reviews the results obtained since the 1961-62 report went to press in late 1962. Specific research programs present the detailed data, but this introduction will outline a few general interpretations and conclusions to emphasize some of the Institute's contributions toward an understanding of the factors influencing the yield of rice in the tropics.

Average rice yields in most tropical rice-growing countries range from 1,000 to 2,000 kilograms per hectare. Even experimental fields, where presumably the best available varieties and cultural practices are used, often yield only 2,500 to 3,500 kilograms per hectare. As compared with yields in many temperate zone countries, these values are exceptionally low. For example, the FAO Rice Report for 1963 gives average rice yields for 1961-62 in kilograms per hectare as follows: Japan, 4,700; United Arab Republic, 5,050; Spain, 6,360, and Australia, 6,630. Experimental fields and selected individual farms, in these same countries, frequently report

yields ranging from 8,000 to 10,000 kilograms per hectare.

Institute scientists, fully aware of the low average yields in the tropics, direct the bulk of their research toward gaining an understanding of why productivity is low and of how it can be increased.

Although such factors as poor weed, insect, and disease control, unsatisfactory cultural methods, and poor soil management practices influence the low productivity, it appears that the most important single factor is the lack of varieties of rice that are adapted to the soil and climatic conditions of most tropical countries. Specifically, the typical *indica* rice varieties grown in the tropics are tall, heavy-tillering, photoperiod sensitive, and late-maturing. They are susceptible to severe lodging when even moderate amounts of nitrogenous fertilizers are applied.

Although it will require several years to develop satisfactory varieties, Institute plant breeders have undertaken a comprehensive breeding program designed to

A JAPONICA VARIETY FROM TAIWAN (right) and a tropical *indica* variety (left), transplanted at the same time, show many differences as they near maturity. Note the late maturity and susceptibility of lodging of the *indica*.

produce varieties that will be short, stiff-strawed, non-lodging, responsive to nitrogen, early maturing, non-photoperiod sensitive, and disease resistant. In addition, these new varieties must have the eating and cooking characteristics that rice-eating people of southeast Asia prefer. It seems evident from experience at the Institute and elsewhere that a breeding program can produce this type of rice plant and that the capacity of such a plant to produce grain can exceed that of many varieties now grown in the tropics.

The higher rice yields recorded in the various tables and graphs in this report range from 6,000 to more than 8,000 kilograms per hectare. This performance demonstrates that high yields are possible in the tropics. In all instances, these high yields were obtained on plots where either the rice did not lodge at all, or where it did not lodge until just before the grain reached maturity. The absence of lodging resulted either from the fact that a short, stiff-strawed, early-maturing variety (such as one of the *ponlai* varieties) was used, or from the fact that the rice was grown during the dry season when the tillering rate and height growth were retarded,

even though these same varieties lodged severely when grown in the rainy season.

The promising results obtained by the use of systemic insecticides for the control of the rice stem borer deserves mention. If later results confirm the earlier findings that a single application of a systemic insecticide placed in the irrigation water will control the rice stem borer as satisfactorily as 10 foliar applications of certain other types of insecticides, surely a real economic advantage would result. The important fact is that, in several instances, the application of either foliar sprays or systemic insecticides increased the yield in excess of 2 metric tons per hectare.

The rice blast disease is ubiquitous, being present to some degree in all rice-producing regions of the world. During recent years it has become more prevalent, and new physiological races have developed or at least have been identified.

The Institute has accepted the responsibility of leading an international project to establish in 15 or more countries some 40 Uniform Rice Blast Disease Test Nurseries to identify sources of blast resistance and to develop an international set of dif-

ferential varieties for the identification and classification of the physiological races in different countries. This project continues and expands the FAO Uniform Blast Nursery project.

The Institute's thorough investigation of the chemistry of flooded soils merits attention. The dynamic nature of flooded soils is well demonstrated by the fact that such properties as pH and the contents of ferrous iron, manganese, and ammonia change markedly when a soil is either flooded or drained. The reasons for the better growth of rice on flooded soils, as compared to its growth on non-flooded soils, have become clearer as a result of these investigations.

The fact that the protein content of polished rice varies more than 100 percent from the lowest to the highest values may be of real importance from the standpoint of the nutrition of the rice-eating peoples of the world. During the next few years, the Institute scientists hope they can determine more specifically the reasons for the high protein content of various samples and can demonstrate how high levels can be consistently obtained.

If the Institute's program is to have an impact throughout the rice-growing regions of the world, the results of this program must be tested in many other localities. Furthermore, it is hoped that the research data and the discussions presented in the annual report and other documents will stimulate other countries to place greater emphasis on rice research than has been true in the past. The job is too big to be done by one agency.

The international program of the Institute has as its main objective the dissemination of ideas and materials. The research scholars in training at the Institute will carry new thoughts and, hopefully, new vigor to already existing programs on their return to their countries. The international symposia bring the working scientists together for a thorough review of existing knowledge in a given field of specialty and the exchange of ideas on a person-to-person basis. The cooperative research projects that the Institute has inaugurated throughout southeast Asia serve to determine whether practices that have proved successful at Los Baños can be employed in other localities.

GENETICS SYMPOSIUM PARTICIPANTS inspect the rice blast disease nursery (left to right): T. Tateoka, W. T. Chang, S. Wortman, H. W. Li, N. E. Jodon, K. Ramiah, N. Parthasarathy, H. I. Oka, T. Morinaga, and M. Takahashi.

THE SOIL CHEMIST EXPLAINS the greenhouse study of flooded soils to the Institute trustees.

The Institute's total research effort encompasses all phases that appear to have any significant bearing on rice production. With such a comprehensive and well-integrated program, the Institute is confident that during the next few years it will make truly significant contributions to the understanding of those factors which affect rice yield and quality under tropical conditions.

THE TRUSTEES

The terms of service of three of the trustees of the Institute expired in late 1963, and their replacements were elected by mail ballot. The retiring members are Dr. Hitoshi Kihara of Japan, Dr. K. R. Damle of India, and Prince Chakrabandhu of Thailand. The newly elected members are Dr. Yoshiaki Ishizuka, professor of soils and plant nutrition, Hokkaido University; Mr. P. N. Thapar, vice chancellor of Punjab Agricultural University, India; and Mr. Ahsan ud-Din, a Pakistani who is now serving as regional representative of FAO in Asia, with headquarters in Thailand.

Dr. Paulino J. Garcia, who resigned as chairman of the National Science Develop-

ment Board of the Philippines, also resigned as a trustee of the Institute. Dr. Garcia was succeeded by Dr. Juan Salcedo, Jr., the newly appointed chairman of the National Science Development Board.

In January, 1963, Dr. J. G. Harrar, the president of The Rockefeller Foundation, found it necessary to resign as a trustee of the Institute, and Dr. Albert H. Moseman, the director for the agricultural sciences, was appointed to represent the Foundation. At the January meeting of the Board of Trustees, Dr. F. F. Hill, the Ford Foundation representative, was elected as chairman of the Board, a post that Dr. Harrar had held since the Institute was founded.

THE BUILDING PROGRAM

The Institute's construction projects completed during 1963 include a women's dormitory with a capacity of 32, four new greenhouses, a cistern for collecting rainwater for the water deionizers in the laboratory and the greenhouse, a machinery storage shed, and one additional staff residence.

NEW STAFF MEMBERS

Four new senior staff members were added in 1963. Dr. Francis C. Byrnes arrived in March to assume responsibility for the Institute's communication program. Dr. Vernon W. Ruttan came in May and is developing the research program in agricultural economics. Dr. Ian C. MacRae arrived in July to conduct research in soil microbiology, and Mr. Henry M. Beachell came in October to augment the Institute's staff in plant breeding.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT

The financial support of the Institute continued to come largely from The Rockefeller Foundation and the Ford Foundation. The Rockefeller Foundation contributed \$515,000 toward the operating costs of the Institute and, in addition, supplied the services of seven staff members and their travel and perquisites at an estimated annual cost of \$300,000. The Ford Foundation provided \$360,000 for capital needs to complete the physical plant and for the purchase of additional scientific equipment.

The second year of the Institute's inter-

national program (training of research scholars, symposia, and cooperative regional research) was financed from the original 3-year grant of \$750,000 from the Ford Foundation. This grant is being used at the rate of approximately \$250,000 annually.

In early 1963, the Institute received a grant of P103,440 (payable over a 3-year period) from the National Science Development Board of the Philippines toward the cost of investigating the virus diseases of rice. Of the P54,480 received this year, P30,000 was applied toward the construction of the new greenhouses.

The Institute received a \$5,000 grant from the Foundation for International Potash Research (with headquarters in Los Gatos, California), and one from the International Potash Institute (Berne, Switzerland) for \$2,500, as contributions toward the cost of an international symposium on the mineral nutrition of the rice plant to be held at the Institute in February, 1964.

The Institute is seeking additional sources of financial support and has discussed possible projects with various agencies.

FIELD CREW APPLIES HERBICIDE to experimental plots.

ONE OF THE
STATE VISITORS
the year, Princess
of the Netherland
the Institute gues

VISITORS TO INSTITUTE

The Institute has attracted world-wide interest, and several visitors from abroad come to the Institute each week for visits ranging from a few hours to several days. These include administrators of scientific and educational institutions in various foreign countries, ministers and directors of agriculture, and many scientists.

The Institute has been honored by several state visitors who have been invited by the Government of the United States. Included among these have been Queen Beatrix of the Netherlands, the Queen of Thailand, the President of Mexico, the Vice-President of China, and the Prime Minister

PRESIDENT ADOLFO LOPEZ MATEOS, Mexico (center), accompanied by Philippine officials, meets the Institute director.

RESEARCH SCHOLARS FROM THAILAND AND CAMBODIA select panicles from hybrid populations. The men's dormitory is in the background.

Varietal Improvement

There is an urgent need to develop improved rice varieties for most of the tropical and sub-tropical rice-producing areas of the world. Most of the presently available varieties are excessively tall and are susceptible to lodging. Many are late maturing, and their grain yields often are disappointing when fertilizers are applied. While such varieties are capable of producing moderate yields during the wet season on soils of low fertility, they respond to nitrogenous fertilizers with an excessive vegetative growth. This results in lodging, decreased light penetration to the lower leaves, and a limited increase or even a decrease in grain yield.

As increased rice production per unit area will require increased use of fertilizers, it is necessary that new varieties have short, stiff straw to minimize lodging. Resistance to the blast disease is becoming increasingly important. Earliness and in-

sensitivity to day-length are required if two or three crops per year are to become a reality. Moderate seed dormancy is obviously required for the humid tropics. New varieties must efficiently utilize applied nitrogen to produce grain rather than vegetative growth. Finally, the new varieties must possess grain types and cooking characteristics acceptable to the public.

There is considerable circumstantial and some direct evidence that certain plant morphological traits condition yielding ability in rice and that these traits are particularly important in the low-light, high temperature environment of the tropics. Based upon available evidence, the selection criteria followed are: Short, narrow, erect, thick, dark-green leaves, and short, slender stems. These characteristics increase light penetration and utilization as well as reduce respiration losses, and they ultimately lead to lodging resistance, fertilizer responsiveness, and high yield.

Most of the *japonica* varieties from Japan or other temperate zone areas possess an excellent plant habit, but they usually are quite sensitive to temperature and/or length of day, have little or no seed dormancy, and have grain characteristics which are not popular in tropical Asia. The *japonicas* (*ponlais*) from Taiwan typically have the desired plant characteristics, earliness, and insensitivity to photoperiod. They produce excellent yields in the Philippines, but their grain quality is considered undesirable in most parts of Asia, they lack seed dormancy, and they are difficult to thresh. In general, the

indica varieties of the tropics possess an undesirable plant habit and are late in maturity, but they possess the grain quality desired, have the needed seed dormancy, and some are resistant to diseases troublesome in humid areas.

The Institute's varietal improvement program is designed (a) to identify, or to develop by hybridization, varieties showing improvement in the desired characteristics, (b) to develop improved rice breeding methods and techniques, (c) to develop information on lodging, and (d) to acquire genetic information of value to rice breeding.

VARIETY TESTING AND DEVELOPMENT

World Collection of Varieties

An additional 2,563 cultivated varieties were received during the year, increasing the collection total to 9,430. Classification and long-term seed storage of each accession are being accomplished at the rate of approximately 2,000 varieties per year. During the year, the Institute shipped 2,296 seed lots from this collection to 26 institutions in 17 countries.

This collection, by several times the largest in existence, represents most of the variability existing in all of the rice-producing areas of the world. The further collection of glutinous varieties has been initiated in Thailand through a cooperative project with the Rice Department, Bangkok.

During the year, 436 strains of *Oryza* species and 127 mutants and testers were received, bringing the total number of genetic stocks to 1,194. Following acquisition, the various strains were grown for observation and seed increase. Each strain was re-identified, based on morphological characters, to insure appropriate designation. In the case of *Oryza* species, cytological determination of somatic chromosome numbers was often used as an ad-

ditional classification tool. Herbarium specimens were collected from each of the re-identified entries.

Among the five strains of *O. punctata* Kotschy ex Steud. received, all five were tetraploid forms. This observation is useful in distinguishing *O. punctata* from the diploid *O. officinalis* Wall. ex Watt which has similar characteristics. The somatic chromosome number of *O. longiglumis* Jansen was found to be 24. This was not known previously.

During the same period, 155 lots of seed and 19 cuttings of testers and species were sent to seven requesting institutions in five countries. A botanical garden was set up adjacent to the Plant Experimentation Center to display the 27 species and subspecies of *Oryza* which represent the principal taxa of the genus.

Varietal Testing

During the year, the Institute's world collection of varieties was continuously searched for the most promising material, and 669 selected varieties were observed at two nitrogen levels. A second planting of 480 of the best of these is underway and discarding will continue until

only superior material remains. These varieties will form the nucleus of parental material for hybridization or for possible direct commercial use.

Eighty standard commercial varieties from Asia and the United States, including 19 Taiwan *japonicas*, were tested for two seasons in replicated yield trials. None of the *indica* varieties was superior in yield to Peta, a well-known *indica* from the Philippines. The earlier-maturing *japonica* group yielded better than the *indicas*, and a few were superior or equal to Peta in yield.

A duplicate set of 60 *indica* varieties was planted at the Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station, Taiwan (23° 27' lat. N) in May, 1962. In each trial, two local varieties were added as checks — Chianan 8, a *japonica*, and Chin-gou-tsin, an *indica*. Most of the varieties from tropical Asia were late maturing. Thirty-one of these varieties were harvested in November and

December, 1962; six others matured in January, 1963. The seed set in these varieties was generally poor because of low temperatures in November, December, and January. Hence, none of the southeast Asian varieties exceeded Taiwan's Chin-gou-tsin in grain yield. The yield of Chianan 8 in these trials also was low, because of unfavorable competition with the tall and lodging *indicas* grown next to it.

Development of Improved Varieties

In May, 1963, approximately 10,000 seedlings of each of 29 F₂ populations of *indica* and *indica* x *japonica* crosses were subjected to a severe blast epidemic in nursery beds, and about 5,000 resistant seedlings of each cross were transplanted to form F₂ bulks. A modified bulk breeding method, in which obviously undesirable plants are removed from the bulks and the better plants are harvested, is followed.

THE INSTITUTE PLANT BREEDER stresses need for improved rice varieties in session with field day visitors.

PLANT BREEDERS GROW PARENT VARIETIES for hybridization in this screen house.

Eighteen backcross F_1 populations of about 75 plants each, in which the recurrent parent has stiff straw, are being grown. Short stature and erect leaf types are being selected to form F_2 bulks. Six similar populations, differing in that the recurrent parent is an adapted but tall, weak-strawed variety, were produced for comparison of reciprocal parentage on appearance of desirable phenotypes in segregating generations.

Partial Sterility in *Indica* x *Japonica* Hybrids

Although the partial sterility that is characteristic of intervarietal hybrids between *indica* and *japonica* races has been the subject of a great deal of research, there are still several issues which lack critical evidence. This project is designed to provide information relating specifically to the following problems.

a. The relationship between percentage

of stainable pollen and percentage of florets setting seed in partially sterile hybrids.

- b. The role of cytoplasm in inter-varietal hybrid sterility.
- c. The influence of difference in dates of flowering on degree of sterility.
- d. The relative frequency in which sterility occurs among hybrids of different *indica* and *japonica* parents.
- e. The genetic behavior of a group of crosses which differ greatly in degree of sterility in the F_1 generation.
- f. The effect of sterility on the ability to bring desirable characters from separate parents into combination in a breeding program.
- g. The effect of sterility on the ability to obtain strains which have higher yielding capacity than either of the parents involved.

The parental material consists of 13 *indica* and 14 *japonica* varieties. Most of the parents are strictly representative of

the race under which they are classified. However, a few are known to possess some germ plasm from a race other than the one in which they are classified.

Crosses and reciprocals involving each of the *indica* parents with each of the *japonica* parents, a total of 182 different hybrid combinations or 364 crosses including reciprocals, were made. From 15 to 20 F₁ plants were grown of each hybrid combination excepting a few in which fewer F₁ seeds were obtained.

Material for pollen grain studies and for seed set has been harvested from the main culm of each F₁ hybrid plant, and fertility counts are underway.

Upland vs. Lowland Varieties

The distinction between "upland" and "lowland" rice is not well understood. In the tropical areas, upland rice generally is directly planted in fields that cannot be irrigated because of altitude or lack of water-retaining levees. In the Philippines, much of the so-called upland rice grows and matures within the span of the rainy season. Upland varieties generally are described as short-growing varieties which give satisfactory yield under the above cultural practice as compared to that of lowland varieties under the same management. Drouth resistance often is mentioned as one of the objectives in the breeding of upland rice.

To compare the drouth resistance of upland varieties with that of lowland varieties, 61 varieties of the so-called upland types from China, Japan, Philippines, and Thailand were tested alongside 14 lowland varieties of tropical origin. Replicated groups of plants were grown in clay pots together with *Mimosa pudica* L. plants during March-May. When the rice seedlings had reached the tillering stage, the addition of water was stopped until the *Mimosa* plants ceased to respond to external mechanical stimuli. At this point, the water content of Maahas clay in the pots

had reached the wilting point (20 percent). Water was withheld for another 48 hours (18 percent soil moisture) and then applied to the pot.

Rice varieties showed varying degrees of injury, mainly in the death of older leaves and the apex of younger leaves. The drouth-resistant varieties would recover within 24 hours. In susceptible ones, the whole plant might succumb, a few tillers would die or the plant would not produce panicles. Thus, a range of plant reactions to drouth can be recorded. The 75 test varieties distributed as follows:

Group	Rating of drouth damage (slight - serious)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6 (dead)
Upland	1	4	8	1	30	17
Lowland	2	1	2	3	2	4

Actually, the lowland varieties Peta and Bir-me-fen were as drouth-resistant as the most resistant entry of the so-called upland group, N.A.R.B. There was a wide range of variation in drouth resistance in both groups. A higher proportion of the upland varieties fell under the susceptible category (class 5 and 6). Thus, drouth resistance was not necessarily correlated with the cultural classification of rice varieties.

The effect of cultural practices upon the growth characteristics of the above varieties was studied under upland and lowland field conditions. The maturity and leaf number of both groups were least affected by cultural practices, whereas tiller number and panicle weight were most markedly influenced by cultural differences. The weight of 100-grain samples showed an intermediate range of variation.

With three exceptions, upland and lowland varieties alike had higher tiller numbers and gave higher grain yields under lowland culture. When values for tiller number and grain yield were plotted against the rating for drouth resistance, the scatter distribution patterns indicated

a lack of association between drought resistance and the decline or increase in growth resulting from the cultural practice. However, within the lowland group, all entries produced lower tiller numbers and grain yield when grown under upland conditions.

This experiment demonstrates a lack of association of drought resistance with cul-

tural classification of varieties or with relative changes in vegetative and reproductive growth because of cultural differences. It also points to the need for a better understanding of the growth behavior associated with adaptability for upland culture before breeding objectives and procedures for the improvement of upland varieties can be formulated.

BREEDING METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

Floret Emasculation Studies

Any of the commonly used techniques of floret emasculation are satisfactory when few crossed seeds are needed. Each, however, is unsatisfactory for the large numbers of hybridizations required for back-cross breeding and certain special studies. A modified clipping method has been developed in which florets are clipped in the afternoon below the anthers. Florets are reclipped immediately or the following morning to remove filaments and to allow pollination by shaking panicles of the pollen parent over the clipped florets.

An extremely large number of crosses involving parents of widely varying grain sizes was made to test the effectiveness of the method (Table 1). The overall seed set of 38.63 percent is excellent and compares favorably with published results from other emasculation techniques. All crosses were made during the hot, dry period of February-April when the expected seed set is low. The crosses involving Japanese varieties showed lower seed

set because the varieties were stunted by the short photoperiods and high temperature, and their panicles were small and partially sterile. All results were obtained from panicles averaging 52 clipped florets; this large number likely interfered with the pollination of the lower florets by dusting. Consequently, fewer florets per panicle, use of normally fertile parents, and crossing during more humid periods would likely improve the results.

The time required to clip, reclip, and pollinate a panicle of 50 florets is approximately 11 minutes. This is faster by three to six times than any other technique known. Of even greater appeal is the ability to emasculate florets in afternoons, reclip at once and use the entire period of blooming for pollinations. Emasculation by hot water or air requires pollination immediately after emasculation before florets close and, thus severely limits the number of crosses possible during the blooming period.

The F_1 seeds developed from this technique are poorly formed because of lemma and palea removal. Seeds were surface sterilized, germinated, held in flats for 2 weeks, and transplanted. From 7,555 F_1 seeds sown, 7,141 F_1 seedlings were obtained. The extremely high percentage (about 94 percent) of F_1 plants from sown seeds eliminates any objection to the appearance of the F_1 seed.

Table 1. Results of floret clipping studies.

Cross	Florets clipped	Seeds set	Seeds set (%)
<i>indica</i> x Japan <i>japonica</i>	9,407	2,569	27.31
<i>indica</i> x Taiwan <i>japonica</i>	12,414	5,086	40.97
Japan <i>japonica</i> x <i>indica</i>	9,961	3,134	31.46
Taiwan <i>japonica</i> x <i>indica</i>	13,360	6,649	49.77
Totals	45,142	17,438	38.63

About 5 percent of the F₁ plant resulted from self-pollinations. This amount is unusually high but can be reduced by further practice in clipping closer to the stigma and by practicing reclipping in the afternoon rather than in the early morning.

Breaking Dormancy in Rice Seed

Seed dormancy in rice is considered a valuable trait, particularly in tropical areas where rains frequently occur during the harvesting period. Non-dormant or partially dormant grain often germinates *in situ* under such conditions and especially when the crop lodges into standing water. Two plantings per year of experimental rice material are common in tropical breeding programs, and the available time between harvest and sowing is frequently insufficient to allow dormancy to disappear naturally. If rice is transplanted, freshly harvested seed is sown in nursery beds. Dormant seed remains in the beds and only the less desirable non-dormant seed is transplanted. Unless segregating hybrid material is treated to break dormancy, dormant phenotypes will be lost.

To satisfy the need for a rapid, safe, non-liquid technique for breaking dormancy, the effectiveness of heat treatment was investigated. Typical results are in

Table 2. The data indicate that heating at 50°C for 4-5 days effectively breaks dormancy in Peta. Seed exposed directly to heat is not injured, but seed sealed to prevent loss of moisture content is killed at the longer heating periods.

To further test the results, a group of 27 *indica* varieties, varying in grain size and country of origin, were treated at 49°C for 4 days (Table 3). The heat treatment successfully broke dormancy in most of the 27 varieties. Five varieties, however, germinated under 50 percent after treatment, and dormancy in the variety Seraup 27 was only slightly broken. Three non-dormant varieties, which germinated normally after treatment, were identified.

Since Seraup 27 seemed not to respond to treatments effective for other varieties, it was treated for longer periods of time at higher temperatures (Table 4). The data show that dormancy can be broken and that loss of dormancy is more a function of length of time of treatment than of temperatures used. Nine or ten days of treatment were most effective, and 50°C was superior to higher temperatures. No loss of viability was noted even after 10 days at 65°C.

These and other results indicate that treatment at 50°C for 4-5 days breaks dormancy in nearly all varieties. More in-

Table 2. Percentage of germination of exposed and sealed seed of the variety Peta following heating at 48, 50, and 52°C for 2 to 6 days.

Days Treated	48°C		50°C		52°C		Untreated Check
	Exposed ¹	Sealed ²	Exposed	Sealed	Exposed	Sealed	
	(Percentage of Germination)						
2	71	76	82	76	64	76	38
3	71	67	73	79	74	79	36
4	79	75	78	80	81	21	35
5	47	77	80	71	86	35	33
6	79	79	85	50	87	4	36
Mean germination	69	75	80	71	78	43	36

¹ Exposed: Seed placed in seed envelopes in the incubators. Moisture contents were below 5.28 percent (not measurable) following all time-temperature treatments.

² Sealed: Seed placed in envelopes inside sealed battery jars in the incubators. Moisture contents ranged between 11.46 and 12.62 percent following all time-temperature treatments.

Table 3. Percentage germination of seed of 27 rice varieties heated for 4 days at 49°C.

Variety	Origin	Percent Germinated	
		Untreated Seed	Treated Seed
Seraup 27	Malaya	1	7
Milbuen 5 (3)	Philippines	6	22
CO 29	India	7	26
Mayang Ebos 80	Malaya	1	32
H-6	Ceylon	9	46
Tjere mas	Philippines	7	56
Tangkai Rotan	Malaya	7	72
Tam Vuot	Vietnam	10	72
Siam 29	Malaya	11	77
BE-3	Philippines	11	90
H-105	Ceylon	13	81
Leuang Rahaeng	Thailand	15	74
Reyong 6	Malaya	16	71
Peta	Philippines	21	85
Lua Thuoc	Vietnam	21	86
O Tre	Vietnam	22	95
Raminad Str. 3	Philippines	23	98
SLO 15	India	27	75
Serendah Kuning	Malaya	27	87
FK-165	Philippines	29	93
FB-121	Philippines	32	76
Trang Doc	Vietnam	33	89
Taipei woo-co	Taiwan	54	73
Woo-gen	Taiwan	54	87
I-geo-tze	Taiwan	89	73
H-5	Ceylon	95	95
MTU 15	India	95	98

tensely dormant varieties require treatment for 7-10 days. Seed must be treated in open or paper containers to permit rapid loss of moisture content and to avoid injury from the heat treatment. This technique has been thoroughly tested with thousands of coin envelopes containing varietal and segregating seed. No instances

of unsatisfactory germination were noted in more than 25,000 seedbed rows.

The technique is effective, rapid, convenient, and involves little danger to viability or dormancy breakage even if temperatures should rise as high as 65°C.

Natural Selection in Bulk Populations

The bulk breeding method is not being used in many *indica* improvement programs despite its several advantages of economy, easy management, requirement of minimum labor in initial stages, and a minimum of record keeping. The bulk method operates on the principle of natural selection through competition. But, is yielding ability equated with competitive ability? It is suspected that desired types having short, stiff culms and small, erect leaves may not compete effectively against the lower yielding, tall, lodging types having large, drooping leaves.

To test the suspicion that yielding ability is not equated with competitive ability, a long-term experiment is underway. Five highly contrasting varieties were mixed in equal numbers to form four initial bulks of 5,000 plants each. Two of these bulks were planted at high and low nitrogen levels during the rainy season and the other two under the same conditions during the dry season. Each bulk will be kept separated from the others and will be planted for several seasons under the same environmental conditions.

Composition of the bulks will be traced by identifying each surviving plant during

Table 4. Percentage of germination of Seraup 27 after 2-10 days heating at four temperatures.

Temperature °C	Days treated									Mean germination
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
50	31	27	43	50	67	69	70	83	84	58
55	26	22	34	49	52	49	62	69	74	49
60	16	20	21	36	43	50	63	74	80	45
65	19	17	35	44	54	61	66	77	72	50
Check	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	10	—

flowering. The varietal composition of each bulk will measure competitive ability. Concurrent yield trials of the five varieties at the two nitrogen levels will determine yielding ability. Thus, these two sets of data should indicate the relationship between competition and yield as influenced by nitrogen and season variables.

Varietal Performance: Direct Seeding and Transplanting

Under some circumstances, it would be convenient to direct seed breeding material even though the varieties to be developed are intended to be used for transplanting. This would not be advisable, however, if it would eliminate types which would be high yielding if trans-

planted. Conversely, it is of interest to know if varieties which yield well when transplanted can also be expected to perform well if directly seeded.

Twelve varieties differing in type, tillering ability, and adaptability to planting methods were compared at two densities for both direct seeding and transplanting during the dry and wet seasons. Should yielding ability be similar, then varieties bred under transplanting conditions likely would perform satisfactorily when directly seeded. Data for the dry season, 1962-1963, are in Table 5.

As shown, no significant differences in yield were associated with the seeding densities or with the direct planting and

Table 5. Mean yields in tons per hectare of 12 varieties with direct seeding and with transplanting, IRRI, dry season, 1962-1963.

Variety	Drilled		Transplanted	
	1 gm/meter row	2 gm/meter row	1 plant/hill	3 plants/hill
Peta	4.95 ¹	4.97 ¹	5.72 ¹	5.32 ¹
Tjere Mas	4.47 ²	4.67 ²	5.04 ²	5.01 ²
Tainan 3	4.38 ³	4.12 ³	4.87 ³	5.18 ³
Tangkai Rotan	4.01 ⁴	3.86 ⁵	4.21 ⁶	4.36 ⁶
Chianung 242	3.59 ⁷	4.00 ⁴	4.26 ⁴	4.55 ⁴
Taichung (native) 1	3.68 ⁶	3.76 ⁷	4.21 ⁵	4.52 ⁵
Chianung Yu 280	3.67 ⁶	3.82 ⁶	3.54 ⁸	4.06 ⁷
Milfor (6) 2	3.50 ⁸	3.60 ⁸	3.98 ⁷	3.98 ⁸
TP Mil 45	3.29 ⁹	3.48 ⁹	3.25 ⁹	3.69 ⁹
FB-121	3.18 ¹⁰	3.23 ¹⁰	2.62 ¹¹	3.48 ¹⁰
Century Patna 231	2.53 ¹²	3.07 ¹²	2.97 ¹⁰	2.97 ¹¹
Bluebonnet 50	2.83 ¹¹	3.09 ¹¹	1.32 ¹²	2.53 ¹²
Means	3.67	3.81	3.77	4.14

Superscripts from 1 to 12 indicate the yield ranking of varieties from highest to lowest within each treatment.

Analysis of Variance for Yield

Whole Plots	D. f.	Mean squares
Drilled vs. transplanted	1	2.253
Densities within drilled	1	0.417
Densities within transplanted	1	3.158
<i>Sub-Plots</i>		
Varieties	11	62.63**
Variety vs. Treatment	33	2.79**
Variety x Drilled x Transplanted	11	5.75**
Variety x Drilled	11	0.54
Variety x Transplanted	11	2.09*

* Significant at 5 percent level.

** Significant at 1 percent level.

transplanting treatments. More importantly, the yield ranking of each variety virtually was constant in relation to the other varieties regardless of the planting variable employed. For example, Peta yield was the highest, the yields of Chianung Yu 280 and Milfor (6) 2 were intermediate, and yields of FB-121, Century Patna 231, and Bluebonnet 50 were the

lowest in all planting treatments.

These data suggest that varieties adapted for transplanting might perform satisfactorily when seeded directly. The lowest yielding varieties are low tillering types, suggesting that moderate to high tillering ability is required for effective performance, at least when transplanted at spacings usually employed.

STUDIES ON LODGING

Effects of Lodging on Yield

It is well recognized that most of the *indica* rice grown throughout the tropics is unusually weak-stawed, and that this is a major factor in the low yields reported throughout this area. Of equal concern is the generally low response in yield of these varieties to added nitrogen which promotes greater growth and lodging than occurs normally.

To determine the effects of lodging on grain yield, six varieties differing in straw strength were subjected to varying levels of nitrogen during the dry and wet seasons. Data were collected from paired

plots of each variety at each nitrogen level; one plot in each pair was allowed to lodge normally and the second was supported and held erect. The objectives of this study are to (a) determine whether lodging is the direct cause of loss in yield when rice lodges, and (b) if so, to relate the amount of loss to the degree and time of lodging. Data from the 1962-1963 dry season crop are in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Grain yields of unsupported plots in percentages of plots supported to minimize lodging.

Fig. 2. Grain yields of supported and unsupported plots of Peta and MTU-15.

There was little or no lodging with Tainan 3, C22, Milfor 6, and H-5 in the dry season, and the yields of the plots supported with strings were somewhat lower than those of the unsupported plots (Fig. 1). Thus, the placing of string to support the straw was responsible for some yield loss. This was estimated and used to adjust yields for the two varieties, Peta and MTU 15, which lodged severely.

Fig. 2 shows the marked losses in yield resulting from lodging in the two weak-strawed varieties. It is concluded that lodging directly causes loss since supported and unsupported plots were equal in all respects until the time of lodging. Of particular interest is the response in yield to nitrogen in the supported plots of Peta and MTU 15. Unsupported plots lost yield in response to nitrogen once lodging started. This suggests that erectness is a prerequisite for nitrogen responsiveness and further, that erectness (stiff straw) might be an excellent selection criterion for response in yield to nitrogen.

Relationship of Lodging and Internode Elongation

Lodging commonly is associated with increased height through excess internode elongation or an increase in the number of elongated internodes. Work with *japonica* types suggests that a knowledge of varietal differences in internode elongation is basic to an understanding of varietal differences in lodging. Weak-strawed varieties showed marked elongation of internodes 3-5 (counting down from the panicle) in response to lodging stimuli, while stiff-strawed material showed little elongation in these internodes.

The Institute now is investigating the varietal differences in numbers of elongated internodes and the amount of elongation occurring in response to nitrogen in *indica* varieties. Thirty varieties differing in straw strength are being grown in wet

and dry seasons at high and low nitrogen levels. Data being recorded include main culm height, the number of elongated internodes, length of each elongated internode, the internode at which lodging occurs, and the amount of lodging.

Internode Elongation in Short-Stature Varieties

Data collected from the 1963 dry season crop show that among 67 short or intermediate and 9 tall varieties the number of elongated internodes (0.5 cm. or longer) varies from three to eight. Within each group of varieties with the same number of elongated internodes, two or more sub-groupings can be made, in which varieties with unequal culm length showed a proportional distribution of internodal length. Thus, varieties of each sub-group had a definite pattern of internode elongation despite differences in culm length. Comparison with data obtained from a number of varieties in the wet season indicated that culm length and number of elongated internodes were more variable than the elongation pattern in different seasons. This suggests that the pattern of internode elongation probably is a highly heritable trait.

Sixteen of the short-statured strains, originating from irradiated seed, were obtained from the Rice-Pasture Experiment Station, Beaumont, Texas, U.S.A. Most of these strains possess high levels of straw strength and appear promising as parents in a breeding program. However, sterility has been observed in most of the lines. The spikelet sterility ranged from 8.2 to 73.1 percent with an average of 27.5 percent. The cause and nature of the sterility is being investigated.

Varietal Differences in Straw Strength

To determine plant characteristics associated with resistance to lodging, 20 varieties, with varying degrees of straw

strength, were grown in the dry season under two levels of added nitrogen (0 and 120 kg.). A number of plant characteristics were studied in detail.

Preliminary field observations indicated that most of the bending over or buckling of rice culms occurred at the two lower elongated internodes above soil level which were generally longer than 4 cm. Internodes shorter than 4 cm. were difficult to break even with mechanical devices. Therefore, measurements on culm diameters, weight per unit length of culm, and breaking strength were taken from the two basal internodes (BI_1 and BI_2) which were more than 4 cm. in length.

To minimize variation among tillers of the same plant, data were collected from the main culm at about 20 days following heading. In addition, cross- and longitudinal-sections of the culms were sectioned, stained, and microscopically examined for structural differences. Measurements obtained so far are not sufficient to account fully for varietal differences in lodging resistance. The data do provide information on certain plant characteristics or their combinations which are associated with lodging resistance.

The rice culm essentially is a hollow tube with septums (nodes) interposed between adjoining internodes, moving freely about a fixed axis, the grounded parts of the plant. The structural strength of rice culms can be partly indicated by the slenderness ratio (l/r) which is the quotient between the length of the culm and the radius of the culm at BI_1 . The 20 varieties differed highly significantly in their culm diameters (Fig. 3) and culm length. Data obtained in the dry season indicated that *indica* varieties with slenderness ratios greater than 600 were liable to bend or lodge. Measurements made in the wet season indicated that 600 also appeared to be the dividing line for *indicas*. This partially explains why tall varieties tend to lodge and why lodging also occurs in some short-statured varieties having culms thin in cross section and weak in strength.

The elongation of the internodes in each variety assumed a fairly definite pattern, and the variation among varieties was of sufficient magnitude to detect varietal differences. It may be generalized that varieties possessing a series of short internodes at the basal part have an advantage over those with long internodes

Fig. 3. Note the difference in culm diameters, culm thickness, and amount of persistent leaf sheaths in these 100 10-cm. basal culm sections of Early Sutarsal 39, Chianung 8, Century Patna 231, Chianung 242, and BPI-76.

in that short internodes tend to be stronger and gain more reinforcement from the septum between internodes (Fig. 4). However, the exact strength of an internode appeared to be an inherent property of the variety rather than a mere function of length. Some varieties with short in-

ternodes were rather weak in strength.

The breaking strength of culms did not appear to index closely the lodging behavior of varieties. This is understandable from the fact that breaking strength represents only one facet of the strength of culm material. Moreover, the strength of straw is derived from two integral parts, the culm and its surrounding sheath.

Varieties also differed significantly in culm density at BI_1 and BI_2 . The tall and late varieties tended to have higher culm density than the short and early ones. The association between culm density and breaking strength was highly significant ($r = 0.607$); whereas, the correlation between culm density and the lodging resistance factor (cL_r) appeared to be poor. Similarly, the cross-section area of culms computed from the outer and inner diameters did not appear to be an efficient indicator of lodging resistance.

As resistance to bending is an interaction between the bending moment of the shoot and the strength of straw, a lodging index was calculated from (plant height x tiller weight)/breaking strength. The index appeared to be a fair indicator of the plant type; tall, broad-leaved varieties vs. short or narrow-leaved varieties. The index failed to differentiate between lodging and non-lodging varieties. Again, the index does not measure the strength provided by leaf sheaths.

Many of the non-lodging varieties had photosynthetic and persistent leaf sheaths enveloping the lower internodes at the time of maturity. On samples collected in May and June, the varieties differed significantly in the number of functional sheaths at the time of harvest (Table 6 and Fig. 3).

Varieties also differed considerably in the length of leaf sheaths which enveloped the culms and in the surface coverage of the sheaths. These properties can be measured and expressed in percentages.

Fig. 4. Culms of Peta, Chianung 242, Century Patna 231, and BPI-76 with the leaf sheaths removed to reveal internode patterns. The arrows indicate the nodes.

Table 6. Average number of elongated internodes and functional leaf sheaths in 11 varieties on unfertilized plots at harvest, May-June, 1963.

Variety	Lodging resistance	Elongated internodes	Functional sheaths
Peta	Low	7	0.1
MTU-15	Low	6	0.7
Taichung 1	Intermediate	5	0.7
FB-24	Low	6	0.7
Liuchow	Low	6	0.8
Milbuen-5 (3)	Intermediate	6	1.5
Milfor-6 (2)	Intermediate	6	2.0
Chianan 8	Intermediate	5	2.5
CP 231	High	5	2.5
CP 231 dw x TP	High	5	3.2
BPI-76	High	6	3.6

The strength added by persistent leaf sheaths was indicated by breaking tests. In a Bbt-50 dwarf selection, 30 percent additional weight was required to buckle a section of the lower basal internode (BI_1) with a persistent sheath than a corresponding section of culm with the sheath removed; for the next internode (BI_2), 42 percent more load was required in the breaking test. In BPI-76, the additional strength provided by the sheath was 58 percent for BI_3 and 57 percent for BI_4 .

Study of the histomorphological features of culm sections indicated that varieties differed significantly in the thickness of the lignified sclerenchyma layer, the number of outer and inner vascular bundles, the distribution pattern of the vascular bundles, and the amount of intercellular air spaces. The two basal internodes, BI_1 and BI_2 , also differed in the thickness of the sclerenchyma layer, the number of inner vascular bundles and the distribution

of the bundles. The lodging-resistant varieties also tended to have a higher percentage of the outer vascular bundles fused with the sclerenchyma layers (Fig. 5). Usually a higher percentage was found in the BI_2 which had higher breaking strength (Table 7). The fusion of the sclerenchyma layer and vascular bundles, lignified structures continuous throughout the culm, add considerable strength to the culm. From BPI-176 culms collected at different plantings, the percentage of outer bundles fused with sclerenchyma appeared to vary with environmental influences.

Other structural features of the culm which appeared to be associated with non-lodging varieties were a circular cross-sectional shape, uniform thickness, symmetrical distribution of vascular bundles, and small compact parenchyma cells.

Preliminary observations obtained in the wet season indicated that most varie-

Table 7. Breaking strength and percentage of outer vascular bundles fused with sclerenchyma layer in two basal internodes of nine varieties grown on an unfertilized plot, April-June, 1963.

Variety	Breaking strength		Percentage of fused outer vascular	
	BI_1	BI_2	BI_1	BI_2
Peta	66.59	95.45	0.62	18.08
MTU-15	50.04	60.96	0.00	21.98
Liuchow	84.38	136.23	1.23	49.34
Milbuen-5 (3)	90.47	115.93	12.66	70.60
Milfor-6 (2)	61.70	78.83	24.92	83.00
BPI-76	89.71	113.14	38.46	88.88
Taichung 1	44.21	78.76	39.41	87.87
Chianan 8	87.10	128.90	62.03	98.79
CP 231 dw x TP	103.99	125.29	83.06	99.40

Fig. 5. Cross sections of basal internodes of MTU-15 (left) and Taichung Native-1 (right). MTU-15 has a thicker culm, larger intercellular air spaces and asymmetrical distribution of vascular bundles. Taichung Native 1 has a thinner culm, fewer air spaces, and symmetrical arrangement for vascular bundles. The outer vascular bundles in MTU-15 are not united with the dark-staining, lignified sclerenchyma layer. In Taichung Native-1 the outer vasculars are fused with sclerenchyma.

ties tended to be taller, with one to two more elongated internodes, and had thicker culm diameters, longer basal internodes, heavier tillers, and lower breaking strength. These changes resulted in a heavier load over a weaker culm, although the slenderness ratio was little affected. The above changes were reflected in the more widespread and serious lodging in the experimental plots.

Measuring Lodging Resistance

As a simple and objective test for measuring lodging resistance, the lodging resistance factor (cL_r) obtained by the use of a brass chain was most promising. The cL_r values were computed as the ratio between (a) the weight of links a culm was capable of supporting at a point of equilibrium when freely suspended from base of the panicle, and (b) the length of culm, from ground level to the base of the panicle. In the dry season when practically no lodging occurred, the cL_r estimates were the only criteria which differentiated among va-

rieties and between nitrogen levels in the same variety, as they took into consideration the resistance offered by leaf sheaths. In repeated tests with Chianan 8, the cL_r values appeared to have good repeatability. The cL_r estimates of varieties were negatively correlated with their slenderness ratios at the 1 percent significance level ($r = -0.767$). When the cL_r values obtained in the dry season were compared with actual field lodging in the wet season, the estimates appeared promising in predicting lodging behavior (Table 8).

The correlation between cL_r and actual lodging will be studied further to ascertain the value of cL_r in predicting lodging behavior.

Table 8. Comparison of lodging resistance factor (cL_r) values in the dry season with actual lodging in the wet season, IIRI, 1963.

cL_r values obtained in dry season	No. of varieties	Behavior of varieties in wet season		
		Lodged	Bending	Erect
Above 0.20	10	—	—	10
0.10 - 0.20	7	4	3	—
Under 0.10	3	3	—	—

Effect of Added Nitrogen and Spacing on Lodging Resistance

An increased supply of soil nitrogen repeatedly has been reported as the main cause of serious lodging. Others consider that close spacing results in more lodging.

In one experiment at the Institute, an identical set of 20 varieties was grown at two levels of added nitrogen, 0 and 120 kilograms. During the dry season, only three varieties perceptibly bent. However, the effects of the added nitrogen supply on the varieties as a whole were: (a) significant increase in culm length, (b) significantly longer basal internodes (BI_1 and BI_2), (c) slight (but not significant) increase in number of photosynthetic sheaths at maturity, (d) significant increase in tiller weight, (e) significant decrease in culm thickness with accompanying increase in the diameter of the pith cavity, (f) significant decrease in breaking strength of both BI_1 and BI_2 , (g) significant increase in the slenderness ratio, and (h) significant decrease in thickness in the sclerenchyma layer. The number of outer and inner vascular bundles and the percentage of outer vascular bundles fused with the sclerenchyma were not significantly affected by added nitrogen.

One of the most significant findings in this experiment was the differential increase among varieties in the length of elongated internodes, especially that of the BI_1 and BI_2 (Fig. 6). The non-lodging and nitrogen-responsive varieties, Taichung 1 and BPI-76, showed relatively little elongation of the lower internodes, despite the increase in total culm length as a result of an added nitrogen supply. In the lodging and non-responsive varieties, Peta, Milfor 6 (2), and MTU-15, much of the increase in culm length occurred at the lower internodes. This feature could be one of the factors associated with the complex problem of varietal differences in nitrogen response. Preliminary data ob-

Fig. 6. Effect of added nitrogen on internode elongation, 1963 dry season.

tained in the wet season showed similar trends.

The effect of spacing on lodging was studied from plants grown in the yield component studies. In the experiment involving four *japonica* varieties from Taiwan, the plants responded to closer spacing with a decrease in culm diameters, poorer sheath protection, longer basal internodes, and lower weight of culms. These changes were reflected in modified cL_r estimates and slenderness ratios (Figs. 7 and 8). The cL_r estimates showed a small but perceptible rise (improvement in resistance to lodging) as the spacing was increased from 25 x 5 to 25 x 10 and up to 25 x 20 cm. The difference in cL_r between 25 and 20 cm. and 25 x 40 cm. was nil. The slenderness ratios ($1/r$) indicated a gradual decrease (improvement) as the spacing was widened. The decrease in the ratio was more marked among the spacings of 25 x 5, 25 x 10, and 25 x 20 cm. There was little difference in $1/r$ between 25 x 20 and 25 x 40 cm.

Four *indica* varieties harvested from a spacing experiment in the wet season did

Fig. 7. Effect of spacing on cL_r values.

not show consistent effects of closer spacing on plant characteristics associated with lodging resistance. H-4 and Milfor 6 (2) responded to wider spacing with increases in cL_r estimates and culm diameters with accompanying decreases in culm length and slenderness ratios. Sukhwel-20

Fig. 8. Effect of spacing on slenderness ratios.

JAPAN'S PRIME MINISTER HAYATO IKEDA inspects rice plants used in studies of characteristics associated with resistance to lodging.

gave higher cL_r values at wider spacings despite concurrent increases in the slenderness ratio. Peta produced taller plants at both the closest and the widest spacings. Peta plants in all treatments lodged prior

to harvest. The slenderness ratio measured in four treatments involving Peta ranged from 583 to 632. This would be expected since the critical ratio appears to be about 600.

GENETIC STUDIES

Yield Component Studies

Four *japonica* varieties from Taiwan representing contrasting types in tiller number and panicle size were grown at five levels of added nitrogen and at four planting densities in replicated yield trials during the dry and wet seasons of 1963. Five *indica* varieties from southeast Asia were grown at four levels of added nitrogen during the wet seasons of 1962 and 1963. Similarly, the five *indica* varieties were tested under four planting densities. Data were taken on grain yield, sterility, grain/straw ratio and the three yield components — number of panicles per plant, number of grains per panicle, and weight of 100 grains. These studies were designed to estimate the heritability value of the respective yield components and to study

the effects of nitrogen levels and planting densities on yield components.

Effect of added nitrogen on japonica varieties from Taiwan. The levels of added nitrogen in this experiment were 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg./ha. The data obtained in the dry season of 1963 showed that within the range of 0-90 kg. of added nitrogen, the four varieties responded positively in grain yield to increasing levels of nitrogen (Fig. 9). The highest yield of 5,255 kg./ha. was obtained with Chianan 8 at the 90 kg. level. For all four varieties, the highest yield was obtained with the addition of 90 kg. of nitrogen, while a higher level of 120 kg. resulted in lower yields for Chianan 8, Chianung 242, and Taichung 65. The four varieties differed significantly in yield at all nitrogen levels.

Fig. 9. Grain yield in kg./ha. of four *japonica* varieties from Taiwan at four levels of applied N; IRR, 1963 dry season.

Fig. 10. Number of panicles per plant for four *japonica* varieties from Taiwan when grown at four levels of applied N; IRR, 1963 dry season.

In terms of yield components, the high tillering variety, Taichung 181, gave the highest increase in panicle number in response to increasing nitrogen levels, and the low tillering variety, Chianung 242, was the least affected (Fig. 10).

The number of well-formed grains per panicle showed a slight but statistically insignificant decrease with increasing levels of nitrogen, mainly as a result of increased spikelet sterility at higher levels. When the number of grains per panicle was compensated for sterility, no nitrogen effect was detected. The weight of grains differed significantly at the 1 percent level among the four varieties, but the effect of nitrogen levels was not significant. The grain/straw ratio of each variety remained about the same at the lower nitrogen levels but showed a significant drop at the 120-kg. level; however, the four varieties differed in their grain-straw ratios at various nitrogen levels. Consistent varietal differences in each of the yield components were more obvious than the nitrogen effect or the variety x nitrogen interaction.

Data for the 1963 wet season indicated that for Chianan 8 and Chianung 242 the highest yields were obtained at the 60 kg. level, while with Taichung 181 and Taichung 65, the highest yields were obtained at the 90 kg. level. Taichung 181 gave the highest yield, 4,251 kg. The nitrogen response curves showed a definite rise between 0 and 30 kg. of added nitrogen but at higher levels, no clear yield changes were noted.

Among the yield components, the number of panicles increased significantly with added nitrogen up to the 90 kg. level. At 120 kg. the curve for panicle number leveled off for Taichung 181 and Chianung 242 and dropped slightly for Chianan 8 and Taichung 65. At the 90 and 120 kg.

levels, spikelet sterility increased. Seed weight and number of grains per panicle were not significantly affected by nitrogen.

Effect of nitrogen on indicas. This experiment was harvested in the wet season, 1962. The levels of nitrogen involved were 0, 27, 54, and 81 kg./ha. The five varieties differed significantly in grain yield and in the three yield components. However, no significant effect related to nitrogen levels was noted in any of the quantitative traits recorded.

Effect of planting density on japonicas. The four spacings in this experiment were 25 x 5, 25 x 10, 25 x 20, and 25 x 40 cm. Four varieties were included and all received 40 kg./ha. of applied N. Results in the dry season, 1963, showed that all four varieties differed significantly in grain yield, panicle number, and grains per panicle. The effect of spacing was highly significant for grain yield and panicle number, significant for grains per panicle, and non-significant for seed weight. For grain yield, a highly significant interaction of variety x spacing was indicated.

As a group, the response of four varieties in panicle number to distance between

Fig. 11. Number of panicles per plant, as affected by spacing, for four japonica varieties from Taiwan; IRRRI, 1962-63 dry season.

hills had a linear relationship (Fig. 11). The regression of panicle number ($\hat{Y}$) on hill distance (x) is expressed as $\hat{Y} = 4.56 + 0.48x$. As the four varieties differed in panicle numbers, the regression equation for each of the varieties assumes a different function: for Chianung 242 (low tillering type), $\hat{Y} = 3.18 + 0.38x$; for Taichung 181 (high tillering type), $\hat{Y} = 0.61 + 0.81x$; for Taichung 65 (intermediate type), $\hat{Y} = 0.85 + 0.65x$; for Chianan 8 (intermediate type), $\hat{Y} = 0.02 + 0.77x$.

The highest plot yields for all four varieties were obtained at the 25 x 5 cm. spacing (Fig. 12). Chianung 242 was highest with 7,779 kg./ha. At wider spacings, the yield of Chianung 242 and Chianan 8 continuously decreased. The yield of Taichung 65 and Taichung 181 remained at about the same level at the three closest spacings; at 25 x 40 cm., the yield of all varieties dropped markedly.

Fig. 12. Grain yields in kg./ha. of four *japonica* varieties from Taiwan when grown at four spacings; IRRI, 1962 dry season.

Results in the wet season, 1963, showed similar trends. The effect of spacing on grain yield was highly significant. The highest mean yield for the four varieties was obtained at the 25 x 5 cm. spacing, although it averaged only 3,715 kg./ha. The number of panicles and number of grains per panicle were significantly affected by the planting densities. The panicle number was negatively associated with planting density. However, all varieties gave lower panicle numbers than those observed in the dry season. Seed weight was little affected by planting density, but spikelet sterility increased as the spacings became wider.

Effect of planting density on *indicas*.

Five varieties were tested in this experiment under four spacings (30 x 10, 30 x 20, 30 x 30, 30 x 40 cm.). Results in the 1962 dry season are in Fig. 13. The

Fig. 13. Grain yields in kg./ha. of five *indica* varieties when grown at four spacings; IRRI, 1962 dry season.

overall effect of planting density on yield was not statistically significant in this test, but the five varieties again differed significantly in their yields. As to the yield components, the varietal differences were highly significant for all components, and differences associated with planting density were highly significant for panicle number and seed weight, and significant for grain number. The relationship between panicle number and spacing indicated a nearly linear trend. The mean regression equation for the five varieties was computed as $Y = 5.60 + 0.68x$, where $\hat{Y}$ is the predicted panicle number and x is the distance between hills (cm.). The regression equations for individual varieties were as follows: for Peta, $\hat{Y} = 4.00 + 0.56x$; for H-4, $\hat{Y} = 5.50 + 0.58x$; for SLQ-15, $\hat{Y} = 5.00 + 0.76x$; for Sukhwel-20, $\hat{Y} = 9.50 + 0.94x$; for Milfor-6(2), $\hat{Y} = 4.50 + 0.54x$.

The above studies suggest that *indica* and *japonica* varieties definitely responded to differences in planting density. The varietal response to nitrogen was generally poor, even in the responsive *japonica* varieties from Taiwan, presumably because of high residual soil nitrogen. As a group, the *japonica* varieties varied less than the *indica*; therefore, they gave more precise results. By comparison, the *japonica* varieties had an inherently lower tillering ability and responded in a lesser degree to wider spacings, as indicated by the regression equations. However, the *japonica* varieties from Taiwan were capable of higher yields when closely spaced or adequately fertilized.

Among the three yield components, panicle number appeared to be most readily affected by change in spacings or nitrogen levels. Seed weight was least affected by the treatments. As the varieties studied herein, especially the *japonicas*, differed sufficiently in each one of the yield components at either the lowest or

the highest nitrogen level or planting density, the description of varieties by geometrical characterization of the three components in volumetric form can be attempted. From this method of representation, based on evaluation of genotypes under a range of environments, the breeder will find it possible to increase the yield of well adapted varieties by increasing the particular component which is relatively deficient in dimension and the least susceptible to environmental influences.

Genetic Analysis of Quantitative Characters

In a breeding program where the development of short-statured, nitrogen-responsive and early maturing strains is emphasized, the early and short *indica* varieties from Taiwan appear to be a promising source of the desired traits. These varieties possess a number of clearly contrasting characters when compared with the tall and leafy varieties common to Southeast Asia. The hybridization of the two contrasting types of *indica* varieties theoretically would yield recombinants which possess desirable characters from both parents without entailing the problem of hybrid sterility.

A study of the hybrid progenies from the above cross would provide information on the relationship of traits like leaf number, leaf dimensions, erectness of leaf, leaf color, plant height, maturity, tillering ability, culm dimensions, internode elongation, number of functional leaves at maturity and panicle size to yielding ability and, in certain respects, to lodging and nitrogen response. The study also would yield information on the mode of inheritance and approximate number of genes involved for traits, like maturity, plant height, tillering ability, culm dimensions, panicle number, grains per panicle, grain weight, grain size and shape, and quality characteristics.

One of the crosses selected for this purpose involved the tall, leafy, late Peta and the early, short-stature, short-grain I-g-t. The cross was made in the latter part of 1962; the F_1 's were grown in the dry season, 1963; and a population consisting of the two parents, F_1 's and F_2 's from reciprocal crosses was grown in the wet season, 1963. A duplicate population of parents, F_1 's and F_2 's, will be studied in the dry season of 1964 to sample seasonal effects on various quantitative traits. The study of F_3 populations will be made in 1964.

Preliminary data obtained from the F_1 's and the two parents in the dry season indicated that although the parents and the true F_1 hybrids have produced 15 leaves in common, they could be definitely distinguished from one another on the basis of plant height and maturity. The mean heading date of the reciprocal F_1 's was 108 days, which was 3 days longer than the mid-value of the two parents, indicating an intermediate value. In the case of plant height, the Peta x I-g-t hybrids had a mean value of 153 cm., whereas the I-g-t x Peta hybrids measured 127 cm. The mid-value of the parents was 128.4 cm., suggesting maternal influence from the tall Peta. The two parents differed in the number of elongated internodes by one internode; the hybrid plants have the same number as the shorter parent. The difference in culm height of the parents and the hybrid, therefore, can be attributed to differences in internode length.

On the other hand, the culm diameters of the hybrids were similar to those of the thick-culmed parent, Peta. However, the culms of Peta x I-g-t hybrids had a larger outer diameter than those of the I-g-t x Peta hybrids. The differences in culm thickness and culm height between reciprocal crosses were also reflected in the cL_r estimates which indicate resistance to lodging. The F_1 's had grains which were

highly significantly shorter than those of Peta and which were not significantly different from those of I-g-t. The mean grain length of the reciprocal F_1 's was shorter than the mid-parent value, indicating that short grain was dominant to long grain.

The F_1 plants showed considerable hybrid vigor in several characters. The hybrids produced more tillers and more panicles per plant than either one of the parents. The hybrids also approached the higher parent in the number of grains per panicle. On a single-plant basis, the hybrids yielded more grain than either parent.

***O. perennis* x *O. sativa* f. *spontanea* Hybrids**

In cooperation with H. I. Oka of the National Institute of Genetics, Japan, a long-range experiment has been established to investigate the change of genotypes in a population of wild rice under different cultural environments. F_1 bulks of an *O. sativa* f. *spontanea* x *O. perennis* cross were grown in two plots: one representing a cultivated field and the other simulating a natural habitat of the wild forms. Seeds have been collected from individual plants in each of the two bulks and will be used to provide subsequent generations of progeny grown successively through respective treatments.

In 1966, F_2 lines from the two bulks will be grown and compared with the progenies of remnant plants in the two original plots of ratooned plants. The impact of cultural selection upon the bulk population would be reflected in the changes in genotypes as measured by a number of plant characters which are often used to differentiate cultivated forms from wild forms. Such data might indicate the evolutionary pathway in which the domestication of wild growing forms had occurred.

THE PLANT PHYSIOLOGIST SUPERVISES transplanting of seedlings in his experimental plots.

Plant Physiology

During the past 2 years, the physiologists have studied the cultural practices which contribute to maximum rice yields in the tropics. Of particular importance, for each variety, are (a) application of suitable amounts of nitrogen at the optimum growth stage of the rice, (b) correct spacing of plants in the field, and (c) determination of the optimum planting season.

Evidence clearly indicates that varieties of different growth habits require different field management practices, and the initial results obtained at the Institute were published in the 1961-1962 Annual Report. There is a continuing need to seek more complete understanding of the physiological phenomena involved in the response of rice to various cultural practices.

The Institute has used three varieties frequently in the physiological studies re-

ported, choosing these because they are reasonably representative of the major types of rice of interest in the tropics.

The Philippine variety Peta is typical of many of the tall, weak-strawed, leafy varieties now extensively planted in the tropics. It is weakly sensitive to photoperiod; that is, it does not vary greatly in length of growing period when planted at different times of the year. Information reported on this variety should apply to other varieties of this type under conditions similar to those at Los Baños.

Tainan-3 is a *japonica* variety from Taiwan. It has relatively short, stiff straw. Its plant type approaches that believed to be required to achieve high yields per hectare per year in the tropics. It is relatively insensitive to photoperiod (day-length). Unfortunately, it cannot be recommended for use by farmers in the tropics, it lacks seed dormancy and has a *japonica* grain

quality. Nevertheless, information obtained with this variety should be applicable to similar, suitable varieties as soon as they are available.

BPI-76 is a Philippine variety which, if planted in the proper season, has relatively strong straw and is more vigorous than Tainan-3. Its growth period is markedly affected by date of planting. Usually it will flower only when the day-length is shorter than about 11.5 hours. It usually is taller than Tainan-3 but shorter than Peta.

The experimental results obtained to date lead to the few general conclusions outlined below:

1. In the rainy season, using a tall, leafy variety such as Peta, there is little hope of getting yields much greater than 4 tons per hectare (the maximum reached so far is 4.32 ton/ha.). However, by using short,

stiff-strawed varieties, such as Tainan-3, yields greater than 6 tons can be obtained with optimum spacing and proper timing of nitrogen applications (the observed maximum is 6.65 ton/ha.).

2. In the dry season, a yield greater than 7 ton/ha. is possible with closer spacing and higher nitrogen levels than are recommended for the rainy season. Proper timing of nitrogen applications is important. The maximum yields achieved so far are 8.23 ton/ha. for Taichung Native-1, 7.68 ton/ha. for Peta, and 7.33 ton/ha. for Tainan-3.

3. It is possible to produce 6 ton/ha. in any season with varieties such as Tainan-3, which matures in about 125 days in any season. By keeping seedlings in the seedbed for 25 days, the grain yield per day in the main field should be 60 kg./ha. or, assuming 300 crop days and 65 land preparation days per year, a yearly yield of at least 18.0 ton/ha.

Varietal Response to Photoperiod

A knowledge of the photoperiodic response of a variety aids in understanding its growth pattern and in predicting the regions and seasons for which it will be adapted.

Therefore, a number of varieties were subjected to different photoperiods to obtain their flowering response. Each day the plants received 8 hours of natural light, and the additional photoperiods necessary were supplied by artificial lights of low intensities.

All the varieties tested were sensitive to photoperiod since the number of days from sowing to flowering changed with different photoperiods. Some varieties, however, were much more affected by photoperiod than others (compare Norin 20 and Tainan 3 with Subang Intan 117 and Puang Nahk 16, Table 1).

The photoperiod or day length in most rice-growing areas during the cropping

Fig. 1. Flowering response of nine rice varieties when grown under different photoperiods. The broken line connected to the last mark indicates that no flowering has occurred as of that date.

season is within 11 to 16 hours. Within this range, varieties such as Norin 20 and Milfor 6(2) changed little in growth duration; so, for practical purposes, they usually are considered as "non-seasonal."

On the other hand, varieties such as BPI-76 and FB-121 changed markedly in growth duration from 11 to 16 hours, and are considered "seasonal" varieties (Fig. 1). At 14 to 16 hours of photoperiod, some of these varieties did not flower even after 200 days of growth. It would

be impossible or impractical to plant such varieties in the high latitudes. Most of these varieties come from the Philippines, Thailand, Malaya and Indonesia, or other tropical areas.

Rice plants are short-day plants in the sense that short day lengths decrease their growth period. Rice plants show no definite "critical day length," however; so it has been suggested that the term "turning point" be used instead. The problem remains of how to determine the turning

Table 1. Days from sowing to flowering, and an initial classification of response to photoperiod, of 27 varieties exposed to seven different day lengths.

Variety	Country of origin	Rate of change	Change in growth duration†	Days from sowing to flowering with day length indicated in hours						
				8	10	12	13	14	16	24
Norin 20	Japan	<10	11	57	49	48	50	48	59	57
Fujisaka-5	Japan	<10	28	64	67	64	65	71	—	92
Century Patna-231	U.S.A.	<10	10	89	99	97	94	97	—	104
Chianung 242	Taiwan	<10	19	95	102	94	99	98	—	113
Milfor 6(2)	Philippines	<10	7	95	108	108	106	111	—	104
Nato	U.S.A.	>10<20	24	77	81	78	80	89	—	101
Taichung Native-1	Taiwan	>10<20	27	78	83	84	87	105	—	97
Bluebonnet 50	U.S.A.	>10<20	37	92	80	109	107	114	—	117
Bir-me-fen	Taiwan	>10<20	47	91	73	77	86	99	120	93
Tainan-3	Taiwan	>10<20	31	107	99	97	90	104	127	121
Peta	Philippines	>20<30	87	73	74	101	109	130	—	160
Dawley 4-2	Thailand	>20<30	77	110	79	79	86	107	156	111
221/BC	Indonesia	>20<30	69	103	83	97	103	127	152	132
Sukanandi	Indonesia	>20<30	94+	126	117	113	106	120	163	✓
Norin 25	Japan	>30<40	141+	75	59	60	66	81	151	✓
Acheh	Malaya	>30<40	82	88	93	116	149	168	—	170
Guze	Taiwan	>50<50	75	59	48	50	66	117	123	120
Chung-lin-chon	Taiwan	>50<60	147	50	45	64	123	168	—	192
Podiwi A-8	Ceylon	>60<70	133+	67	76	136	✓	✓	✓	✓
BPI-76	Philippines	>70<80	148+	69	52	77	123	✓	✓	✓
Nahng Mon S-4	Thailand	>70<80	145+	68	55	79	164	✓	✓	✓
Tah Pow Gaew 161	Thailand	>70<80	139+	77	61	82	154	✓	✓	✓
Meung Naung 62M	Thailand	>80<90	137+	69	63	103	113	✓	✓	✓
Gow Ruang 88	Thailand	>90<100	141+	76	59	71	100	✓	✓	✓
Puang Nahk 16	Thailand	>100<110	132+	78	68	90	✓	✓	✓	✓
Subang Intan 117	Malaya	>110<120	141+	74	59	89	✓	✓	✓	✓
FB-121	Philippines	>110<120	150+	57	50	73	187	✓	✓	✓

* Rate of change equals the difference in number of days to flower divided by the difference in photoperiod in hours. The data reported here are the maximum rates of change possible for a variety.

† Maximum change in growth duration equals the longest growth duration from sowing to flowering minus the shortest growth duration.

Bold face numbers denote the basic growth duration.

✓ No panicle emerged after 200 days of growth.

point, which again is arbitrary.

The flowering response of rice varieties to photoperiod has not been adequately classified because of the difficulty in selecting the criteria for classification. Research workers have tried the use of "turning points," differences at two different photoperiods, optimum photoperiod, difference at two planting seasons, etc. These measure only part of the flowering response of a variety. Even the response of a variety at two planting seasons at Los Baños will not indicate reliably what its response will be when planted in the northern latitudes.

It is suggested that the response of rice varieties can be classified, temporarily, using the following criteria (Fig. 2): (a) The maximum rate of change possible with increase in day length; (b) the basic growth duration, and (c) the maximum change in growth duration possible.

Varieties with the least changes in date of flowering with different photoperiods

Fig. 2. Response to photoperiod of varieties differing in maximum rate of change, in basic growth duration and in maximum change in growth duration possible.

have the smallest "maximum rate of change" (Table 1). On the other hand, this "maximum rate of change" was highest in varieties that showed a high degree of change in date of flowering with different photoperiods. Conversely, varieties with the smallest "maximum rate of change" had smaller "maximum change in growth duration." There is no dividing line between the so-called "photosensitive" and "non-photosensitive" reactions.

Except in Norin 20 and Acheh, the basic growth duration is longer in varieties in which the "maximum rate of change" is less than 10 than when it is greater than 30.

Varieties that generally are considered "non-seasonal" fall under the $>20 \leq 30$ "maximum rate of change."

Effect of Season on Varietal Performance

In 1962-1963, Peta, Tainan-3, and BPI-76 were compared in four different seasons. The first sowing was made March 15, considerably earlier than the normal June-July wet season planting period in the Philippines. The second was seeded May 1; and later plantings were made July 13 and October 26. All plots received 40 kg./ha. each of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O and were uniformly spaced at 30 x 30 cm., with one plant per hill. Varieties differed markedly in yield per crop of dry grain (Table 2).

Table 2. Yield of dry grain, in tons per hectare, of three varieties planted on four dates, IRRI, 1962-1963.

Planting date	Grain yield (ton/ha.)			
	Tainan-3	Peta	BPI-76	Mean
March 15, 1963	4.89	3.80	4.80	4.50
May 1, 1962	4.30	4.32	5.63	4.75
July 13, 1962	5.10	3.21	4.29	4.20
October 26, 1962	5.69	6.04	2.88	4.87
Mean	4.99	4.84	4.40	

The number of days from sowing to harvest varied with varieties and with seasons (Fig. 3). The October 26 planting of Tainan-3 required 12-14 days longer than the earlier crops, probably as a result of cooler weather. Peta, on the other hand, required less time as the date of planting was delayed—a photoperiodic effect which probably was reduced to some extent by cooler temperatures. The growth duration of BPI-76 was markedly shortened with later planting dates, the March planting requiring 90 days more than the October planting; this clearly indicates the photoperiod sensitivity of the variety.

Because the different crops of the three varieties required different times to produce grain, true productivity (or efficiency of production) can be measured best by calculating the grain yield per day in the main, transplanted field (Table 3).

Table 3. Yield of dry grain, per crop day in the main field, of three varieties planted on four dates, IRRI, 1962-1963.

Planting date	Grain yield (kg/ha./day)			
	Tainan-3	Peta	BPI-76	Mean*
March 15, 1963	49.9	30.4	22.6	34.3
May 1, 1962	43.9	35.7	36.8	38.8
July 13, 1962	51.0	29.1	38.6	39.6
October 26, 1962	50.8	53.9	29.7	44.8
Mean	49.0	37.2	31.9	

The productivity of Tainan-3 was nearly constant at 50 kg./ha. per day of dry grain. The productivity of Peta was high, at 54 kg./ha. per day, when planted in October; however, in the earlier crops it was relatively inefficient, yielding about 30 kg./ha. per day. While the May crop of BPI-76 gave a rather high yield, it occupied the land a longer time, and its productivity was low.

Fig. 3. Growth characteristics of Tainan-3, Peta, and BPI-76 planted at four indicated dates; IRRI, 1962.

These data indicate that under Los Baños conditions, Tainan-3 produces satisfactory yields in both the wet and dry seasons; Peta is a good variety for the dry season, but BPI-76 is inefficient in all seasons.

It should be emphasized that all the above plantings involved spacings of 30 x 30 cm., and this is known not to be optimum for Peta in the rainy season or for Tainan-3 in the dry season. Had optimum spacings been employed, productivity might have been increased.

As indicated in Fig. 3, there was little seasonal effect on height and number of leaves of Tainan-3, but the effects were great on Peta and BPI-76. This suggests that varieties with growth habits similar to Tainan-3 can be expected to be adapted to a wide range of climatic conditions. Availability of such varieties would make it possible for farmers to grow two or even three crops per year instead of one or two as now practiced. Also, farmers would find it possible to produce satisfactory crops at any time of the year, thus encouraging them to produce crops to be harvested when prices generally are high. This would minimize the seasonal availability of rice in the market.

Nutrient Uptake by Variety by Season

There was a marked difference in the process of nitrogen uptake of Tainan-3 and Peta in the rainy season, as indicated in the Annual Report, 1961-1962; but the two varieties behaved similarly in the dry season. BPI-76 and Peta behaved similarly in the wet season. The seasonal change in the nitrogen uptake process of Tainan-3 was small. Except for nitrogen, the nutrient uptake of these three varieties did not differ significantly.

The analysis of various nutrient elements indicated that if panicles as well as straw are removed from the field, great amounts of silica and significant amounts

Table 4. Removal of nutrient elements from the field by a rice crop yielding 4.74 tons of dry grain per hectare, IIRRI, 1962.

Nutrient elements	Amount of nutrient in the rice plant at harvest (kg./ha.)		Amount of nutrient removed by 1 ton rice production (kg.)	
	Total	Panicle	Total	Panicle
N	90	48.0	19.0	10.0
P	20	13.0	4.3	2.7
K	219	11.0	47.0	2.3
Ca	34	12.0	7.2	2.6
Mg	25	9.0	5.3	1.9
Fe	12	1.6	2.6	0.3
Mn	12	2.3	2.6	0.5
SiO ₂	1780	371.0	379.0	79.0

of potassium are removed. If only the grains are harvested, the amount of silica removed is reduced greatly but the removal of nitrogen becomes relatively significant (Table 4).

These data indicate that if farmers harvest the rice crop by cutting at a high level and if most of elements in the straw are left or returned to the field as straw or after burning, an application of nitrogen will be the only element required for the succeeding crop.

Effect of Growth Duration on Yield of Rice

Varieties differ greatly in the number of days they require to produce a crop, and the periods required by individual varieties often differ markedly with season. To determine the effect of length of growing period on final yield, 40 varieties having requirements of 90 to more than 190 days were tested during the dry season, 1962-1963. This test was planted Dec. 4, 1962; all varieties received a total of 40 kg./ha. of nitrogen, and the spacing used was 25 x 30 cm., with one plant per hill.

When length of growing period was plotted against grain yield, the resulting curve indicated that the optimum growing period under the conditions of this test was 130-140 days (Fig. 4, top).

Fig. 4. Relation between growth duration and grain yield, total plant weight, and panicle-to-staw ratio.

Grain weight is the product of the total plant weight and the grain weight-total plant weight ratio. The longer the growth period of a variety, the more the total plant weight (Fig. 4, bottom). However, the rate of plant weight increase with the extension of the growth period becomes smaller if the duration is extremely long. This is associated with two limiting factors. One is the limitation in space for expansion of leaves; the leaf area index (LAI) increases with increase in growth period, while light transmission rate (LTR) in the plant population decreases (Fig. 5, top). The other factor is the limitation of nutrient supply to the plants. As plants grow, these absorb nutrients from the soil and the level of nutrient in the soil goes down. Thus, the plant becomes deficient in some of the nutrients, especially nitrogen (Fig. 5, bottom).

The straw is the product of growth during the vegetative phase, and the grain is the product of growth during the reproductive and ripening phases. Growth

rates decrease after a period of time, and the relative activity of later stages of growth becomes weaker because of the two limiting factors mentioned above. For these reasons, the panicle-staw ratio decreases as the length of the growth period increases (Fig. 4). Thus, the grain yield increases with the extension of growth period until it reaches an optimum duration caused by an increase of total plant weight. It then decreases because of the decrease in the grain-staw ratio.

Preliminary field studies described earlier (Fig. 4, top) indicated that varieties having growth periods of 130-140 days gave highest yields during the 1962-1963 dry season.

To determine the effects of length of growing period on grain yield, the yield components, and other plant characteristics, BPI-76 was caused to flower, after a predetermined length of time, by manipu-

Fig. 5. Relation between growth duration, and leaf area index (LAI) at flowering, light transmission rate (LTR) at flowering, and nitrogen content of straw at harvest.

Table 5. Number of days from seeding to flowering, yield and yield components of BPI-76 plants given different photoperiodic treatments.

Days before photo-induction	Days to flower	Mature panicles per plant	Grains per panicles	Grain yield per plant (g.)
0	49	6.8	126	16.1
20	56	8.0	120	17.9
40	81	11.0	194	38.3
60	98	10.5	190	34.8
80	116	11.5	135	29.9
100	137	10.8	133	26.6
120	154	10.8	134	28.4
LSD	2	2.00	24	4.9

lating photoperiods. This variety will flower only when the photoperiod is shorter than about 11.5 hours; consequently, length of its growing period was controlled by keeping it under a 14-hour photoperiod for varying length of time, then subjecting it to 10-hour photoperiods (Table 5).

The maximum yield was obtained with the treatment which flowered in 81 days and matured in about 115 days. The plants giving high yields also had the most spikelets and grains per panicle. Differences in filled grain percentage and 1,000-grain weight were small.

As the growth period was lengthened, total plant weight increased, primarily as a result of increasing straw weight (Table 6). The best treatment had the highest panicle weight per plant and the highest panicle-straw ratio.

The plants flowering after 49 and 56 days produced dry matter mostly during

Fig. 6. Dry matter produced by BPI-76 at various growth phases as percentages of the total dry weight at maturity. Variations in date of flowering were obtained by manipulation of photoperiods.

the ripening phase (Fig. 6). The high yielding plants, which flowered after 81 and 98 days, produced more than 70 percent of their dry matter during the reproductive phase.

There was a slight increase in content of carbohydrates (total sugars and starch) with increasing length of growing period. In the treatments flowering after 49 and 56 days, almost no carbohydrates were produced during the vegetative or reproductive phases; nearly all were produced during the ripening stage (Fig. 7). The high yielding treatments accumulated small quantities during the vegetative phase, large amounts during the reproductive phase, and sizeable amounts during ripening. With long vegetative periods, most

Table 6. Dry weight of straw and panicle at maturity, panicle-straw ratio and other characteristics of plants of BPI-76 given different photoperiodic treatments.

Days to flower	Straw weight per plant (g.)	Panicle weight per plant (g.)	Total weight per plant (g.)	Panicle weight-straw weight ratio	Height main culm (cm.)	Number elongated internodes
49	17.2	16.8	34.0	0.98	56	4.3
56	21.6	20.8	42.4	0.96	57	4.3
81	29.9	38.3	68.2	1.28	85	4.7
98	57.8	34.9	92.7	0.60	90	5.7
116	68.0	28.4	96.4	0.42	86	7.0
137	75.4	27.7	103.1	0.37	84	8.0
154	81.0	28.0	109.0	0.35	88	9.0
LSD	11.0	5.0	—	—	6.9	4.1

Fig. 7. Carbohydrates produced by BPI-76 at different growth phases as percentages of the total carbohydrates at maturity. Variations in date of flowering were obtained by manipulation of photoperiods.

of the carbohydrates present at maturity were formed before flowering, with small quantities being added during ripening.

The supply of nitrogen was limited in this experiment. Two grams each of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O had been added to the 6 kg. of soil used in each pot in this experiment. In all treatments, the amount of nitrogen absorbed by the plants was about 1.4 g., indicating that most of the available N had been absorbed. Plants with long vegetative periods absorbed most of the available nitrogen during the vegetative phase, while those with short vegetative periods did so during the ripening stage. The high yielding plants absorbed most of the nitrogen during the vegetative and reproductive phases. By the time of flowering, plants with long duration contained less than 0.7 percent nitrogen.

The number of leaves on the main culm increased with duration of the growing period, varying from 9 to 21. The highest-yielding plants produced 15 leaves. Height of plants and number of elongated internodes also increased with length of growth period.

These data suggest that when nitrogen supply is limited, varieties with relatively

short growing periods will yield the most and will make most effective use of the nutrients available.

Nitrogen Response of Varieties of Different Plant Type

To determine if varieties differ in response to additions of nitrogenous fertilizer, 13 varieties were grown with 0 and 100 kg./ha. of added N during the 1962 wet season. Varieties were planted July 3 and were transplanted at a spacing of 30 x 30 cm., with one plant per hill. All plots received an application of 40 kg./ha. of P₂O₅ and K₂O. The amount of nitrogen in the soil obviously was relatively high, as some varieties yielded 4.7-5.3 ton/ha. of grain without added nitrogen (Table 7).

The *japonica* varieties from Japan were not adapted to tropical conditions and all yields were low. These varieties produced short plants with small panicles.

The *japonica* (*ponlai*) varieties Chianung-242 and Tainan-3 are well adapted in the Philippines, and they gave good yields.

Of the *indicas*, Taichung Native-1 produced an excellent yield and responded well to the added N. This variety has a short plant, it tillers profusely, and it does not lodge. Century Patna 231 is a variety of medium height developed in the U.S. for direct seeding, and it consequently produces few tillers. The tall, leafy, late-maturing tropical varieties actually produced less grain when nitrogen was applied.

A pot experiment using the same 13 varieties, was conducted almost simultaneously in the greenhouse. The results completely contradicted the results of the field experiment (Fig. 8). The varieties (i.e. Peta, 59-368, and Acheh Puteh), which showed negative response to nitrogen in the field, responded to nitrogen better than most other varieties under pot conditions.

The light transmission rate (penetration to the base of the plants) decreased with the growth of the plants. The rate was lower inside the population than at the border and also became lower as nitrogen levels increased. This indicates an increasing mutual shading with the increase

of nitrogen level (Fig. 10b).

Nitrogen response of the plants at the border was greater than that of the plants inside the populations (Fig. 10c).

These observations demonstrate that mutual shading increases at higher levels of nitrogen, and that this mutual shading reduces the effect of the nitrogen.

A. Arrangement of Pots and Plants.

Fig. 10. Layout of the mutual shading experiment (A), data on light transmission rate (B), and panicle weights (C).

Effect of Spacing on Nitrogen Response by Varieties

On Dec. 20, 1962, a field experiment was established to determine the variety x spacing x nitrogen level interaction and to test the conclusions drawn from the pot and water culture experiments previously described. Century Patna-231, Taichung Native-1, and Peta, were grown at three spacings and with 0 and 100 kg./ha. of added N. In this experiment, spacing was the factor controlling the amount of light available to a plant. The yield data revealed several significant interactions (Table 9).

Century Patna-231, the variety with few tillers and developed in the United States for direct seeding, gave more or less similar response at any spacing, but it produced the highest yield at 15 x 15 cm. with added nitrogen. Its best yield (5.52 kg./ha.) was considerably lower, however, than the best yields obtained with Taichung Native-1 or with Peta.

Taichung Native-1, the profusely tillering short-stature *indica* from Taiwan, also gave its greatest response to added nitrogen at the wider spacings, but it also yielded best at the 15 x 15 cm. spacing, with added nitrogen.

Peta, the tropical variety which normally does not respond to nitrogen applications in the wet season, responded markedly in this test at the two wider spacings. However, the highest yields were obtained

Fig. 11. Variety x spacing interaction for grain yield, 1962-1963 dry season.

at 30 x 30 cm., with added nitrogen.

The variety x spacing interaction, ignoring nitrogen levels and number of plants per hill, is represented in Fig. 11.

One vs. Four Plants per Hill

In the 1962-1963 dry season field experiment described above, one and four plants per hill were compared for the three varieties at three spacings and at 0 and 100 kg./ha. of added nitrogen. Generally, one plant per hill was equal or superior to four plants except in the cases

Table 9. Grain yield in tons per hectare of Century Patna-231, Taichung (Native) 1, and Peta at various spacings and two nitrogen levels in the 1962-1963 dry season.

Spacing (cm.)	Variety	Plants per hill	Century Patna-231		Taichung-1		Peta	
			Nitrogen level (kg./ha.)					
			0	100	0	100	0	100
15 x 15	1	1	3.99	5.03	6.77	8.23	6.10	7.59
		4	4.37	5.52	6.30	5.79	6.88	6.61
30 x 30	1	1	3.68	4.84	6.04	7.59	6.32	7.68
		4	3.84	4.68	5.99	7.29	6.52	7.27
60 x 60	1	1	2.59	3.79	4.78	6.53	5.35	6.73
		4	2.80	4.49	4.91	6.76	5.40	6.84

of Century Patna-231 at 15 x 15 cm. with added N and of Peta at 15 x 15 cm. with no added N (Table 9).

When Tatchung Native-1 and Peta were planted at 15 x 15 cm. and 100 kg./ha. of N was applied, the use of four plants per hill, rather than one, resulted in overcrowding, and yields were markedly reduced.

In this test, the number of plants per hill was critical only at the 15 x 15 cm. spacing. At the wider spacings, either practice appeared satisfactory.

These data demonstrate the value of determining with some precision the proper cultural practices for each variety destined for commercial production.

Variety x Spacing x Nitrogen Level x Season Interaction

Tainan-3 and Peta were compared at 25 x 25 and 50 x 50 cm. spacings and at five levels of applied nitrogen in the 1962-1963 dry and the 1963 wet seasons. The two varieties behaved differently in the two seasons (Fig. 12).

In the dry season, for both varieties at both spacings, nitrogen response was observed up to 120 kg./ha. N. The best yield was obtained with Tainan-3 at 120 kg./ha. N and at 25 x 25 cm., but without added nitrogen, Peta was somewhat superior when planted closely.

In the wet season, at 25 x 25 cm., the yield of Tainan-3 increased with applications up to 60 kg./ha. N and then it decreased; at 50 x 50 cm., total yields were lower but there was a perceptible response up to 120 kg./ha. N. The performance of Peta was entirely different; application of nitrogen resulted in decreased yields except in the case of the wide spacing, in which case there was a slight response to 30 kg./ha. N, followed by decreases.

These data indicate that nitrogen response is greater in the dry than in the rainy season, particularly with tall, leafy

varieties. This may be associated with more sunshine and low temperatures along with the less leafy characteristics of the plants in the dry season.

In the rainy season, rice plants respond to nitrogen better at wide than at close spacing. Peta, in the rainy season, responds to nitrogen only when it is planted wide enough for individual plants to receive sufficient light.

It should be noted, however, that the maximum yield of Peta at 50 x 50 cm., obtained with 30 kg./ha. N, was not much higher than the maximum yield at 25 x 25 cm. which was obtained without additional nitrogen. The most probable reason for this limited nitrogen response, even at wide spacing, is the mutual shad-

Fig. 12. Effect of nitrogen levels and spacing on grain yield of Tainan-3 and Peta in the wet and dry seasons.

ing within a hill. At 50 x 50 cm. with 120 kg./ha. N, the Peta plants had as many as 65 tillers each at the maximum tiller number stage (under some conditions it can be more than 100 tillers per hill); but of these many tillers, only a few tillers per plant received sufficient light, and the rest were shaded by the tillers located at the edges of the hill.

Timing of Nitrogen Applications

An experiment on the time of nitrogen application was conducted during the 1963 rainy season to determine whether mutual shading might be overcome and yields increased by timing or splitting the nitrogen application. Tainan-3 and Peta were grown at 25 x 25 and 50 x 50 cm., using 12 different rates and schedules of nitrogen application. All plots received a uniform application of 40 kg./ha. P₂O₅ and 40 kg./ha. K₂O.

Generally, the effect of nitrogen and of spacing was similar to that shown in Fig. 12. In the case of Peta, the basal application of nitrogen had a definite negative effect, and the situation was not im-

proved either by timing the nitrogen applications or by splitting the applications (Table 10).

From these data, at least on the soil at the Institute, there seems to be almost no way in the rainy season to increase the yield of Peta significantly by changing either spacing or timing the nitrogen application. In the case of Tainan-3, at 25 x 25 cm., when all nitrogen was basally applied, 50 kg./ha. N produced a maximum yield, and there was a remarkable decrease with an additional basal application of 30 kg./ha. N. When the application of the additional 30 kg./ha. N was timed at later stages of growth, however, some slight yield increases resulted.

Leaf Characters in Relation to Nitrogen Response

Mutual shading results mostly from the leaves. Rice breeders argue that short, narrow, and erect leaves are associated with the high nitrogen response character.

To obtain comparable leaf measurements, plants of five varieties were grown in water culture at 0, 20, 80, and 320 ppm

Table 10. Yield in tons per hectare of two varieties, at two spacings, with various levels and times of application of nitrogen, IRRI, 1963 wet season.

Nitrogen application (kg./ha.) ¹	Tainan-3						Peta			
	1	2	3	4	25x25 cm.	50x50 cm.	Mean	25x25 cm.	50x50 cm.	Mean
0	0	0	0	0	5.48	3.03	4.26	4.14	4.32	4.23
30	0	0	0	0	5.87	3.78	4.83	3.45	3.65	4.55
0	30	0	0	0	5.51	3.83	4.67	3.03	3.02	3.02
0	0	30	0	0	5.41	3.50	4.46	2.99	3.06	3.03
0	0	0	30	0	5.27	3.28	4.28	3.50	3.86	3.68
50	0	0	0	0	6.15	4.31	5.23	2.23	2.40	2.32
80	0	0	0	0	4.70	4.37	4.54	1.97	2.20	2.09
50	30	0	0	0	6.14	4.43	5.29	1.97	2.39	2.18
50	0	30	0	0	6.23	4.47	5.35	1.91	2.67	2.29
50	0	0	30	0	6.65	4.63	5.64	1.74	2.43	2.09
7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	5.63	3.56	4.60	1.76	2.62	2.19
20	20	20	20	20	6.09	4.20	5.15	1.96	2.05	2.01
				Mean	5.73	3.94		2.56	2.89	

¹ Time of nitrogen application (as ammonium sulfate).

1. One day before transplanting.
2. Forty days after transplanting.
3. Five days after ear-initiating.
4. Booting stage.

N, and average data for the four treatments were determined.

The size of the flag-leaf does not seem to correlate with nitrogen response (Table 11). For example, Century Patna-231 has a long and wide flag-leaf, but the variety responds well to nitrogen. Peta, a low response variety, has a short flag-leaf. Taichung Native-1, a high response variety, has a wide flag-leaf.

As size of the flag-leaf apparently is not closely related to nitrogen response, the relation between total leaf area and nitrogen response was tested. Data on the estimated leaf area (Table 11) indicated the possibility of a relationship between total leaf area and degree of nitrogen response. Peta and 59-368 have bigger leaf areas than the other varieties.

The leaf area index (LAI) and the light transmission rate (I/I_0) were obtained on the field plots of the experiment reported in Table 9.

There was a close relationship between leaf area index and light transmission rate (I/I_0) which fit to $I/I_0 = e^{-K \cdot LAI}$ (Fig. 13). However, more precise examination of the data reveals that the points of Peta

Fig. 13. Relation between leaf area index and light transmission rate at flowering for three varieties, 1962-63 dry season.

in Fig. 13 are always located lower than the other varieties. This suggests that there is a varietal difference in the extinction coefficient (K). Average K values were 0.67, 0.64, and 1.02 for Century Patna-231, Taichung Native-1, and Peta, respectively. A big K value is related to low nitrogen response.

There is a relationship between the grain yield and leaf area (Fig. 14): the greater the leaf area, the greater the grain yield. However, the efficiency of the leaf in producing grain decreases with increase in leaf area. Furthermore, beyond an optimum

Table 11. Length and width of leaves on the main culm and estimated total leaf area per plant of five varieties, 1962 dry season, under water culture conditions.

Position of leaf ¹	Chianung 242	Taichung (Native) 1	Century Patna-231	Peta	59-368
Length (cm.)					
1	38	27	41	26	34
2	46	39	51	44	57
3	59	50	60	55	70
4	70	52	69	64	70
Total	203	168	221	189	231
Width (cm.)					
1	1.55	1.73	1.72	1.75	1.60
2	1.45	1.45	1.37	1.62	1.35
3	1.32	1.27	1.30	1.45	1.20
4	1.17	1.17	1.22	1.37	1.12
Mean	1.39	1.40	1.40	1.54	1.31
Estimated Relative Leaf Area ²					
	1.49	1.90	1.07	2.80	2.47

¹ Numbers indicate the position of leaves beginning with the flag leaf.

² Total length of leaves $\times$ mean width $\times$ tiller number.

Fig. 14. Relation between leaf area index at flowering and grain yield. Data obtained from the same experiment described in Fig. 13.

leaf area, the efficiency becomes negative. Varieties differ in optimum leaf area. The optimum of Peta is smaller than that of the other varieties, and this difference seems to be related to the large K value of the variety.

The maximum leaf area of Peta was far smaller than Taichung Native-1. Although Peta is a leafy variety, because of serious mutual shading from the early stages of growth caused by active tillering and the large K value, the lower leaves do not receive sufficient light. These lower leaves start to die, and the variety cannot have a large LAI. However, Taichung Native-1 has a small K value because of its erect leaf character and extremely short stature, the mutual shading is not serious, the variety has less dead leaves and can have quite a large LAI (as high as 8). The optimum or maximum LAI for each variety depends to a great extent on climatic conditions.

Death of Rice Leaves

A considerable amount of dead leaves has been observed in the field—more so at close spacings than at wide spacings and more so at low than at high nitrogen levels. These phenomena suggest that nitrogen and light are possible causes. Studies were undertaken to clarify the following points: (a) The possibility of varietal differences in the quantity of dead leaves produced; (b) the extent to which deficiencies in light and nitrogen cause

death of leaves, and (c) the possibility that, by chemical analyses, and by measurement of the rate of photosynthesis and respiration, specific causes of the death of leaves could be determined.

During four successive planting seasons starting May, 1962, to March, 1963, dead leaves of Tainan-3 and Peta at harvest were collected from the field plot of the experiment reported in Table 12.

The percentage of the total straw weight composed of dead leaves at the four times of harvest revealed no significant seasonal differences but a definite varietal difference (Table 12).

In another attempt to determine the cause of death, the dead leaves gathered from Tainan-3 and Peta in the July planting at booting, heading, and harvest were analyzed for various elements (Table 13).

The tall, vegetative *indica*, Peta, definitely had more dead leaves than the short, less vegetative Tainan-3. The amount of dead leaves increased as the crop matured.

The analyses of the dead leaves reveal that nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium are low. For the maintenance of adequate photosynthetic activity in the leaves the critical contents are 2, 0.15, and 1.2, respectively. However, the content of phosphorus and potassium in the active leaves was high. This indicates that the death of the leaves was most probably caused by low nitrogen content, phosphorus and potassium translocating with nitrogen as the leaves died. It may be noted that nitro-

Table 12. Amount of dead leaves, as percentage of total straw weight, of two varieties during four seasons, IRRI.

Planting date	Dead leaves as percentage of total straw weight		
	Tainan-3	Peta	Mean
March 15, 1963	19	28	24
May 1, 1962	18	32	25
July 13, 1962	4	49	27
October 26, 1962	15	37	26
Mean	14	37	

Table 13. Composition of dead leaves gathered from Tainan-3 and Peta during the 1962 wet season.

Composition	Tainan-3 at:			Peta at:		
	Booting	Heading	Harvest	Booting	Heading	Harvest
Dry weight (grams plant)	0.24	.53	2.00	8.90	14.00	38.00
Percentage of:						
N	.73	.45	.53	.44	.44	.31
P	.08	.08	.07	.08	.08	.04
K	.84	.55	.37	1.21	1.02	.70
Fe	.53	—	.36	.21	.25	.68
Mn	.67	.76	.67	.32	.31	.27
Ca	.70	.58	.58	.78	.64	.30
Mg	.39	—	.29	—	—	.54
SiO ₂	26.98	33.50	31.08	21.64	20.16	24.30

gen, iron, manganese, and silica are higher in Tainan-3 than in Peta while potassium is higher in Peta.

From the variety, spacing, and nitrogen level interaction experiment (Table 9), data on the weight of dead leaves, light transmission rate at the base of the plant population, and the nitrogen content of the plant were compiled. As the nitrogen content in the plant decreased, the percentage of dead leaves increased (Fig. 15).

The data on light transmission rate were plotted against the percentage of dead leaves (Fig. 16); where the light transmission rate was low, there were more dead leaves.

From the pot experiment reported in Fig. 10, the plants at various positions in

Fig. 15. The relationship of percentage of leaves dead to total nitrogen in the plant; 1962-63 dry season.

the population were sampled at harvest, and the dead leaves of these plants were collected and analyzed for total nitrogen. The weights of the active leaves also were taken, and the weights of the dead leaves as percentages of the total leaf weight were determined (Fig. 17). The percentage of total nitrogen in the dead leaves was plotted against the percentages of leaves dead; the resulting curve has an inverted horse-shoe shape. This relationship reveals that low nitrogen content is associated with death of leaves. However, a considerable amount of dead leaves also is found again at a high nitrogen content; death of these leaves could result from lack of light caused by mutual shading.

In another major experiment, effects of greatly reduced and controlled light on the physiological characteristics of plants were determined.

Peta plants growing in complete nutrient solution for 50 days were subjected to three levels of nitrogen, namely, 0, 20 and 100 ppm. Twelve days later, when the treatments showed marked differences, the photosynthetic and respiration rates of each organ of the plants from each nitrogen level were measured with an infrared gas analyzer.

The dry weight of these organs were then taken and photosynthetic and respiratory activity calculated on the basis of dry matter.

Fig. 16. The relationship of percentage of leaves dead to light transmission rate; 1962-63 dry season.

A set of plants growing in the different nitrogen levels were then subjected to reduced light, 400 lux above the plants, in a Percival growth chamber. After 13 days of treatment the condition of the plants was noted, and the respiratory and photosynthetic activity of the leaves from the plants grown in 0 to 100 ppm N measured. Dry weight of these plants were taken. Chemical analyses were conducted on samples of the plants growing at various nitrogen levels at normal and reduced light intensities.

Fig. 17. Percentage of leaves dead vs. nitrogen content of the dead leaves. From mutual shading experiment described in Fig. 10.

Before reduced light treatment, dry weight of the active leaves and culm-sheath was greater at the high nitrogen level than at the low nitrogen level (Table 14). However, the proportion of leaves dead was greater at the low nitrogen level.

After the reduced light treatment, the proportion of dead leaves increased, especially at 100 ppm N. This indicates that reduced light results in death of leaves and that death is accelerated by increasing the nitrogen supply.

The plants receiving no nitrogen increased in weight by 6 g. during the reduced light treatment, but the ones supplied with 100 ppm N lost more than 20

Table 14. The effect of 13 days of reduced light on the weight of various organs of 75-day-old Peta plants.

Light treatment	Weight of plant parts in grams per pot					
	Nitrogen level (ppm)	Active leaf-blade	Dead & yellow leaf-blade	Leaf-sheath & culm	Roots	Total
Daylight for 62 days	0	12.6	0.9	27.6	18.9	60.0
	20	20.1	1.0	36.5	19.4	77.0
	100	26.4	0.5	38.2	17.0	82.1
Daylight for 62 days plus + 400 Lux for 13 days	0	18.3	3.4	30.5	14.1	66.3
	20	20.5	3.8	31.4	10.4	66.1
	100	12.7	10.9	32.0	5.4	61.0

g. The loss of root weight with increased supply of nitrogen under reduced light was particularly noticeable. These figures clearly demonstrate an effect of nitrogen on the balance between photosynthesis and respiration.

Holding the plants for 13 days at 400 lux resulted in a number of changes in chemical composition, a few of which can be summarized briefly as follows:

1. Percentage of total nitrogen increased slightly, but percentage of soluble nitrogen increased markedly. As a result, the ratio of soluble N to total N was higher after the reduced light treatment.

2. Total sugars decreased sharply, especially in the 20 and 100 ppm N treatments. Starch content dropped to low levels in all treatments.

3. Amide-N was present in a considerable amount in the leaves at 20 and 100 ppm N levels, especially in the dead leaves at 100 ppm N.

4. Ammonium was higher in the dead leaves at the 20 and 100 ppm N levels.

The analyses of various phosphorus-containing compounds indicated that there is a higher amount of inorganic phosphorus and a lower amount of RNA-phosphorus in the dead leaves than in the active leaves when these are subjected to reduced light.

These data reveal that the reduction in carbohydrates, which is a consequence of the plant's inability to photosynthesize in the absence of light, leads to the degradation of proteins.

Data on the photosynthetic and respiration rates of plants growing normally and provided with different nitrogen levels indicated that, both on the basis of plant and of dry weight, photosynthesis and respiration increase with increasing levels of nitrogen (Table 15). While the leaves are the most active of the plant organs in

Table 15. Photosynthetic and respiration rates of Peta plants at various nitrogen levels.

Plant parts	Nitrogen level (ppm)		
	0	20	100
ON PLANT BASIS (CO ₂ mg./hr./4 plants):			
Photosynthesis			
Leaf-blade ¹	400	967	1518
Leaf-sheath + culm ²	36	80	145
Total	436	1047	1663
Respiration			
Leaf-blade ¹	31	61	148
Leaf-sheath + culm ²	52	104	194
Roots ³	62	94	116
Total	145	259	458
ON WEIGHT BASIS (CO ₂ mg./hr./g. dry weight):			
Photosynthesis			
Leaf-blade ¹	32	48	58
Leaf-sheath + culm ²	1.3	1.9	3.8
Respiration			
Leaf-blade ¹	2.5	3.0	5.1
Leaf-sheath + culm ²	1.9	2.9	5.1
Roots ³	3.3	4.8	6.8

¹ Measurement was made on a sample of five leaves. The data for maximum rate of photosynthesis were used. The photosynthetic and respiratory rate per dry weight was then worked out and the activity on plant basis was recalculated on dry matter basis.

² The plant portion was placed in a chamber and the change in CO₂ concentration in the passing air was read with 40 klux and without light.

³ The root was hung in a chamber and the CO₂ concentration change in the passing air was read.

photosynthesis, the roots on a dry matter basis respire at the highest rate.

On the basis of leaf area, the rates of photosynthesis and respiration of leaves were measured before and after the 13-day reduced light treatment. Figure 18 shows graphically the photosynthetic rate of the leaf samples from the plants grown with the different levels of nitrogen fertilization. Here, again, the higher the nitrogen content, the more active the photosynthesis. After the reduced light treatment, the leaf sample from the 100 ppm N treatment was practically incapable of photosynthesis while that from the 0 ppm was still able to do so, although at a much decreased rate.

Fig. 18. Photosynthesis and respiration of Peta plants before and after a 13-day dark treatment at different light intensities. The respiration rates in mg CO₂/100 sq. cm./hr were: Before (August 6) — 0 = 0.757, 20 = 1.004, 100 = 1.807; after (August 20) — 0 = 0.84 and 100 = 0.86.

The plants growing at the different levels of nitrogen differed in their ability to survive under conditions of low light intensities. The plant provided with 100 ppm N suffered greatest, and death of the entire plant was rather sudden. Under low light intensities, the plant for which no nitrogen was provided did better than any of the three.

To determine the ultimate cause or causes of the death of leaves resulting from lack of light, an experiment employing a more severe treatment, i.e., 7 days of complete absence of light, was helpful. The data in Table 16 show that the soluble nitrogenous fractions of the treated leaves were high; these were higher in Tainan-3

Table 16. The amount of nitrogenous fractions in mg./g. fresh weights in the leaves of Peta and Tainan-3 grown in the dark for 7 days as compared to those grown in the light.

Nitrogenous fractions	Amounts of fractions (mg./g. fresh weights)			
	Peta		Tainan-3	
	Control	Dark	Control	Dark
Ammonium — N	.09	.34	.09	1.16
Amino — N	.68	3.04	.85	5.13
Amide — N	.14	.36	.01	.84
Peptide — N	.44	.55	.63	.58
Protein — N	15.20	7.53	11.70	9.65

than in Peta. The lower amounts of protein nitrogen in the treated plants as compared to the control are evidence of the degradation of proteins.

The paper chromatogram of the treated leaves revealed the presence of asparagine while that of the control showed none.

These findings led to a series of tests of ammonium sulfate and asparagine as possible compounds causing the death of leaves under reduced light conditions. Detached leaves of Peta and Tainan-3 were placed in various concentrations of these solutions. The results suggest that by feeding ammonium nitrogen to detached leaves at a certain level, ammonium nitrogen accumulates in the tissue and the tissue starts to die from ammonium toxicity. While present data implicate ammonium nitrogen as a toxic substance leading to the death of rice leaves, the possible toxic effect of asparagine itself is not ruled out.

Loss of Nitrogen Through Rain or Dew

Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and magnesium are mobile in the rice plant, being translocated in significant quantities from old organs to new. The high mobility indicates that a large fraction of these elements may be in a soluble form which under some conditions may leach out of the plant.

Plants of the tall-growing *indica* variety, Peta, were transplanted at 30 x 30 cm. in June, 1962; and received 0, 60, or 120 kg./ha. N as ammonium sulfate just before planting. There was evidence of significant losses at the two higher levels of nitrogen during later stages of growth (Table 17). In the plots receiving 120 kg./ha. N, about 30 percent of the maximum nitrogen was lost.

As only the above ground parts had been sampled, and it seemed possible that some nitrogen might have been translocated to the roots. However, rice plants were

Table 17. Amount of nitrogen in the rice plant at successive stages of growth, different nitrogen levels (mg. hill).

N applied (kg./ha.)	Nitrogen in mg. hill at various sampling dates ¹				
	July 15	Aug. 3	Aug. 24	Sept. 14	Oct. 22
0	50	463	516	587	815
60	78	790	877	1056	916
120	104	908	1530	1379	1110

¹ Transplanting date, June 23; data of flowering, September 14.

grown in clay pots placed within a field population to facilitate sampling of the roots, and subsequent analyses revealed no measurable translocation from shoots to roots.

A Peta plant growing in a field plot which had received 120 kg./ha. N was enclosed in a vinyl chamber and was sprayed lightly with distilled water for 2 days. In addition, early morning dew was collected from leaves of plants growing in the 120 kg./ha. N plot. Since dew collected from metal poles in the field contained only about 2 ppm N, the high levels in the dew and in the artificial rain indicate that considerable nitrogen and potassium actually leached from the plants (Table 18).

To determine differences in nitrogen losses from young and old leaves, Peta plants were water-cultured with 5 and 100 ppm N. Four leaves from upper and lower positions were removed from plants growing at each nitrogen level, and these leaves were immersed in water, taking care

Table 18. Concentration of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in artificial rain water and dew collected from leaves of rice plants, 1962.

Nutrient	Rain (ppm)	Dew (ppm)
N	46	102
P	trace	3
K	44	156

that the cut end was not immersed. In another test, the tips of attached leaves were dipped in water in test tubes. Although some nitrogen was lost in all cases, the lower leaves from plants grown at the higher nitrogen level lost the greatest amount (Table 19). Losses of phosphorus and potassium also were greater from the lower leaves of plants growing at the higher nitrogen level.

To determine the loss of nitrogen under different conditions, Peta plants were water-cultured for 40 days in a standard solution. Three treatments then were given: One plant was allowed to continue growing in the standard solution, nitrogen was withheld from the second, and the third was placed in the dark. After 1 week, leaves were collected, immersed in water for 24 hours, then the water was analyzed. The plant kept in the dark lost a high amount of nitrogen, but even greater amounts of potassium (Table 20). The "no nitrogen" plant lost greater amounts of N, P, and K than the one in standard culture.

For the plant kept in the dark, 50 percent of the nitrogen in the leachate was

Table 19. Loss of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium from the upper and the lower leaves of rice plants.

Nutrient	Nitrogen levels in culture solutions							
	5 (ppm N)		100 (ppm N)		5 (ppm N)		100 (ppm N)	
	Detached leaves				Attached leaves			
	Upper	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper	Lower
<i>Amounts lost in mg./4 leaves:</i>								
N	0.40	0.50	0.46	4.34	0.17	0.20	0.20	0.83
P	0.05	0.17	0.11	0.37	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.07
K	0.56	0.90	2.00	- ¹	0.16	0.66	- ¹	0.67

¹ no data.

Table 20. Loss of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium from leaves of the rice plant under different conditions (mg. g. fresh leaf).

Nutrient	Control	No N supplied	Grown in dark, 1 week
N	0.08	0.20	3.20
P	0.04	0.06	0.38
K	0.25	1.50	5.20

NH₄-N, 35 percent was amino-plus amido-N, and 15 percent was in higher molecular forms. The leachate from the "standard culture" plant contained no measurable NH₄-N, most of the nitrogen being amino-N.

This tall-growing variety, Peta, develops serious mutual shading in the field under heavy applications of nitrogenous fertilizers. The upper leaves shade the lower leaves and nitrogen leaches from the latter; consequently, some of the lower leaves die. If the plants are not crowded and low levels of nitrogen are used, rain or dew is less likely to leach nitrogen from the leaves.

In regions where temperatures are lower and there is less rainfall, rice plants produce less growth and become less crowded even at high nitrogen levels. Thus, they do not lose nitrogen. Most varieties used in temperate climate areas have relatively short, stiff straw. This eliminates undesirable amounts of shading. In the tropics, where there is limited sunshine and heavy rains occur during the wet season, ordinary tall-growing *indicas* become crowded and shaded when fertilized heavily. Under such conditions, the plants lose a great amount of nitrogen and potassium. Large losses should not occur in the tropics when short, stiff-strawed varieties are used.

Leaf Function in Relation to Root Activity

Evidence presented earlier (Table 14), indicated that one effect of growing entire plants at greatly reduced light is a marked decrease in root growth. Under

field conditions, however, only the lower leaves are severely shaded. It seemed desirable to clarify the functions of the leaves, particularly with relation to root development.

First, an upper leaf (7th) and a lower leaf (4th) each of 40-day old plants of Peta and Tainan-3 were exposed to ¹⁴CO₂ for 24 hours, then were autoradiographed. In these plants, internode elongation had not yet occurred. Examination of the autoradiographs revealed that at this stage of growth there was no differentiation of function of the upper and lower leaves; both supplied the whole plant with assimilation products (Fig. 19).

When the procedure was repeated with 75-day old plants, in which internode elongation had occurred, a definite differentiation of function was apparent. The lower leaf supplied assimilated products only to the roots; the upper leaf primarily supplied the upper portions of the plant.

In another treatment, the blades of the lower leaves were cut off from 95-day old plants which had developed 16 leaves. Only four leaves remained on the main culm. Three days later, the lowest leaves remaining on the main culms were exposed to ¹⁴CO₂, as was a middle (12th) leaf of Peta. Autoradiographs suggested that the function of the middle leaf is not affected by removal of the lower leaves, and that the main function of the lower leaves as major suppliers of energy to the roots is irreplaceable.

Next, partial shading of a 40-day old Peta plant was simulated by wrapping it with black vinyl until only about 10 cm. of the upper leaves were exposed. Two days later, the 8th leaf, which was exposed to light, of the main culm of this plant and of an unshaded plant were exposed to ¹⁴CO₂. The autoradiographs revealed that the shading had greatly reduced the supply of assimilated products to the roots (Fig. 20). As shaded leaves are low in assimilation products, they retain most of

Fig. 19. Autoradiographs of 40-day-old plants, in which internode elongation had not occurred. An upper leaf (7th) of the plant on the left, and a lower leaf (4th) of the plant on the right, had been exposed to $^{14}\text{CO}_2$. Note that in both cases, assimilated products were distributed throughout the plants, indicating no differences in function of the leaves at this stage of growth.

Fig. 20. Autoradiographs of 40-day-old plants, of which the upper (8th) leaves had been exposed to $^{14}\text{CO}_2$. The plant on the right had been exposed to normal light, while the other had been shaded for 5 days, except for the upper 10 cm., with black vinyl. Note that the shading decreased the amount of assimilated products going to the roots of the plant on the left.

those produced by exposed upper leaves so that only a small part is left for translocation to the roots. In this particular test, about 24 percent of the assimilated products reached the roots in the unshaded plants; in the shaded plants, the value was only 2.4 percent.

Apparently, a shaded leaf does not retain phosphorus. The 10th (middle) leaf of a Peta plant was placed in a blackened cylinder for 7 days, after which the roots of the separated main tiller were dipped in a solution containing 33 P for 24 hours. Amounts of radioactivity in the exposed lower, exposed upper, and shaded middle leaves, were found to be 778,1233, and 77 counts per minute, respectively.

To determine the effect of shading of lower leaves on root development and activity, six uniform 53-day old Peta plants were used. Two plants continued to receive sunlight, the lower leaf blades of two plants were detached, and the other two plants were partially shaded with black vinyl. After a week, the roots were collected, dried, and weighed. The roots of the plant which received sunlight weighed 2.46 g. and the roots from plants with

detached leaves weighed 2.32 g. Roots from the shaded plants weighed only 1.70 g. Respiration rates and phosphorus absorption capacities were markedly reduced in plants with detached leaves and both were much lower still in the case of shaded plants. In all cases, shading of the lower leaves caused a more severe decrease in root development and activity than the removal of the lower leaves.

Root Distribution and Activity

In 1963, preliminary studies of root development of the *indica*, Peta, and the *japonica*, Tainan-3, were made during the dry season, a period when these varieties yield well at close spacings and respond well to high amounts of applied nitrogen.

The varieties were transplanted January 28 at 25 x 25 and 50 x 50 cm. and all plots received basal applications of fertilizer, each of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O. After 36 days, and at 14-day intervals thereafter, roots were observed.

There were no important differences in the root distribution patterns of the two varieties at either spacing or at any stage of growth.

Fig. 21. Distribution of Peta roots, 50 days after transplanting, 1963 dry season; left, at close spacing; right, at wide spacing.

Fig. 22. Distribution of Peta roots at maturity, 1963 dry season; left, at close spacing; right, at wide spacing.

At 36 days after transplanting, roots had begun to intertwine at the close spacing, indicating an early competition for nutrients. At this stage, no intertwining of roots was noticeable at the 50 x 50 spacing.

Fifty days after transplanting, the roots at the closer spacing were intermingled rather seriously (Fig. 21) and this situation continued to worsen up to maturity. At the wider spacing, roots were only slightly interplaced, and they did not overlap until maturity (Fig. 22). This pattern suggests why, at close spacing, competition for nutrients becomes serious as early as the maximum tillering stage and why, at wider spacings, competition sets in later.

Effect of High Temperature Irrigation Water

The temperature of the irrigation water coming from the Institute's deep wells sometimes is as high as 45°C. A plot, 100 meters long and 3 meters wide, was constructed with the water source at one end and a spillway at the other, creating flowing water with a temperature gradient of about 42-25°C.

By growing a uniform crop in the plot and by recording yields and average water temperatures at various points along the length of the plot, the effect of water temperature on yield was obtained (Fig. 23). Water temperatures between 25° and 32°C seem critical. Plants growing in water constantly above 38°C died a few days after transplanting. Plants outside but adjacent to the lethal zone developed narrow white or striped leaves.

Fig. 23. Average day temperature of irrigation water and the grain yield per hill of the dry season crop of rice. The open o and the solid o denote the temperature range.

RESEARCH SCHOLARS FROM FOUR COUNTRIES (Vietnam, Philippines, Thailand, and China) study various chemical phenomena associated with flooded soils.

Soil Chemistry

The objectives of the research program in soil chemistry are (a) to obtain a deeper knowledge of the chemistry of flooded soils; (b) to understand the behavior of the rice plant in its peculiar chemical and physical habitat, and (c) to evaluate and improve current cultural practices in the light of the chemistry and physics of flooded soils and the physiology of the rice plant.

Research begun in August, 1962, was expanded and continued in the following areas: (a) Chemical kinetics of flooded soils; (b) electrochemistry of submerged soils; (c) ionic equilibria in reduced soils; (d) water regime in the rice soils; and (e) physiological diseases of rice associated with reduction of the soil.

CHEMICAL KINETICS OF FLOODED SOILS

Flooding of a soil cuts off the oxygen supply of the microbial population of the soil. Within a few hours, the aerobic organisms exhaust the oxygen present in the soil water and become quiescent or die. The facultative and obligate anaerobes then take over the decomposition of plant residues and soil organic matter, using oxidized soil components as electron acceptors in their respiration. Thus begins the reduction process in flooded soils.

The reduction of the soil proceeds slowly

at first, then with increasing tempo, until a dwindling food supply or the accumulation of toxins slows the process and brings it to a halt. The reduction of the soil is accompanied by dramatic changes in the chemical and physicochemical properties of the soil that produce a highly dynamic character in flooded soils. Chemical kinetics of flooded soils thus holds the key to understanding the chemistry of flooded soils.

A knowledge of the chemical kinetics of

submerged soils is no less important from the ecological standpoint. High productivity of rice soils depends on: (a) the availability of key nutrients at the stages at which the rice plant needs and utilizes them most; and (b) the absence of toxic concentrations of reduction products, especially at the physiological stages at which the rice plant is most vulnerable to them. A study of the kinetics of submerged soils will throw considerable light on the rates of availability or loss of nutrients and production of toxic substances and also indicate the potentialities of the soil for meeting the nutrient requirements of a rice crop. Chemical kinetics is, therefore, of utmost importance in assessing fertilizer needs and avoiding physiological diseases of rice caused by reduction of the soil.

Among the important chemical changes that take place when a soil is kept flooded are: (a) The reduction of iron and manganese; (b) denitrification; (c) accumulation of ammonia; (d) increase in availability of phosphorus and silicon; (e) generation of toxic organic compounds such as fatty acids, mercaptans, sulfides, amines and other unidentified substances; (f) release of ammonium, sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium from the colloidal complex into the soil solution.

With a view to studying these and the associated physicochemical changes brought about by flooding, 31 representative rice soils from Luzon were submerged in pots in a greenhouse at a mean temperature of about 30°C, and the quantitative changes, with time, of the following properties or constituents, were studied: (a) Redox potential and pH value of the soil and soil solution; (b) specific conductance of the soil solution; (c) reduced iron and manganese and also ammonium in the soil and soil solution; (d) nitrate, nitrite, oxidizable matter, alkalinity, calcium, magnesium, potassium, and sodium in the soil

solution. The significant findings are reported and discussed below.

Kinetics of the Reduction of Iron

The most important chemical change that takes place when a soil is flooded is, perhaps, the reduction of iron and the accompanying increase in its solubility. This may be one of the chief benefits of flooding rice soils because the apparent iron requirement of rice is higher than that of other plants. On the other hand, an excess of soluble iron is toxic to rice and also may lead to adverse secondary effects, such as phosphorus and potassium deficiencies. The changes in concentration of reduced iron in the soil and soil solution, therefore, are of considerable practical significance. They are also important from the chemical standpoint for iron dominates ionic equilibria in flooded soils.

There were wide differences among the 31 soils in the changes in concentration of iron in the soil solution with time. At one extreme was an acid, latosolic soil, fairly well supplied with organic matter, that built up a concentration of 380 ppm Fe^{++} in the soil solution and more than 15,000 ppm in the soil within 4 weeks of submergence; at the other extreme was a calcareous soil, low in iron and organic matter which, at no time during the 180 days of submergence, had an Fe^{++} concentration in the soil solution in excess of 2 ppm and in the soil of 1,300 ppm. There were fairly well defined patterns, associated with soil properties, in the changes of concentration of Fe^{++} in the soil solution.

The very strongly acid and strongly acid latosolic clays and loams, containing 2.3–4.4 percent organic matter, built up Fe^{++} concentrations of the order of 300 ppm in the soil solution, exponentially, within 30 days of submergence, showed a sharp exponential decrease, and assumed concentra-

tions in the range 48-116 ppm after 171 days of submergence. The final concentration of Fe^{++} in the soil solution ap-

peared to be positively correlated with the organic matter content of the soil. The following soils fell into this class:

Soil No.	Peak Fe^{++} (ppm)	pH	O.M. (%)	Color	Texture
24	380	5.33	3.77	Dark reddish brown	Sandy loam
6	325	4.81	2.68	Dark brown	Clay
21	312	4.61	3.79	Dark reddish brown	Clay loam
28	293	4.65	2.91	Yellowish red	Clay
16	286	4.72	2.26	Yellowish red	Clay
15	285	5.27	2.50	Dark grayish brown	Clay loam
25	225	4.84	4.37	Brown	Fine sandy loam

The moderately acid, dark grayish-brown loams, with organic matter contents of 3.2-8.0 percent, accumulated soluble iron at a slightly slower rate, attained broader peak concentrations of less than 200 ppm, suffered a slower decline in soluble iron and ended up with higher

concentrations of Fe^{++} than the very strongly acid and strongly acid soils. These soils had Fe^{++} concentrations of more than 100 ppm in the soil solution for more than 100 days of submergence. The soils below behaved in this fashion.

Soil No.	Peak Fe^{++} (ppm)	pH	O.M. (%)	Color	Texture
30	280	5.64	4.27	Dark grayish brown	Clay loam
29	228	5.80	6.08	Dark grayish brown	Clay loam
22	200	5.73	3.17	Dark brown	Silty clay loam
23	137	5.73	7.99	Dark grayish brown	Fine sandy loam
13	119	5.40	2.92	Dark brown	Clay ✓

Closely resembling the soils of the last group in general trends of Fe^{++} concentration with time, but generating peak concentrations of less than 100 ppm, were

the following slightly acidic soils of variable texture and organic matter content:

Soil No.	Peak Fe^{++} (ppm)	pH	O.M. (%)	Color	Texture
5	98	6.25	2.17	Very dark grayish brown	Clay
18	91	5.60	4.95	Very dark gray	Sandy loam
16	90	6.22	1.88	Dark grayish	Silt loam
20	76	6.08	5.72	Very dark gray	Clay
9	65	6.03	3.87	Very dark brown	Clay loam
2	64	6.24	1.90	Dark brown	Clay loam

Quite distinct from the soils so far considered is a nondescript group in which the concentration of soluble Fe^{++} increased extremely slowly in a rectilinear or asymptotic manner and attained maxi-

imum concentrations not exceeding 30 ppm. These soils were low in organic matter or high in pH value, as shown below.

Soil No.	Peak Fe ⁺⁺ (ppm)	pH	O.M. (%)	Color	Texture
3	14	5.66	1.22	Dark grayish brown	Clay
10	30	5.38	1.39	Dark brown	Clay
11	30	6.38	2.02	Dark brown	Clay
17	29	7.01	1.72	Dark grayish brown	Clay loam
26	2	7.55	1.07	Dark gray	Clay
27	13	6.64	2.02	Dark grayish brown	Clay

Some typical patterns of the kinetics of Fe⁺⁺ in the soil solution are in Fig. 1. The strongly acid latosolic soils built up extremely high concentrations of soluble Fe⁺⁺ within 30 days of submergence and thereafter suffered a rapid decline, as for soil no. 6; the moderately acid soils, such as soil no. 22, showed lower and broader maxima; the neutral and alkaline soils and all soils low in organic matter had the lowest concentrations of soluble Fe⁺⁺ at any time.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Soil No. 17} &: (\text{Fe}^{++}) = 1.58 + 0.168 t \\ \text{Soil No. 8} &: (\text{Fe}^{++}) = 0.913 t - 0.0033 t^2 \\ \text{Soil No. 11} &: \log (\text{Fe}^{++}) = -0.723 + 2.596 \log t - 0.735 (\log t)^2 \\ \text{Soil No. 20} &: \log (\text{Fe}^{++}) = 0.002 + 2.500 \log t - 0.831 (\log t)^2 \\ \text{Soil No. 23} &: \log (\text{Fe}^{++}) = 0.438 + 2.235 \log t - 0.744 (\log t)^2 \end{aligned}$$

(Fe⁺⁺) is the concentration of Fe⁺⁺ in ppm, and t is time of submergence in days.

The calculated and observed figures for these soils are in Table 1.

Although the changes in concentration of Fe⁺⁺ in the soil solution can be treated mathematically and are associated with soil type, quantitative interpretation presents difficulties. The theoretical criteria available for the definition of the concentration of Fe⁺⁺ in the soil solution are redox potential and pH, but at no stage of submergence, except in the final leveling off, was there a significant quantitative correlation between the redox potential or pH and the concentration of Fe⁺⁺ in the solution, although a general parallelism was discerned.

Presumably, much of the Fe⁺⁺ in the early stages of reduction was in the form of chelates and complexes. With the destruction of the organic moieties by microbial action, the concentrations of

In view of the possibility of iron toxicity in the strongly acid soils and iron deficiency in the neutral and alkaline soils, ability to predict the concentration of Fe⁺⁺ at any time after submergence, for a given soil, would be an advantage. This can be done with comparative ease for many of the soils under the conditions of this experiment. The equations for the kinetics of Fe⁺⁺ in the soil solution for five typical soils are:

Fe⁺⁺ apparently tended towards the values permitted by ionic equilibria. The

Fig. 1. Changes in concentration of Fe⁺⁺ in the soil solution of five soils.

Table 1. Calculated and observed values of Fe⁺⁺ in the soil solution at different intervals of submergence.

Soil No.	8		11		17		20		23	
Days submerged	Calc.	Obs.								
10	8.8	5.0	13.7	17.4	3.3	4.9	46.7	51.0	84.8	85.6
25	20.8	13.5	29.5	34.0	5.8	5.4	74.3	73.8	128.1	131.0
39	30.6	34.3	35.2	36.5	8.1	7.8	74.9	75.0	128.6	129.0
52	38.6	39.0	36.9	37.0	10.3	10.6	69.9	69.6	120.6	120.0
66	45.9	47.0	36.9	34.3	12.7	12.2	62.8	62.0	109.7	103.2
80	51.9	54.0	35.9	34.0	15.0	15.3	56.0	55.8	98.9	97.4
101	58.6	60.3	33.7	31.2	18.6	18.4	47.0	48.1	84.5	81.5
115	61.5	61.0	32.0	32.8	20.9	21.0	42.0	46.4	76.3	79.0
129	62.9	61.0	30.3	32.0	23.3	24.0	37.6	44.3	69.0	71.7

exponential decay of the Fe⁺⁺ concentration from the peak values supports this view. But the highly significant and meaningful correlation between soluble Fe⁺⁺ and pH of the soil solutions of the 31 soils 143 days after submergence provides striking proof of the regulation of the Fe⁺⁺ concentration in the final stages by ionic equilibria (Fig. 2). The correlation between Fe⁺⁺ and pH is expressed in the equation:

$$\log (\text{Fe}^{++}) = 11.42 - 2.14 \text{ pH}$$

$$r = 0.649^{**}$$

Fig. 2. Relation between the concentration of Fe⁺⁺ in moles/liter and pH of the soil solution, 143 days after submergence.

The value of 2.14 for the gradient favorably compares with the theoretical slope of 2.0. Further, this expression yields a solubility product of 10^{-17.3}, compared with the theoretical value of 10^{-17.2}, for Fe(OH)₂. Because of the wide range of soils studied and the omission of temperature and activity coefficient corrections, these results are truly remarkable. They suggest that the species of ferrous hydroxide present in solution in flooded soils is ferrosferric hydroxide with a solubility product of 10^{-17.2} and not the other forms postulated.

Changes in Concentration of Fe⁺⁺ in Soil

Only a small fraction of the reduced iron in a flooded soil is in the soil solution; the bulk of it is in the solid phase as hydroxide, carbonate, sulfide, and exchangeable Fe⁺⁺. Kinetics of the reduction of iron therefore is not complete without a study of the changes in concentration of solid phase Fe⁺⁺.

There were marked differences among the soils in the rate and magnitude of the reduction of iron. Some typical patterns are in Fig. 3.

The reddish brown latosolic soils with pH values of 4.6 - 6.2, active iron contents of 2.8-7.6 percent, and organic matter contents of 2.3-4.3 percent, showed steep increases in the concentration of reduced iron during the first 30 days of sub-

Fig. 3. Changes in concentration of Fe^{++} in the soil.

mergence. The concentrations reached maximum values of about 10,000-15,000 ppm and remained more or less constant. Soils with a lower content of organic matter or active iron, regardless of pH and texture, attained lower maxima (6,000-9,000 ppm) and at a slower rate than the first group. Soils low in active iron, irrespective of pH and organic matter content, attained still lower maxima (500-4,000 ppm) at an even slower rate.

The fraction of active iron reduced ranged from 5.5 percent for a calcareous clay with 1.1 percent organic matter to 47 percent for a slightly acid clay loam with 8.0 percent organic matter and comparable active iron content.

These results suggest that the maximum amount of reduced iron in a soil is determined by the active iron content and availability of organic matter; the pH is relatively unimportant.

Kinetics of Manganese Reduction

Manganese compounds, just as ferric iron, function as electron acceptors in biological oxidations in flooded soils and

Fig. 4. Changes in concentration of Mn^{++} in the soil solution.

undergo reduction, forming the more soluble manganous compounds. Manganese is more easily reduced than iron, but the kinetics of manganese reduction is similar to that of iron (Fig. 4).

The strongly acid latosolic clays rapidly accumulated soluble Mn^{++} slightly ahead of iron, reached maximum concentrations of 60-70 ppm and rapidly declined to values ranging from 2-10 ppm after 171 days of submergence. In striking similarity to the reduction and solubilization of Fe^{++} , the moderately acid clays and loams showed slower increases, lower maxima and slower declines, and higher final concentrations than the soils of the first group. The coarse textured soils, regardless of pH and organic matter content, accumulated, in asymptotic manner, no more than 10 ppm Mn^{++} . These soils were extremely low in active Mn^{++} . Some typical changes are depicted in Fig. 4. The changes in concentration of soluble Mn^{++} can be described by equations similar to those for soluble Fe^{++} . Two such equations are given below:

$$\text{Soil No. 8 : } \log (Mn^{++}) = -3.353 + 5.489 \log t - 1.532 (\log t)^2$$

$$\text{Soil No. 16 : } \log (Mn^{++}) = -2.147 + 4.359 \log t - 1.256 (\log t)^2$$

As with Fe^{++} , soluble Mn^{++} , although ecologically significant, constitutes only a small fraction of total reduced Mn^{++} . The picture of the kinetics of manganese reduction is not complete, therefore, without the changes in concentration of solid phase Mn^{++} .

Changes in Concentration of Mn^{++} in the Soil

There were marked differences among the soils in the patterns of manganese reduction. Soils with a high content of active manganese, regardless of pH and organic matter content, showed steep increases in Mn^{++} during the first 30 days of submergence and declined slowly thereafter. Soils low in active manganese increased slowly in Mn^{++} concentration and reached maximum values which were very much lower than in the high manganese soils. Other soils were intermediate.

The overriding factor that determined the kinetics of manganese reduction was the active manganese content of the soil (Fig. 5).

Changes in Concentration of Soluble Oxidizable Matter

The soil solution of a flooded soil contains reducing substances (oxidizable matter) that can compete with rice roots for the oxygen transported from the aerial parts. Knowledge of the changes in concentration of oxidizable matter will (a) throw considerable light on the reducing stress to which rice roots are subjected at critical phases in the growth of the plant, and (b) help in the identification of reduction products in the soil solution at different stages of reduction, in conjunction with other chemical analyses.

Among the components of the soil solution which are estimated by mild oxidation with 0.01 N $KMnO_4$ in acid solution are: (a) ferrous iron, nitrite, hydrogen sulfide, sulfides; and (b) alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, simple sugars mercaptans,

Fig. 5. Changes in concentration of Mn^{++} in the soil.

dibasic, hydroxy and unsaturated carboxylic acids, cysteine, and glutathione. Since nitrites and sulfides are present in the soil solution only in exceedingly small amounts, oxidizable matter, as determined by the above method, is a measure of the content of Fe^{++} and the organic substances mentioned above.

The changes in concentration of oxidizable matter with time varied from soil to soil, both in rate and magnitude. Soils with more than 3.8 percent organic matter, with few exceptions, gave peak values of more than 20 milliequivalents (m.e.) per liter of oxidizable matter 6 weeks after flooding and declined slowly to final values of about 8 milliequivalents per liter 143 days after submergence. With a decrease in organic matter content of the soil, peak and final values for oxidizable matter decreased (Fig. 6). The highly significant correlation between oxidizable matter and organic matter content of the soil is expressed as

$$(Ox) = 0.54 + 2.48 (Om) \\ r = 0.749^{**}$$

where (Ox) is peak oxidizable matter in m.e. per liter and (Om) is the organic matter percentage of the soil.

Fig. 6. Changes in concentration of oxidizable matter in the soil solution.

Although there was a striking parallelism between the changes in concentration of soluble Fe^{++} and oxidizable matter, Fe^{++} accounted for only a fraction of the oxidizable matter. This, along with the influence of organic matter content of the soil on oxidizable matter, is shown in Table 2.

The presence of a high proportion of reducing substances other than Fe^{++} suggests that (a) the iron system may not be the dominant redox system in flooded soils; and (b) organic reduction products may contribute more than Fe^{++} towards the smothering of rice roots in highly reduced soils. Also, as the concentration of reduction products is highly correlated with the organic matter content of the soil, addition of green manure and straw is contraindicated for poorly drained soils in which reduction products accumulate.

Table 2. Milliequivalents of oxidizable matter and Fe^{++} in the soil solution of six soils at two stages of submergence.

Days submerged	39					143			
	Soil No.	pH	O.M.%	Ox. matter	Fe^{++}	Diff.	Ox. matter	Fe^{++}	Diff.
	25	4.8	4.4	22.6	2.6	20.0	14.0	1.3	12.7
	14	4.7	2.3	12.6	5.1	7.5	3.9	0.8	3.1
	18	5.6	6.2	13.7	1.5	12.2	8.7	1.2	7.5
	3	5.6	1.2	1.9	0.2	1.7	1.1	0.1	1.0
	31	6.2	3.4	13.0	3.2	9.8	6.1	1.4	4.7
	2	6.2	1.9	4.7	1.1	3.6	2.6	0.2	2.4

Kinetics of Ammonification

The mineralization of organic nitrogen in the soil stops at the ammonia stage in flooded soils because of the absence of oxygen to carry the process through to nitrification. The capacity of a soil to release ammonia when left submerged is a good index of its power to supply nitrogen to rice.

The kinetics of ammonification or ammonia release in flooded soils is important in rice production because (a) nitrogen holds the key to productivity of rice, (b) more than half the nitrogen taken up by a rice crop comes from the soil, and (c) yield of grain is highly sensitive to an excess or deficiency of nitrogen at certain critical phases of growth.

There were astonishing differences in the rates and magnitudes of ammonia release among the 31 soils (Fig. 7). Soils rich in organic matter rapidly released ammonia and reached peak concentrations of more than 300 ppm NH_3-N in the soil within 30 days of submergence. Certain soils low in organic matter attained maxima of no more than 30 ppm. Soil no. 23, with an organic content of 7.99 percent, gave a mean maximum of about 350 ppm NH_3-N after 30 days of submergence. Soil no. 2, low in organic matter, released less than 50 ppm NH_3-N in the same period.

If the small fluctuations in NH_3-N after 30 days submergence are taken as sampling errors or effects of temperature

Fig. 7. Changes in concentration of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ in the soil.

changes, and ammonia production is assumed to follow an asymptotic course, the kinetics of ammonia release in all 31 soils can be described as:

$$\frac{A - y}{A} = e^{-ct}$$

where A is the mean maximum $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ in ppm of the dry soil and y is the actual concentration of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ after t days of submergence.

A is a characteristic for a soil at a given temperature and is determined by the organic matter content of the soil, for the soils studied, according to the equation:

$$A = 14.14 + 38.44 (O) \\ r = 0.810^{**}$$

where A is the mean maximum $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ in ppm of the dry soil and (O) is the percentage of organic matter content in the soil (Fig. 8).

Perhaps equally significant, ecologically, is the time required for a soil to release half the maximum amount of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$. This period is defined by the equation:

$$\log \frac{1}{2} = -ct$$

where c is a parameter for a given soil under the conditions of the experiment and t is the days of submergence cor-

responding to half mean maximum $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ production. According to this equation for ammonia production, no appreciable increase in $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ can be expected beyond a period of about $3 \times t$.

Changes in Concentration of Ammonia in the Soil Solution

A considerable proportion of the ammonia formed when a soil is left submerged may be in the solution phase, especially in coarse-textured soils. This form of ammonia is highly mobile, is the direct source of nitrogen for the rice plant and is liable to loss by leaching. Hence, the kinetics of soluble NH_3 merits consideration.

The kinetics of soluble ammonia fortunately is the least complicated of all the chemical changes in flooded soils. Virtually unaffected, in a reduced medium, by oxidation-reduction, complex formation and precipitation reactions, ammonia in

Fig. 8. Correlation between ammonification in flooded soils and organic matter content of the soil.

the soil solution follows a path carved out by two factors: rate of ammonia production and cation exchange reactions.

As with ammonia production in the soil, the release of soluble ammonia followed an asymptotic path, but there were wide differences among the soils in the rates and maximum values. Some of these differences are indicated in Fig. 9. A sandy loam rich in organic matter built up a concentration of 70 ppm soluble $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ in about 75 days of submergence, while a neutral clay loam, low in organic matter had accumulated barely 5 ppm in the same period. The kinetics of ammonia release into the soil solution can be described by the equation:

$$\frac{A - y}{A} = e^{-ct}$$

where A is the maximum concentration of ammonia in the soil solution, c is a parameter depending on the soil, y is the concentration of ammonia at time t. For soil no. 18, the concentration of ammonia in the soil solution at any time can be predicted by the equation:

$$\log (72 - y) = \log 72 - 0.0148 t$$

Table 3 gives the calculated and actual values for the concentration of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ for this soil. Similar equations could be formulated for nearly all the soils studied.

No quantitative correlation of the A values for $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ in the soil solution with organic matter content or A values for the soil was possible because of variation in the cation exchange capacity. The ratio, A(soluble)/A(total), for $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$, ranged

Fig. 9. Changes in concentration of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ in the soil solution.

from 10 percent for soils of high cation exchange capacity to about 50 percent for the coarse-textured soils.

The study of the kinetics of ammonification has shown that (a) there are marked differences among soils in their capacity to supply nitrogen to the rice plant; (b) the release of ammonia, total and soluble, is amenable to quantitative description by an equation of the type:

$$\log (A - y) = \log A - ct$$

(c) the value for total $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ is a parameter for each soil, highly correlated with the organic matter content of the soil, and (d) sandy soils may build up high concentrations of soluble $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ and, if there is drainage, may suffer heavy losses of the nitrogen released by ammonification.

Changes in Concentration of Potassium

Since potassium is not directly involved in the reduction process in submerged

Table 3. Calculated and observed concentrations of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ in ppm of the soil solution of a very dark gray brown sandy loam kept submerged.

Days submerged	10	18	25	39	52	66	80	101
Calculated	20.8	33.0	41.3	52.9	60.0	64.4	67.3	69.7
Observed	22.9	30.8	35.6	51.6	61.0	63.9	68.0	71.3

Table 4. Relationship between increase in concentration of K⁺ in the soil solution on submergence and soil properties.

Soil No.	pH	O.M.%	Texture	Ex. K ⁺ ppm of soil	Soluble K ⁺			Soluble (Fe ⁺⁺ and Mn ⁺⁺)
					ppm start	peak	increase	
25	4.8	4.4	Fine sandy loam	140	7.6	12.5	5.9	230
18	5.6	6.0	Sandy loam	185	6.3	12.7	5.4	90
1	7.4	2.6	Loamy fine sand	100	3.2	5.2	2.0	73
28	4.7	2.9	Clay	165	2.3	7.9	5.6	342
14	4.7	2.3	Clay	108	2.4	6.5	4.1	340
31	6.2	3.4	Clay	160	3.5	6.0	2.5	174
4	6.9	1.8	Clay	60	1.6	1.9	0.3	39

soils, any changes in the concentrations of exchangeable potassium and potassium in the soil solution must be secondary effects.

Exchangeable K⁺ increased slightly in all soils after submergence. The increase was highest in the strongly acid latosolic soils rich in active iron. This suggests that the efficiency of extraction of exchangeable K⁺ by the leaching agent was increased with the dispersion of soil particles, following the reduction and solubilization of ferric compounds that acted as binding agents.

Potassium in the soil solution increased markedly, reached peaks coincident with maximum reduction of the soil, and decreased slightly thereafter. The increase in concentration of soluble potassium was most marked in the sandy soils rich in organic matter and least in the clay soils low in organic matter. The association of this increase with low cation exchange capacity and a high concentration of soluble iron and manganese suggest that it is caused by the release of exchangeable K⁺ by competing ions, chiefly Fe⁺⁺ and Mn⁺⁺ (Table 4). If the concentration of an ion in the soil solution governs its uptake by rice, then increased availability of K⁺ may be yet another benefit of flooding.

Changes in Alkalinity

When a soil is left submerged, pH and titratable alkalinity increase because of the mobilization of calcium, magnesium, manganese, and iron from the solid phase by

CO₂ and organic acids. The number of milliequivalents of H₂SO₄ per liter of soil solution required to lower the pH value of the soil solution to methyl orange acidity is a measure of the increase in solubility of these cations.

In the 31 soils studied, alkalinity increased with duration of submergence, reached peak values at 30-60 days, and declined. But there were striking differences in the peak values and in the rates of increase and decrease. These differences appeared to be associated with one or more of the following soil properties: Presence of free carbonates, organic matter content, pH, and cation exchange capacity. Some of these differences and their relationship to Fe⁺⁺ are shown in Fig. 10.

The calcareous loamy fine sand (Fig. 10, soil no. 1) with 2.6 percent organic matter showed a steep increase in alkalinity, reached a peak 45 days after flooding, and declined slowly. Of the peak alkalinity of 38 m.e./liter, more than 30 m.e. were Ca⁺⁺ and Mg⁺⁺. The increase in alkalinity in this soil was caused largely by the mobilization of Ca⁺⁺ and Mg⁺⁺ by organic acids and CO₂. In the strongly acid latosolic soils, alkalinity increased sharply and declined somewhat less rapidly, just as soluble Fe⁺⁺ did (Fig. 10, soil no. 6). In these soils, Fe⁺⁺ appeared to be associated with nearly 50 percent of the total alkalinity. Alkalinity in the moderately acid soils followed a path roughly parallel to soluble Fe⁺⁺, but the contribution of Fe⁺⁺ to alkalinity was con-

Fig. 10. Relationship between the changes in concentration of Fe^{++} and alkalinity in the soil solution.

siderably less than in the previous group (Fig. 10, soil no. 22). The relationship between soil properties and the contributions of various species of cations to peak alkalinity are shown in Table 5.

These figures show that (a) in neutral and slightly alkaline soils, alkalinity is caused almost entirely by Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} ; (b) with increase in soil acidity, the contribution of iron increases; (c) organic matter favors the development of alkalinity; and (d) residual alkalinity is highly negative in the soils where the proportion of Fe^{++} to total cations is high. The last point merits explanation.

Table 5. Relationship between soil properties and composition of peak alkalinity of the soil solution.

Soil No.	pH	O.M.%	Alkalinity in m. e. per liter						
			Total	Ca^{++}	Mg^{++}	NH_4^+	Fe^+	Mn^{++}	Residual
26	7.5	1.1	10.85	6.10	5.33	0.10	0.06	0.15	-0.69
4	6.9	1.8	12.20	4.90	6.50	0.22	0.09	0.63	-0.14
31	6.2	3.4	20.69	8.80	8.33	1.17	6.36	0.45	-4.42
3	5.6	1.2	10.85	5.30	4.33	0.20	0.42	1.64	-1.04
18	5.6	6.2	19.41	10.30	7.67	3.04	3.03	0.13	-4.76
6	4.8	2.7	17.12	5.30	5.42	1.08	11.61	1.32	-7.61

A negative value for residual alkalinity could be caused by (a) cumulative errors, and (b) overestimation of the contribution to alkalinity by some of the cations. Allowing a generous margin of 10 percent for cumulative errors, there is still a residuum of 2.5-6.0 m.e. for the solutions high in iron. This means that the contribution to alkalinity by Fe^{++} , determined colorimetrically, has been overestimated. In other words, an appreciable part of the iron in the soil solution at peak concentrations is in the form of complexes or chelates. This was subsequently confirmed in a study of the fractionation of reduced iron in submerged soils.

Influence of Duration of Submergence on Yield

Rice fields are kept flooded, by choice or otherwise, for varying periods of time prior to planting. If a flooded soil is the dynamic system that the chemical kinetics of flooded soils indicates, duration of submergence prior to planting should markedly influence the growth and yield of rice through its effects on nutrient availability and the presence of toxins.

Two varieties of rice, Chianung 242 and Milfor 6 (2), were planted at the same time in plots (Soil: Maahas clay, pH 6.6 organic matter content 2.0 percent) which had been left submerged for 4, 3, 2, 1, and 0 weeks prior to transplanting. Since the dynamics of flooded soils is intimately linked with the presence of decomposable organic matter, half of the plots was treat-

ed with a mixture of rice straw and fresh green manure at the rate of 7.4 ton/ha. at the time of flooding. Forty kg./ha. of N. as ammonium sulfate was applied at planting to the other plots to balance nitrogen release in the organic matter treatments. All plots were top-dressed with 20 kg./ha. N as ammonium sulfate at panicle initiation.

The duration of submergence prior to transplanting significantly affected the yield of grain (Fig. 11). Delaying planting until 2 weeks after submergence gave the highest yield. The increase was of the order of 1 ton of grain per hectare over planting at submergence. These differences could not be interpreted in terms of changes in $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ concentration in the soil nor redox potentials, although both followed intelligible trends during the season.

The experiment was repeated in the following hot and wet season with nearly the same relative results. Although the average yield was only about half that of the previous cool, dry season, with each successive week's prolongation of submergence of the soil prior to planting from 0 to 3 weeks, there was a progressive increase in average yield from 3.35 ton/ha. to 4.20 ton/ha.

If such substantial increases in yield are possible by delaying planting after submergence, in a nearly neutral soil, low in organic matter, and highly buffered against reduction by virtue of its high MnO_2 content, even more spectacular results may be expected with acid soils or soils rich in organic matter that build up an extremely high concentration of reduction products during the first 3-4 weeks of submergence. Although duration of submergence of the soil is an important variable that can affect yield, this factor often is overlooked in field experimentation with lowland rice.

Fig. 11. Influence of the duration of submergence of a soil prior to planting on the yield of rice in the presence and absence of added organic matter.

Practical Significance of Chemical Kinetics

The study of the chemical kinetics of submerged soils has shown that (a) flooding brings about wide differences in the availability of nutrients and generation of toxins in soils which in the dry state may show no significant differences in these respects; (b) these changes can be described by mathematical functions of the type:

$$y = a + bx$$

$$y = a + bx + cx^2$$

$$\log y = a + b(\log x) + c(\log x)^2$$

$$\log (A-y) = \log A - cx$$

(c) the parameters of these equations can be correlated in the case of certain nutrient elements and reduction products with properties of the dry soil; (d) the period of intense reductive activity is the first 4 weeks of submergence; (e) appreciable losses of even cations may occur in coarse-textured flooded soils; and (f) the dynamic nature of flooded soils is an important aspect of the productivity of lowland rice soils.

ELECTROCHEMISTRY OF FLOODED SOILS

Three important electrochemical changes take place when a soil is kept submerged: (a) an increase in pH value, (b) an increase in specific conductance, and (c) a decrease in redox potential.

The underlying causes of these changes are not clearly understood. This seriously impedes interpretation of the associated chemical changes and the use of these properties for diagnostic and interpretative purposes in rice production. A study of the electrochemical changes in flooded soils was, undertaken in the greenhouse with 31 soils, and under carefully controlled conditions in the laboratory, with three selected soils.

pH Values of Flooded Soils

The pH values of all soils decreased slightly during the first day of submergence and then increased in 2-3 weeks to values which were maintained for the next 100 days. The fairly stable maximum pH value was related to soil properties (Fig. 12).

The pH values of the soils with initial pH values of 4.6-5.7 increased sharply to maxima between 6.5-7.0, within 20 days of submergence. These levels were maintained for the next 100 days. A common feature of these soils was their high active iron content. The slightly acid soils with initial pH values of 6.2-6.6 increased in pH to steady maxima of 7.0-7.2 somewhat more slowly. Many of these soils were low in iron but high in active manganese. Soil No. 27 with an active Mn content of more than 2,000 ppm gave a maximum pH of 7.5. The neutral and slightly alkaline soils showed slight decreases in pH a day after submergence, then resumed and maintained almost their initial values. Soil No. 25 was unusual in that (a) its pH value fluctuated more than the others, and (b) the mean maximum pH value was less than 6.5. This

soil was unusually low in both active iron and manganese and high in organic matter.

The increase in pH values on flooding of the acid latosolic soils is undoubtedly caused by the reduction of iron thus,

The stabilization of the pH values of these soils at 6.5-7.0 may be ascribed to the equilibrium:

The presence of solid phase $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ buffers the soil against further pH changes. This was confirmed in a carefully controlled laboratory experiment with two acid soils; straw and green manure at 0.5 percent made no measureable difference in the final pH, despite the marked increase in production of CO_2 and organic acids.

In neutral and alkaline soils, the pH would appear to be regulated by the $\text{CaCO}_3 - \text{CO}_2 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ equilibrium, and in acid soils rich in iron by the equilibrium, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2 - \text{CO}_2 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$. In soils low in active iron but high in active manganese, $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_2$ may be the dominant factor, while CO_2 tension may be important in soils low in both active iron and active manganese.

Fig. 12. Changes in the pH of three soils kept submerged.

Specific Conductance

The specific conductance of a solution is a measure of its ionic content. It is not surprising to note an increase in specific conductance when soils low in NO_3^- are submerged, for Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} are mobilized by CO_2 organic acids, and cation exchange; also Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} enter the soil solution following the reduction of their insoluble oxidized counterparts, and NH_4^+ is released from soil organic matter. As alkalinity is a chemical measure of the content of these ions, there should be a high correlation between specific conductance and alkalinity. This is illustrated in Fig. 13 and is described for the 31 soils studied by the equation:

$$\lambda = 507.7 + 61.1 a$$

$$r = 0.905^{**}$$

where λ is specific conductance in micromhos/cm. and a , the alkalinity of the soil solution in m.e. per liter. The value 507.7 is the mean specific conductance of the 31 soils at the time of submergence.

The soils varied widely in the changes in specific conductance with duration of submergence. The neutral and slightly alkaline soils, starting with high specific conductances, attained maxima about after 30 days of submergence and maintained them or showed only slight declines. The strongly acid soils with low initial specific conductances showed steep increases during the first 30 days of submergence and declined sharply thereafter. There was a striking parallelism with the concentration-time changes for soluble Fe^{++} . In the slightly acid soils, specific conductance increased slowly, reached broader

Fig. 13. Correlation between specific conductance and alkalinity of the soil solution 39 days after submergence.

maxima intermediate between those of the acid and the neutral soils, and declined slowly.

The influence of soil properties and the contribution of the main species of cations to peak specific conductance are shown in Table 6.

These figures show that (a) in the slightly alkaline soils the increase in specific conductance is caused almost entirely by Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} ; (b) organic matter enhances the solubility of Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , Fe^{++} and increases specific conductance, and (c) in acid soils, Fe^{++} makes an appreciable contribution towards specific conductance while Mn^{++} and NH_4^+ apparently do not.

It may be concluded that the increase in specific conductance when a soil is kept submerged is caused by the mobilization of Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} in neutral and alkaline soils, and in acid soils to the increase in concentration of Fe^{++} and the displace-

Table 6. Relationship between soil properties and peak specific conductance of the soil solution.

Soil No.	pH	O.M.%	m.e. per liter in soil solution					micromhos
			Ca^{++}	Mg^{++}	Fe^{++}	Mn^{++}	NH_4^+	
1	7.38	2.55	12.3	17.2	1.4	0.4	1.4	2700
26	7.55	1.07	4.6	4.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	1300
24	5.33	3.77	10.0	9.5	12.7	0.4	1.5	2500
10	5.38	1.39	4.9	3.7	0.3	1.2	0.1	710
6	4.81	2.68	5.3	5.4	11.6	1.3	1.1	1550

ment of chiefly Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} by cation exchange reactions.

Redox Potentials of Flooded Soils

The single electrochemical property that differentiates a flooded soil from an aerobic soil is its redox potential. Aerobic soils are characterized by highly positive potentials while most flooded soils, after a few weeks of submergence, have strongly negative potentials. The high potential that this property holds for diagnostic and interpretative purposes cannot be fully exploited without a clear understanding of the physical chemistry of redox potentials in soils.

The first requisite for understanding redox potentials in flooded soils is a thorough knowledge of the chemical composition of the soil and the chemical changes that accompany the lowering of redox potentials when a soil is kept flooded. Therefore, the 31 soils of known chemical composition were submerged in pots in a greenhouse and the redox potential measured at two blank platinum electrodes permanently seated at a depth of 6 inches in each pot. Potentials also were determined in the leachate, anaerobically, in a specially constructed electrometric cell. Chemical and physicochemical changes in the soil were followed by analysis of the soil and soil solution at frequent intervals.

The potentials of the soils immediately after moistening, with free access to air, ranged from +350 mv to +620 mv, indicating the presence of a system poised at a high potential. The potentials were highly correlated negatively with pH values of the soil (Fig. 14) and defined by the regression:

$$E_h = 851.2 - 56.47 \text{ pH} \quad r = 739^{**}$$

This implies the operation, in aerobic soils, of a system with an E° of 0.85 V and an E_h/pH slope of -0.056 volts per pH unit. Since the concentration of iron and manganese in the soil solution of aerobic soils

Fig. 14. Correlation between redox potential and pH of aerobic soils.

is exceedingly small, the choice is between the oxygen system and the nitrate-nitrite system.

The thermodynamic potential for the oxygen system, $\text{O}_2 + 4\text{H}^+ + 4e \rightleftharpoons 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is given by the equation:

$$E_h = 1.25 + 0.015 \log p\text{O}_2 - 0.060 \text{ pH} \quad \text{at } 30^\circ\text{C}$$

Applying an empirical correction for the irreversibility of the oxygen potential at a bright platinum electrode, the equation may be rewritten as follows:

$$E_h = 0.93 + 0.015 \log p\text{O}_2 - 0.060 \text{ pH} \quad \text{or:}$$

$$E_h = 0.92 - 0.060 \text{ pH} \quad \text{when } p\text{O}_2 = 20\%$$

The observed values of 0.851 volts for the intercept and -0.056 volts per pH unit for the gradient, are close to these theoretical values for the oxygen system, considering that no corrections were made for ionic strength and that the irreversible oxygen potential is not a precise thermodynamic quantity. This strongly suggests that the redox system in aerobic soils is the irreversible oxygen system. The only

problem is that the nitrate-nitrite system has a comparable standard potential at a pH of 0.0 and the same E_h /pH slope as shown by the equation:

$$E_b = 0.873 + 0.030 \log \text{NO}_3^-/\text{NO}_2^- - 0.060 \text{ pH.}$$

After 1 day of submergence, the potentials of all soils decreased. This drop was most marked in the neutral soils and least in the strongly acid soils. The subsequent changes in potentials and the minimum values reached varied from soil to soil, but four broad patterns were clearly discernible (Fig. 15).

The first type is exemplified by soil no. 9 (Fig. 15). The potential dropped extremely rapidly and reached the low value of -250 mv at a pH of about 7 within 3 weeks of flooding. Soils that behaved in this manner were coarse-textured, low in iron and manganese, and well-supplied with organic matter.

The second type is represented by soil no. 28 (Fig. 15). The potential declined rapidly during the first 3 weeks, then decreased slowly, and attained a minimum of -250 mv after about 150 days of submergence. The slower drop in potential than

for the first type, in the early stages, may be caused by the higher content of active manganese, and the buffering of the potential decrease in the region -50 to -200 mv may be ascribed to the high content of active iron.

Soil no. 27 (Fig. 15) is an example of the third pattern of E_h changes. After a sharp drop in potential to about $+100$ mv in a few days, E_h decreased slowly to a minimum of the order of -50 mv after about 150 days of submergence. These soils were relatively low in organic matter and high in active manganese.

The single soil that maintained a positive E_h during the entire period of submergence was soil no. 26. It had the lowest content of organic matter among the 31 soils studied and a fair content of active manganese.

This study has (a) confirmed the role of organic matter in lowering the redox potentials of flooded soils, and (b) indicated the presence of two poisoning systems in flooded soils, viz, manganese in the E_h range $+100$ to -50 mv and iron in the range -50 to -200 mv. Any poisoning effect by nitrate was not observed, because the initial concentrations of nitrate of the soils were extremely low.

In view of the association of E_h with manganese and iron, unsuccessful attempts were made to correlate the observed potentials with the concentrations of these elements in the soil solution.

The first anomaly was that the trends of the E_h of the soil and concentrations of soluble Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} were almost invariably contradictory, except in the initial phase of reduction (Fig. 16). Secondly, soils at the same E_h had concentrations of Fe^{++} that differed by a factor, sometimes as high as 20. Lastly, the actual concentrations of iron and manganese in the soil solution did not approach, even remotely, the values predicted by the equations:

Fig. 15. Changes in the redox potential of four soils kept submerged.

$$E_h = 1.033 - 0.060 \log Fe^{++} - 0.180 \text{ pH}$$

$$E_h = 1.250 - 0.030 \log Mn^{++} - 0.120 \text{ pH}$$

Fig. 16. Relationship between the changes in redox potential and concentration of Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} in the soil solution.

They were far too small. Clearly, the redox potentials of reduced soils are not governed by the iron or manganese concentration in the soil solution.

If the redox potential of the soil was not determined by the concentrations of Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} , there was a possibility that the E_h of the soil solution might be. Therefore, these potentials were examined.

The redox potentials of the soil solution determined under the strictest anaerobic conditions differed from those of the soils in two important respects: (a) They were higher by wide margins for the highly reduced soils, by smaller margins for the slightly negative soils and were lower than in the soil for the single soil with a positive potential, until the last stages of submergence; (b) they tended to increase af-

ter 80 days of submergence unlike the soil potentials which showed fairly steady minima. This is shown in Table 7. The higher E_h of the solution could be caused by (a) oxidation by air, and (b) pH differences. Since air was rigorously excluded and the pH differences did not exceed 0.2 pH, an alternative explanation is necessary.

The most plausible hypothesis appears to be that potentials measured by electrodes placed in the soil are bacterial potentials. Potentials obtained with suspensions of bacteria cover the entire range observed in these soils. Further, they are known to have pH slopes of -30 to -120 mv - slopes encountered in reduced soils, as will be shown later. Bacterial potentials are believed to be caused by redox systems generated by bacterial metabolism and activated by enzymes. Presumably, bacterial cells and enzymes that catalyze the electron transfers in the highly negative systems are filtered out or adsorbed by the soil as the soil solution is drawn out.

The potentials of reduced soils, as shown earlier, were far too low to be associated quantitatively with soluble Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} concentrations. With the higher potentials shown by the soil solutions, a quantitative correlation appeared possible.

The best correlation obtained was between Fe^{++} in the soil solution and E_7 of the 31 soils, 143 days after submergence when the Fe^{++} concentrations had leveled off and assumed values close to those permitted by pH. The regression of E_7 on

Table 7. Changes of Eh (mv) of the soil and soil solution with duration of submergence.

Soil No.	Days submerged									
	10	25	39	52	66	80	101	115	129	143
9 Soil	-174	-244	-219	-240	-229	-245	-235	-218	-240	-235
Solution	+445	+195	+173	+97	+80	+65	+75	+115	+157	+170
10 Soil	-16	-12	-32	-47	-68	-50	-105	-103	-118	-240
Solution	+445	+195	+225	+155	+130	+93	+170	+247	+223	+275
26 Soil	+206	+168	+119	+112	+119	+93	+143	+123	+89	+82
Solution	+210	+50	-8	+65	+35	-5	+40	+160	+173	+380

Fe^{++} is given by the equation:

$$E_r = 0.967 - 0.368 \log (Fe^{++})$$

$$r = 0.862^{**}$$

The marked deviation of this expression from the theoretical equation:

$$E_r = -0.227 - 0.060 \log (Fe^{++}),$$

for the $Fe(OH)_2 - Fe^{++}$

system implies that the correlation is spurious or fortuitous.

With the exclusion of Fe^{++} and Mn^{++} , the only major components left are organic. The concentrations of organic reduction products, as shown earlier, were several times those of Fe^{++} . The organic constituents, then, qualify for the role of the dominant redox system even in the soil solution.

Further information of the redox systems in soils was sought with carefully controlled experiments with three soils in the laboratory. The criteria used in the attempt to identify the redox systems in submerged soils were the E_h and dE/dpH .

Three soils were incubated anaerobically with and without organic matter, and the variation of E_h with pH was determined potentiometrically within the pH range 1-10 in the complete absence of oxygen after varying periods of incubation. dE/dpH was determined for the soils in air, also, to furnish the curves for zero time of incubation.

The earlier finding that the dominant redox system in soils in equilibrium with atmospheric oxygen is the oxygen system was confirmed. The three soils studied (a) gave aerobic potentials of 460–550 mv at pH 7.0 and E_h —pH gradients of minus 50–55 mv per pH unit, compared with the theoretical values of 530 mv and -60 mv/pH, respectively, for the irreversible oxygen system; (b) responded to increase and decrease if oxygen tension by a rise and fall in E_h , and (c) registered the same aerobic potentials in the presence and absence of 0.5 per cent rice straw or dried green manure, though the dE/pH

gradient was slightly decreased by organic matter.

On submergence and anaerobic incubation, the potentials decreased (most rapidly in the acid soil rich in organic matter and least in the neutral soil high in manganese) to give fairly stable potentials after 4 weeks of incubation.

The addition of straw and organic matter steepened the initial fall in potential in the two soils of medium organic matter content but had no appreciable effect on the rate of fall of potential in the soil rich in organic matter. Organic matter did not lower the final stable potential below the corresponding potential in the absence of organic matter except in the neutral soil rich in manganese. In this soil, straw intensified both the rate and degree of reduction more than green manure.

The E_h —time curves for two soils, in the presence and absence of rice straw, are shown in Fig. 17 for the very strongly acidic soil and the neutral soil rich in manganese.

Two other points of interest about the changes in potential are (a) they are amenable to precise mathematical description by the function:

$$\log E_h = a + b \log t + c (\log t)^2$$

where t is the time of anaerobic incubation,

Fig. 17. Changes in redox potential with time of two soils incubated anaerobically with and without green manure.

and (b) the minimum potentials are considerably higher than for the same soils left submerged in pots but lower than for the soil solution. Apparently, the soil slurry used for the determination of E_h represented conditions intermediate between the soil, with its bacterial population, their metabolites and enzyme systems, on the one hand, and the soil solution, on the other. In view of these findings, recent attempts to interpret redox potentials of flooded soils in terms of the iron system by extrapolation of results obtained with thin suspensions of soil must be viewed cautiously.

Studies on the variation of dE/dpH for different soils at varying stages of reduction have elicited points of considerable theoretical interest in the elucidation of the redox systems in submerged soils.

They show that (a) for a given soil dE/dpH may vary with time of submergence; (b) at a given time of submergence dE/dpH may differ from soil to soil; (c) organic matter may alter dE/dpH for any soil at any stage of reduction, and (d) dE/dpH of a reduced soil varies markedly with pH. Some of these points are indicated in Table 8 and depicted in Fig. 18.

The changes of dE/dpH with time (after 2 weeks) was least in soil No. 6 with no organic matter and in soil No. 27 with rice straw. They tended to increase for the other soils, with one exception, after 4 weeks of incubation. Green manure and rice straw increased $-dE/dpH$ in the two acid soils.

Fig. 18 shows how dE/dpH for a given soil at a given time of incubation varies with pH. For the aerobic soil, dE/dpH is fairly constant and approximately -58 mv over the range pH 2-10. Below a pH 2, dE/dpH tends to zero indicating the operation of the $Fe^{+++}-Fe^{++}$ system. The slopes of the other curves varied markedly in the pH range 1-6. From pH 7-10 it was fairly constant and equal approximately to -110 mv per pH unit.

These changes in dE/dpH bear no relation to the ferric-ferrus system in terms of which some workers have attempted to interpret the potentials of flooded soils. If the ferrous-ferric system were operating, dE/dpH should be 0 up to a pH of about 3 from the acid side, -180 from pH 3 to 7, and -60 from pH 7 onwards. The actual values diverge widely from these theoretical slopes.

These studies have shown that (a) the E_h of a reduced soil is highly negative and much lower than that of its equilibrium aqueous extract or suspension; (b) the potentials are not even remotely related, quantitatively, to the concentration of iron or manganese, though iron and manganese can buffer potential changes; (c) the redox system in soils have E_h -pH slopes of -40 to -140 depending on the soil, kind of organic matter, and stage of reduction.

All these observations are compatible with the hypothesis that the redox potentials of flooded soils are bacterial potentials.

Table 8. Influence of soil, green manure, rice straw and time of incubation on $-dE/dpH$ (at natural pH) of three soils kept submerged.

Weeks incubated	Soil No. 6			Soil No. 24			Soil No. 27		
	Added O.M.%			Added O.M.%			Added O.M.%		
	0	0.5 GM	0.5 RS	0	0.5 GM	0.5 RS	0	0.5 GM	0.5 RS
0	55	53	51	50	40	40	51	48	44
2	111	120	100	116	120	120	52	100	108
4	102	125	100	113	118	113	100	121	113
6	111	116	133	127	138	140	106	118	111
10	118	126	132	126	131	145	114	100	112

Fig. 18a. Changes in redox potential with pH of Louisiana clay incubated anaerobically.

Fig. 18b. Changes in redox potential with pH of Maahas clay incubated anaerobically.

IONIC EQUILIBRIA IN FLOODED SOILS

Ionic equilibria regulate many properties of submerged soils that are of great theoretical and practical importance. Aside from controlling redox potential, pH, specific conductance, cation exchange, precipitation, and complexing reactions, they determine the availability of an array of plant nutrients and also the concentration of substances that can be toxic to rice.

Since iron is generally the most abundant soil element whose compounds undergo reversible oxidation-reduction, ionic equilibria in flooded soils are likely to be dominated by reduced iron. More than 30,000 kg./ha. of reduced iron may be produced in a soil within 4 weeks of flooding but less than 5 percent may be in the soluble form. Of this 5 percent, only a fraction, depending upon soil, stage of reduction, and kind and amount of organic matter, is present as cationic Fe^{++} . This is the entity that directly enters into most chemical and electrochemical equilibria in flooded soils. Its accurate assay and an

appreciation of its relationship to other forms of Fe^{++} are essential prerequisites to the quantitative study of ionic equilibria in submerged soils. The fractionation of reduced iron into total, exchangeable, cationic, and complexed iron was undertaken as the first phase in the study of ionic equilibria in flooded soils.

Fractionation of Fe^{++} in Reduced Soils

Twenty-gram portions of three soils, with and without 0.5 percent green manure and rice straw, were incubated anaerobically in the presence of 50 ml. of water, and the following categories of reduced Fe^{++} , determined at fortnightly intervals: exchangeable Fe^{++} , cationic Fe^{++} , and non-cationic Fe^{++} . The figures for the strongly acid soil and nearly neutral soil are in Table 9, and some of them illustrated in Fig. 19.

These figures show that the contents of exchangeable, cationic, and non-cationic Fe^{++} and their proportions varied with

Table 9. Influence of time of anaerobic incubation and rice straw on the distribution of Fe⁺⁺ in two soils. (Ex. Fe⁺⁺ is in ppm of dry soil; cationic and non-cationic Fe⁺⁺ in ppm of soil solution.)

Weeks incubated	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	16
Soil: Dark brown clay, pH 4.81, O.M. 2.68%								
No added O.M.								
Ex. Fe ⁺⁺			4450	4750	4310	4290	4470	4300
Cat. Fe ⁺⁺			50	26	13	11	9	8
Non-cat. Fe ⁺⁺			19	7	—	3	4	2
0.5% rice straw								
Ex. Fe ⁺⁺			5520	5030	5190	5200	5330	5090
Cat. Fe ⁺⁺			88	64	43	28	29	30
Non-cat. Fe ⁺⁺			27	33	25	21	16	15
Soil: gray brown clay, pH 6.64, O.M. 2.02%								
No added O.M.								
Ex. Fe ⁺⁺			75	56	44	37	75	91
Cat. Fe ⁺⁺			0.3	0.8	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.3
Non-cat. Fe ⁺⁺								
0.5% rice straw								
Ex. Fe ⁺⁺	20	1560	2060	1880	1830	1870	1880	1740
Cat. Fe ⁺⁺	0.1	11	12	15	9	8	5	—
Non-cat. Fe ⁺⁺		8	8	6	8	4	—	—

the soil, duration of submergence, and presence or absence of rice straw.

The strongly acid soil built up, within 2 weeks, an exchangeable Fe⁺⁺ concentration of about 15 m.e. per 100 g. and maintained this value for the next 14 weeks. Rice straw increased the content of this category of Fe⁺⁺ only slightly, although it enhanced markedly the cationic and non-cationic Fe⁺⁺ concentration. The ratio of non-cationic to cationic Fe⁺⁺ was roughly 1:3 during the first 6 weeks of reduction and increased to about 1:2 in the later stages, with and without rice straw.

The neutral soil presented a marked contrast. The concentrations of both exchangeable and soluble iron were extremely low. The highest concentration of exchangeable Fe⁺⁺ was only 0.3 m.e. per 100 g. while soluble Fe⁺⁺ did not exceed 1 ppm. Rice straw had a dramatic effect; exchangeable Fe⁺⁺ was elevated to about 7 m.e. per 100 g., and soluble iron underwent a 20-fold increase in con-

centration. On the average, a higher proportion of soluble Fe⁺⁺ was non-cationic in this nearly neutral soil.

The most important observation, from the theoretical standpoint, was the in-

Fig. 19. Influence of time of incubation, rice straw and green manure on exchangeable Fe⁺⁺.

crease in concentration of both cationic and non-cationic Fe^{++} in all these soils by rice straw and green manure. This means that the decomposition of organic matter produces, in anaerobic soils, substances other than complexing agents that can increase the solubility of Fe^{++} . They are probably CO_2 and lower fatty acids. With the decomposition of the organic acids and loss of CO_2 by diffusion and bacterial reduction to CH_4 , the pH should increase slightly and the concentration of cationic Fe^{++} should move towards the value defined by the new pH of the solution. No big change is necessary; an increase of 0.5 pH unit is sufficient to decrease the concentration of Fe^{++} 10 times. The observed kinetics of soluble Fe^{++} , in this experiment and in the study reported earlier, are in harmony with this explanation.

An additional point of theoretical inter-

est concerns the ferric-ferrous redox system. Since about one-third to one-half of the iron in the soil solution may be in the form of slightly dissociated complexes, it is questionable whether the simple $Fe(OH)_3 - Fe^{++}$ system operates in flooded soils. Further, the use of the total soluble Fe^{++} concentration for the activity of cationic Fe^{++} in redox and chemical equilibria in soils is inept.

The inferences of practical significance are: (a) Considerable amounts of NH_4^+ , K^+ , Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} may be displaced into the soil solution and made available to rice and also lost in the drainage by cation exchange with Fe^{++} in acid soils; (b) organic manures may aggravate iron toxicity by increasing the concentration of cationic and complexed Fe^{++} in acid soils, and (c) organic matter may be the remedy for iron deficiency in neutral and alkaline soils.

WATER REGIME IN FLOODED SOILS

Although rice is almost universally grown in flooded soils, the physiological reasons for the necessity of this practice are not clearly understood. If the principal physiological advantages of flooding are elimination of water stress, increased availability of nutrients, and exclusion of nitrate, it might be possible to achieve the benefits of flooding with chemical treatment of soils at field capacity or with a partially saturated profile. This surmise was tested in pot cultures in the greenhouse and in large drums of soil, out-of-doors.

The Greenhouse Study

The purpose of this study was to ascertain to what extent the chemical benefits of flooding could be achieved by the addition of iron, silicon, phosphorus, and a depressor of nitrification to the soil kept at field capacity.

Peta, an *indica* variety, was grown in pots on three soils, subject to the following water and chemical treatments: (a) Submerged to a depth of 3 inches; (b) saturated; (c) field capacity; (d) field capacity plus all chemical amendments; (e) (d) - Fe; (f) (d) - Si; (g) (d) - P; and (h) (d) - 2-chloro-6-(trichloromethyl) pyridine (Fig. 20).

The soils were Louisiana clay, Maahas clay, and a calcareous clay.

All treatments received 1,000 kg. of 10:5:10 per 2 x 10⁶ kg. soil at planting. Fe was applied as a 2 ppm Fe solution of the chelate, NaFeEDDHA; Si at 250 ppm as silica gel powder; P as bone flour at 100 ppm P_2O_5 ; and 2-chloro-6-(trichloromethyl) pyridine at 2 ppm, to retard nitrification.

The attempt to simulate by chemical treatment the chemical benefits of flooding was not entirely successful. Rice

Fig. 20. The physical arrangement of facilities for the greenhouse study of the water regime in flooded soils.

grew and yielded much better in the submerged and saturated soils than in the soils at field capacity, regardless of the chemical treatment, but for reasons that apparently varied with the soil.

In the acid soils, better growth and yield under flooded and saturated conditions were associated with a higher uptake of silicon, iron and nitrogen but particularly with a much lower uptake of Mn; in the nearly neutral soil, with higher contents of silicon, iron and manganese; and in the calcareous soil, with higher manganese and phosphorus contents, in the plant organs.

The chemical treatments produced only small increases in yield of straw and grain and slight differences in the chemical composition, relative to the soils, at field capacity with no chemical treatment. The calcareous soil was an exception; in this soil, yield under well-drained conditions was improved by the addition of iron, silicon, and phosphorus (see Fig. 21).

Fig. 21. Increased availability of P is one of the benefits of flooding.

The lack of response to chemical treatments appeared to be associated, in the acid soil, with an inordinately high accumulation of manganese and low iron uptake, and in the neutral and calcareous soils, with inadequate absorption of iron and manganese.

The differential responses of rice in the three soils to the water and the chemical treatments are indicated in Table 10.

If Peta performed poorly in aerobic soils, Chianung 242, a *japonica*, in a subsequent experiment fared disastrously in the same soils under well-drained conditions, even in the presence of chemicals. It appeared to suffer from manganese toxicity, and in the absence of extra phosphate, from acute phosphorus deficiency, in aerobic Louisiana clay. In the Maahas clay, where it grew and yielded much better than in Louisiana clay, especially under aerobic conditions, the problem looked, from straw analysis, as if it were a slight iron and manganese deficiency. In the aerobic calcareous soil, visual observation indicated the trouble was obviously extreme iron

Fig. 22. One of the benefits of flooding is the increase in availability of Fe.

deficiency (see Fig. 22).

The conclusions from this study are: (a) The yield of rice is much higher in saturated and flooded soils than in aerobic

Table 10. Influence of three water treatments and chemical amendments on the growth, yield, and chemical composition of rice on three soils.

Treatment	Panicle No.	Straw in gm/pot	Grain	N %	P* %	K %	SiO ₂ %	Fe ppm	Mn ppm
Louisiana clay, pH 4.8, O.M. 2.9%									
Submerged	29.3	102	110	0.59	0.14	0.97	15.2	282	783
Saturated	25.0	95	124	0.74	0.12	1.07	15.6	224	840
Field Cap.	24.3	92	81	0.36	0.11	1.38	12.9	91	1870
Fld.Cap. + all Chem.	28.3	101	84	0.40	0.15	1.20	12.2	87	2250
Maahas clay, pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0%									
Submerged	37.3	140	158	0.27	0.32	2.46	13.9	200	690
Saturated	33.3	144	148	0.28	0.32	2.06	14.1	149	432
Field Cap.	28.0	114	96	0.30	0.26	2.33	13.4	133	141
F.C. + all Chem.	30.0	114	107	0.32	0.25	2.27	13.8	92	96
Calcareous clay, pH 7.5, O.M. 1.1%									
Submerged	27.0	110	118	0.27	0.31	0.35	12.1	77	364
Saturated	25.3	97	97	0.26	0.30	0.18	11.7	43	337
Field Cap.	19.3	78	50	0.33	0.29	0.79	13.3	75	41
F.C. + all Chem.	23.3	89	70	0.28	0.25	0.69	13.3	98	54

* in grain.

soils; (b) flooding or saturating the soil tends to iron out differences in productivity of soils in the aerobic state; (c) the chemical benefits of flooding cannot be attained in aerobic soils, even in the absence of moisture stress, by the addition of chemicals, unless excessive absorption of manganese is suppressed in acid soils, and the uptake of iron and manganese is increased in neutral and calcareous soils.

This study also has apparently resolved the conflict about manganese uptake by rice in flooded soils. In acid soils, manganese uptake is decreased by flooding although there is a several-fold increase in manganese concentration in the soil solution; in neutral and alkaline soils, it is increased despite a smaller relative increase on flooding. This points to differences in the physiology of rice roots in acid and neutral soils, both in the aerobic and anaerobic states.

The Outdoor Drum Study

This experiment was designed to see to what extent some of the physiological benefits of flooding could be attained by a partially saturated profile.

Three soils (Louisiana clay, pH 4.8, O.M. 2.9 percent; Maahas clay, pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0 percent and a calcareous clay pH 7.5, O.M. 1 percent) were subjected to the following water treatments in drums holding 250 kg. of soil: (a) submerged to a depth of 10 cm; (b) and (c) water table at 20 cm. and 40 cm., respectively, below the surface. Changes in redox potential were followed in all treatments with platinum electrodes permanently set at a depth of 10 cm. and soil moisture tension was noted in the partially saturated soils with tensiometers set at a depth of 10 cm. (Fig 23).

The yield of grain was, as in the greenhouse study, highest in the submerged

Fig. 23. The physical arrangement of facilities for the drum study of the water regime in flooded soils.

treatments for all three soils. The yields declined progressively with lowering of the watertable in the Louisiana and calcareous clays but abruptly in Maahas clay. The decrease in yield with depth of watertable was associated with an increase in soil moisture tension from 80–270 millibars at 20 cm. to 215–820 millibars at 40 cm. in the Louisiana clay and from 150–300 millibars to 315–430 millibars for the calcareous clay. Redox potentials indicated oxidizing conditions at a depth of 10 cm. in all soils except the submerged. During this dry season, Maahas clay caked and cracked badly, causing severe root pruning and also vitiating tensiometer and redox readings. The yields of straw and grain are in Table 11.

Structure and hydraulic conductivity appeared to be the main factors influencing the difference in yield between the submerged and partially saturated soils.

The experiment was repeated during the following wet season with modifications: (a) Maahas clay was treated with a soil conditioner to preclude caking and cracking on drying; (b) another variety was included, and (c) 0.15 percent of a 1:2 mixture of ground rice straw and *Glyricidia maculata* was substituted for fertilizer nitrogen.

The results of the experiment were unusual in many ways. First, the 20 cm. watertable treatment was superior to the submerged treatment in Maahas clay and the calcareous clay for both Peta and

M302 and, only slightly inferior in the Louisiana clay, for M302.

Second, both varieties suffered from slight nitrogen deficiency in the submerged Maahas clay but not in the partially saturated Maahas clay.

Third, both varieties suffered from acute iron deficiency in the calcareous soil when the watertable was 40 cm. below the surface.

The influence of level of watertable on the chemical composition of the plants varied with the soil. Lowering the watertable appeared in the acid soil to decrease the percentage of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and iron but markedly increased that of manganese in the straw. In Maahas clay, the effects were different; plants in the submerged treatments had a lower content of nitrogen and a higher content of manganese than those from the low watertable treatments; the contents of phosphorus, potassium and iron were apparently unaffected. The composition of plants for the calcareous clay showed no clear trends, perhaps because of contamination.

The better growth of rice with the watertable 20 cm. below the surface than with 10 cm. above the surface during this wet season when there was no appreciable soil moisture tension in the soil may be associated with a sufficiency of nutrients and partial exclusion of toxic reduction products.

Table 11. Influence of depth of water table in three soils on the yield of straw and grain of variety Peta.

Depth of water table (cm)	Louisiana clay		Maahas clay		Calcareous clay	
	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain
	in grams per drum of four hills					
10 ¹	448	444	522	684	556	576
20 ²	440	360	412	133	444	314
40 ²	456	329	456	70	190	137

¹ submerged to a depth of 10 cm.

² cm. below surface of the soil.

PHYSIOLOGICAL DISEASES OF RICE

A physiological disease of rice known as "bronzing" occurs on acid lateritic soils with poor drainage. This disease has been variously attributed to excess iron, excess aluminum, potassium and phosphate deficiency, and, surprisingly enough, even to hydrogen sulfide toxicity. The occurrence of this disease on acid sesquioxidic soils and its amelioration by liming suggested excess iron as a cause of the disease. This hypothesis was tested in a semi-quantitative manner in a preliminary greenhouse experiment.

Louisiana clay, an acid latosolic rice soil, was strongly reduced by incubation with 1 percent sucrose solution for 2 weeks. The soil was then leached with de-aerated water to remove the organic toxins, and treatments, designed to give varying concentrations of ferrous iron in the soil solution, were imposed, prior to flooding and planting 2-week-old M302 seedlings. The treatments were:

(a) Control. (b) HCl to increase the concentration of soluble Fe^{++} ; (c) NaOH to decrease the concentration of soluble Fe^{++} , and (d) $Ca(NO_3)_2$ to retard further reduction.

There were marked responses to the treatments. The plants in the acid treatment turned purple overnight, wilted, and died. The concentration of 790 ppm iron in the soil solution was obviously lethal. The soil was then drained and submerged again with distilled water. The replanted new seedlings fared no better.

Fresh seedlings were then transplanted extremely shallow. Plants in the calcium nitrate and alkali treatments grew vigorously, tillered profusely, and were deep green in color. Plants in the HCl treatment were the poorest. Within a week of replanting, brown spots appeared on the lower leaves, and they gradually turned reddish yellow and died. The brown speckling spread to the upper leaves and within 6 weeks of planting, the plants were uniformly purplish brown in color. The yields of straw and grain and the Fe^{++} concentrations in the soil solution 10 weeks after planting are in Table 12.

These observations point to excess iron as the cause of the physiological disease known as "bronzing."

Table 12. Influence of four soil treatments on Fe^{++} in the soil solution and the yield of rice and Fe content of straw.

Treatment	Fe^{++} ppm soil solution	Straw gm/pot	Grain gm/pot	Fe content of straw, (ppm)
Control	260	111	138	192
HCl	623	67	78	464
NaOH	150	130	131	108
$Ca(NO_3)_2$	248	131	155	169

DIRECT MICROSCOPIC EXAMINATION of the rice root surface, showing aggregations of two different morphological forms: Rods (rods), and cocci (cocci). Magnification 1,000.

Soil Microbiology

Plant root systems stimulate the soil microflora. This stimulation, called the rhizosphere effect, increases the microbial population in the root zone. The rhizosphere effect, undoubtedly caused by plant root excretions and plant debris, develops as the plant ages. The microbial population of the rhizosphere to a large extent determines the immediate environment of the plant root because this population covers a significant proportion of the root surface area and is in immediate contact with the root surface.

If the rhizosphere population produces toxic substances, then this could result in immediate and severe changes in the plant. Certain physiological diseases of rice, if not directly caused by the rhizosphere microflora, may be aggravated by the metabolic products of this population.

Knowledge of the rhizosphere popula-

tion is essential to an understanding of the environment of the rice root system.

In submerged soil, much of the carbon mineralization is anaerobic. Reduced products resulting from this decomposition may accumulate to such levels as to be toxic to rice plants. A more complete knowledge of the process of organic matter decomposition under reduced conditions is essential to the deriving of general principles for the timing and rate of application of organic matter to rice fields. It is important that the types of microorganisms involved in this transformation should be more completely characterized and that the mechanisms and environmental conditions involved be better understood.

The increasing use of pesticides on both lowland and upland rice crops necessitates investigations of the effects of these chem-

icals upon both the soil microflora and the important microbiological transformations in the soil. It is vital to know about the persistence of these chemicals in the soil. It may be possible that these chemicals can accumulate in the soil to levels toxic to both the rice plant and the soil microflora.

Data on the persistence of chemical pesticides in flooded soils may not necessarily reflect the results obtained for non-flooded soil. Furthermore, microbial degradation of the pesticides may produce metabolic products more toxic than the original chemicals. These possibilities necessitate studies of the microbiological decomposition of these pesticidal chemicals and the characterization of the metabolic products.

Some leguminous crops, such as *Sesbania* sp. and *Phaseolus lathyroides*, show promise as green manure crops and can be grown under flooded conditions. The legume-*Rhizobium* symbiotic system of nitrogen fixation appears to operate even under the reduced condition of flooded soil. This poses several problems on the physiological mechanism of root infection by the *Rhizobium* sp. and offers the possibility of a green manure crop which can be grown under submerged conditions.

The research program in soil microbiology seeks to obtain data to permit a better understanding of the environment of the rice root system. Research on the following topics was initiated in late 1963: (a) Changes in the microflora following submergence of soil; (b) *Rhizobium*-legume symbiosis under submerged conditions; and (c) the rhizosphere population of rice plants grown under both upland and lowland conditions. The future research program will include studies of the (a) characterization of the substances in rice root exudates, (b) organic matter decomposition, and (c) pesticide decomposition.

Rhizosphere Population of Rice Plants

Experiments are in progress to determine: (a) Changes in soil microflora following flooding of the soil; (b) the rhizosphere effect of rice plants grown in both flooded and non-flooded soil, and (c) changes in the root surface microflora of the rice plants over the full growth period and in flooded and non-flooded soils.

In connection with these studies the occurrence and numbers of the following microorganisms are being investigated: Bacteria, actinomycetes, fungi, algae, anaerobes, denitrifiers, sulfate reducers, *Azotobacter* sp., nitrogen-fixing *Clostridium* sp., nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae, *Nitrosomonas* sp., and *Nitrobacter* sp.

Although these studies have not been completed, early results indicate that the numbers of nitrogen-fixing anaerobic bacteria are greater at the root surface than in soil which is free of rice roots. This increase in numbers undoubtedly results from some excretion product of rice roots.

Large numbers of nitrogen-fixing anaerobic bacteria were found in the rhizosphere. The presence of this large population suggests that these microorganisms may play a significant role in the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in paddy soil.

Microscopic examinations of the surface of rice plant roots, following suitable staining procedures to reveal the microorganisms, revealed that the root surface was largely coated by an immense microflora. (See illustration above.)

Nodulation Studies

Pure cultures of the *Rhizobium* sp. responsible for the nodulation of *Sesbania sesban*, *S. aculeata*, and *S. aegyptiaca* were isolated from crushed nodules taken from host plants growing under submerged conditions. These cultures are being examined to determine if they can re infect their respective host plants.

RICE VARIETY BPI-76 approaches maturity in the maximum yield experiment, 1963 wet season.

Agronomy

During 1963, the agronomy group emphasized studies of the practices which, individually or combined, can be expected to contribute to maximum yields per crop and per year under the various rice-growing conditions of the humid tropics. The

major investigations included (a) continuation of the maximum yield experiment, (b) rotation crops and green manures, (c) fertilizers and their use, (d) weed control, and (e) planting methods.

MAXIMUM YIELD EXPERIMENT

In this long-term experiment, production of high levels of grain yield are attempted utilizing two different varieties, three systems of water management, and four levels of nitrogen fertilization. Results for a full year now are available.

1962 Wet Season Results

The *japonica* variety Chianung 242 from Taiwan and the Philippine *indica* FB-121 were sown May 24 in a heavily fertilized seedbed and were transplanted at 20 x 20 cm. on June 9. Three systems of water management were used: (a) Continuous submergence, (b) alternate flooding and drainage, and (c) drained surface (Fig. 1). In addition to the nitrogen

available in the soil at time of planting, all plots received about 32 kg./ha. N in manure and rice straw; superimposed were treatments of 40, 80, 120, and 160 kg./ha. N. The 40 and 80 kg./ha. N treatments received 40 kg./ha. each of P_2O_5 and K_2O while the 120 and 160 kg./ha. N treatments received 80 kg./ha. of P_2O_5 and K_2O .

The two varieties differed markedly in behavior (Fig. 2). Chianung 242 produced from 4,015 to 5,229 kg./ha. of clean dry grain (14 percent moisture) in 93 days after transplanting; the crop did not lodge even at the highest levels of nitrogen fertilization. There were no significant differences in yield associated either with

Fig. 1. Three systems of water management are tested in the maximum yield experiment. In the "drained surface" treatment (center two plots), small ditches were provided around each plot. The water table was maintained several centimeters below the soil surface; the plots were never submerged. Other treatments involved use of continuous flooding (upper left) and alternate flooding and drainage (upper right).

Fig. 2. In the 1962 wet season, applications of nitrogen depressed yields of FB-121 but did not greatly affect Chianung 242.

nitrogen levels or water management practices.

FB-121, a tall, photosensitive *indica*, produced much lower yields, ranging from 2,556 kg./ha. at low levels of nitrogenous fertilization down to 1,167 kg./ha. at the highest fertility level. In concurrent physiology experiments, it was found that a spacing of 20 x 20 cm. is much too close for varieties of this plant type in the wet season, and that the higher levels of applied nitrogen result in increased vegetative growth, increased shading and death of lower leaves, and greatly reduced yields. The date of planting chosen for this photosensitive variety also was too early; consequently, it required 171 days to mature. Productivity of grain of the best treatment was only 18.7 kg./ha. day.

Since Chianung 242 matured much earlier than FB-121, a ratoon crop of the former was produced. An application of 40 kg. ha. N was applied uniformly over all plots, and after 89 days, grain yields ranging from 532 to 1,006 kg. ha. were obtained. The productivity of the best ratoon treatment was only about 11 kg. ha. day, while the average productivity of the main crop of Chianung 242 was 50.2 kg./ha. day.

Following the ratoon of Chianung 242 and the harvest of FB-121, the plots were prepared and broadcast seeded with *Sesbania*. This green manure crop proved to be photosensitive and growth was poor. On February 5, after 75 days in the field, a little more than 1 ton per hectare of organic matter was plowed under, contributing less than 10 kg. ha. of nitrogen.

Fig. 3. In the 1963 dry season, Chianung 242 and Milfor 6 tended to yield about the same within each level of nitrogen application and at each water management treatment. With most treatments, the dry season yields exceeded wet season yields.

1963 Dry Season Results

For the next rice plantings, a revised experimental design was adopted. This used varieties as main plots and water treatments as sub-plots. Levees were plastic-lined to provide better control of seepage. Chianung 242 and the Philippine *indica* Milfor (6)2 were transplanted at 20 x 20 cm. on February 18, with 0, 30, 60, and 120 kg./ha. N as additional variables.

Chianung 242 produced grain yields ranging from 3,122 to 5,852 kg./ha. after 100 days in the main field (Fig. 3). The variety produced reasonably good yields at all levels of nitrogen fertilization when a continuous flood was employed; however, with the alternate flood or drained surface treatments, yields were low at low levels of nitrogen, but there were marked responses to added nitrogen. The best treatment produced 58.5 kg./ha./day of dry grain.

With Milfor 6, grain yields ranging from 3,136 to 5,930 kg./ha. were obtained in 128 days after transplanting. There was an increase of about 1 ton per hectare of grain in the continuously submerged and alternate flood treatments as applied nitrogen was increased from 0 to 120 kg./ha.; in the drained surface treatment, the yield with no additional nitrogen was quite low, but the yield increased even more markedly with increases in applied nitrogen. Although total yields with this variety were reasonably good, it was less productive than Chianung 242, producing grain at the rate of 46 kg./ha./day in the main field.

Effects of Season on Response to Nitrogen

In the dry season, both Chianung 242 and Milfor (6)2 produced higher grain yields with increased levels of nitrogen fertilization; averages for the three water treatments are in Table 1. Neither crop lodged, and it is possible that nitrogen levels even higher than 120 kg./ha. would have further increased the yield.

In the wet season, Chianung 242 yielded about equally well at the four levels of nitrogen, but all levels were unnecessarily high. Addition of nitrogen reduced grain yields of FB-121. On the relatively fertile soils of the Institute farm, no economic gains from nitrogenous fertilizers have as yet been obtained during the wet season even with the efficient *japonicas* from Taiwan.

Water Management

In the 1962 wet season, there were no significant differences among yields obtained with continuous flooding, alternate flooding, or drained surface treatments, but slightly lower yields were obtained with alternate flooding and drainage, possibly a result of draining away nitrogen (Table 2). The drained surface treatment was as good as the continuous flooding; however, although the plots were not submerged, the soils never were dry because of frequent rains.

In the 1963 dry season, the alternate flood treatment again appeared inferior to

Table 1. Grain yields of two rice varieties with four levels of applied nitrogen in the 1962 wet and 1963 dry seasons; averages for four replications and three water treatments.

Nitrogen applied (kg./ha.)	1962 Wet Season		1963 Dry Season		
	Grain yields (kg./ha.)		Nitrogen applied (kg./ha.)	Grain yields (kg./ha.)	
	Chianung 242	FB 121		Chianung 242	Milfor (6)2
40	4934	2621	0	4143	4240
80	4425	1964	30	4439	4436
120	4909	1599	60	4975	4992
160	4690	1263	120	5631	5448

Table 2. Grain yields of two varieties with three water treatments in the 1962 wet and 1963 dry seasons; averages for four replications and four different sets of four nitrogen levels in each season.

Water treatment	Grain yields (kg./ha.)					
	1962 Wet Season			1963 Dry Season		
	Chianung 242	FB 121	Mean	Chianung 242	Milfor (6)2	Mean
Continuous flooding	4809	1820	3314	5282	5410	5346
Alternate flooding	4513	1666	3089	4848	4961	4904
Drained surface	4896	2100	3498	4253	3966	4109

the continuous flooding, and again this was true with both varieties. The drained surface treatments gave substantially reduced yields when averages of the four nitrogen levels were used (Table 2) but Fig. 3 reveals that Chianung 242 and Milfor (6)2 yielded 5,402 and 4,898 kg./ha., respectively, with a drained surface and high levels of nitrogen application. Their yields with 120 kg./ha. N and drained surfaces were about equal to the unfertilized, continuously flooded plots. In the drained surface plots, the upper soil layer dried and cracked badly (Fig. 4), but this permitted water movement across beds 3 meters wide.

During the dry season crop, water utilization was measured, producing consumptive water use figures for the three water management systems. The drained-surface or border-ditch treatment apparently required less water than did the continuous and alternate flooding systems. While the mean yields with the drained-surface system were significantly lower than those of the other two treatments, it produced satisfactory yields with much less irrigation water during the dry season when adequate fertilizers were added.

Maximum Production per Year

In the 1962 wet season, the maximum grain yield obtained was 6,173 kg./ha.

with Chianung 242, a drained surface, an application of 120 kg./ha. N, and with a 944 kg./ha. ratoon crop. The best yield in the dry season, 5,930 kg./ha., was

Fig. 4. The "drained surface" water management system during the 1963 dry season. Wide cracks in the montmorillonitic clay soil (Mahas clay) permitted water movement across beds 3 meters wide. Yields of rice were about 80 percent that of continuous flooding while water use was reduced by half.

obtained with Milfor (6)2 under continuous flooding and at 120 kg./ha. N. The combination of these two crops gives an annual total of 12,103 kg./ha. of clean dry (14 percent moisture) grain.

However, the best combination from an economic standpoint (11,436 kg./ha.) might include Chianung 242 in the wet season with continuous flooding and 40 kg./ha. N (5,044 kg./ha. of grain), its ratoon (754 kg./ha.), and the dry season crop (5,638 kg.) produced by Chianung 242 with high fertility and continuous flooding (Fig. 5). If irrigation water is limited in the dry season, a drained surface might be used.

Chianung 242 occupied the main field only 93 days and 100 days during the wet and dry seasons, respectively. It appears likely, as also suggested in the report of the Plant Physiology Department, that three crops of this or similar varieties could be grown in 12 months—with adequate provision for 14-18 day periods

Fig. 5. In the 1962 wet season, Chianung 242 produced about 5 ton/ha. of clean dry grain in 93 days after transplanting. In the 1963 dry season, this treatment produced 5.6 ton/ha. in 100 days after transplanting. Neither crop lodged. With suitable early varieties and irrigation, three crops a year should be possible.

between crops to plow down the crop residue and to allow partial decomposition of the organic matter. Production of three crops of rice would require the elimination of the green manure crop and the low yielding ratoon.

ROTATION CROPS AND GREEN MANURES

Evidence throughout this report indicates that development of early maturing, non-photosensitive varieties may permit the production of two wet season crops of rice per year in parts of the tropics, or three crops if irrigation water is available. Or, early maturing varieties may be used in cropping systems involving other grain crops such as soybeans, cowpeas, corn, or sorghum, or including the use of legumes as green manure crops.

Legume Introductions

By the end of 1962, 104 varieties or species of legumes had been received from Cambodia, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, and the United States. During the past year, an additional 32 accessions arrived

from India and the Philippines. These introductions are maintained in a nursery where plant characteristics are noted and preliminary yield data are obtained. Yields of green matter and nitrogen of 15 species evaluated as green manure crops ranged from 15.4 to 51.5 ton/ha. and 42.3 to 202.4 kg./ha., respectively (Table 3).

Grain Legumes

Soybeans continue to appear promising for use in rice cropping systems, but yields of the varieties in the Institute's collection have not been consistent (Table 4). Inoculation did not appear beneficial in the April, 1963, test, but it more than doubled the yields of the same varieties in a test planted in November, 1962.

Fig. 6. Determination of optimum spacing for grain production of mungo, soybeans, and cowpeas.

Table 3. Green matter and nitrogen yields of 15 promising green manure species planted April 30, 1963, and harvested 2½ months later.

Species	Green Matter (ton/ha.)	Nitrogen (kg./ha.)
<i>Sesbania sesban</i>	51.5	202.4
<i>Crotalaria quinquefolia</i>	46.9	88.3
<i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	45.0	129.0
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> No. 72	37.4	121.6
<i>Phaseolus lathyroides</i>	31.8	89.8
<i>Crotalaria anagyroides</i>	29.6	98.0
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> No. 71	28.7	103.8
<i>Cassia mimosoides</i>	21.8	96.6
<i>Canavalia ensiformis</i>	21.0	98.0
<i>Phaseolus calcaratus</i>	19.3	42.3
<i>Sesbania microcarpa</i>	17.5	87.5
<i>Glycine koidzumii</i>	17.0	71.4
<i>Stylobium deeringianum</i>	15.8	69.4
<i>Crotalaria usaramoensis</i>	15.5	75.8
<i>Dolichos biflorus</i>	15.4	89.2

In May, 1963, six varieties of mungo, soybeans, and cowpeas were planted in a replicated spacing trial to determine the requirements of each variety for maximum seed production (Fig. 6). This is the first of a series of agronomic experiments to acquire information on management of legumes in the tropics, especially on rice lands.

Green Manure Crops

The yields of several of the more productive species of green manure crops were examined by timing harvests of organic matter and nitrogen at growth stages which gave adequate returns and minimum difficulty of incorporation. Figure 7 illustrates

Table 4. Yield of five soybean varieties when uninoculated and when inoculated with *Rhizobium*.

Variety	NOVEMBER 1962 PLANTING		APRIL 1963 PLANTING	
	Uninoculated (kg./ha.)	Inoculated (kg./ha.)	Uninoculated (kg./ha.)	Inoculated (kg./ha.)
Head Green	1039	2495	1274	1499
Tung Tam	499	2076	2220	1905
Bilomi 3	747	1461	729	947
Black Manchurian	243	1363	2277	2655
Shieng Mai	349	856	318	335

Fig. 7. Production of nitrogen, dry matter, and green material by *Sesbania sesban* under upland conditions as affected by age of the crop.

the relationship of time of harvest to yields of dry matter, nitrogen, and green organic matter for *Sesbania sesban* grown in an upland rotation on a field scale. Harvest at 57 days of age gave maximum nitrogen yields of more than 80 kg./ha. Dry matter yield showed no tendency to decline at this time, and 55 to 60 days is considered the optimum time for incorporating this variety in a wet season planting.

Growth rates of green manures appear to be decreased when flooded at planting or when grown under continuous submergence; however, nodulation of several species of the legume seems to be satisfactory under lowland culture. Studies of the nitrogen production and utilization of *Sesbania aculeata*, *S. microcarpa*, *Phaseolus lathyroides* and *Crotalaria quinquefolia* are being continued. The microbiologist uses material from these tests to study some aspects of the mechanism of nodule production under submerged conditions.

THE INSTITUTE TESTS MANY TROPICAL LEGUMES for possible use as green manures or for rotation with rice.

THE AGRONOMIST REPORTS RESULTS of an experiment on time of nitrogen application in relation to nitrogen level and spacing.

FERTILIZERS AND THEIR USE

At the beginning of the 1963 dry season, an experiment suggested by the soil chemist was initiated to test the effect of reduction of the soil on the yield of Chianung 242 and Milfor (6)2. Plots were established to permit flooding 4, 3, 2, and 1 week before, and on the same day as transplanting. Two sources of nitrogen were compared: (1) A total of 7.4 tons of a mixture of rice straw and green leaves of *Leucaena glauca* were added to half the plots at the time of flooding, and (2) 40 kg./ha. N, as ammonium sulfate, were added to the other plots on the day of transplanting. All treatments received 20 kg./ha. N, as ammonium sulfate, at panicle initiation. It was considered that the amounts of available nitrogen from the two sources should be about equal.

Results of this experiment, presented in the section on Soil Chemistry, demonstrated that delaying transplanting for at least 2 weeks after flooding markedly increased

yields over the treatment involving flooding at the time of transplanting.

Yields with the two sources of nitrogen were not significantly different. Chianung 242 yielded 8,038 kg./ha. of dry grain with organic matter and 8,007 kg./ha. with ammonium sulfate. For Milfor (6)2, yields were 7,358 and 7,137 kg./ha., respectively.

In another field experiment, the effects of silicate fertilization and timing of nitrogen applications on yields of Chianung 242 and Peta were determined. Each variety received basal applications of 100 kg./ha. SiO_2 , as calcium magnesium silicate. In addition, 60 kg./ha. N were applied in split applications (Table 5).

Differences among nitrogen treatments were not significant, but addition of silica resulted in significant yield gains of more than 500 kg./ha. of grain. Although the silica application rate was considered to be too low, and the Maahas clay to which

Table 5. Yield, in kilograms per hectare, of Peta and Chianung 242 with and without 100 kg./ha. SiO₂ and with four nitrogen timing treatments, dry season, 1963.

Timing of nitrogen applied at 60 kg./ha.				Yield of rough rice at 14% moisture				Mean
				Peta		Chianung 242		
Basal	10-leaf stage	Panicle Initiation	Heading	No SiO ₂	100 kg./ha. SiO ₂	No SiO ₂	100 kg./ha. SiO ₂	
0	20	20	20	5132	5746	4004	4970	4963
30	0	30	0	4827	5372	3956	4213	4592
20	20	20	0	4624	5923	4197	4607	4838
0	20	40	0	5320	5549	3913	4497	4820
Mean				4976	5648	4017	4572	

Significant statistics:

LSD:			S.E.	C.V.
	Variety mean	= 603	154	3%
	Silicon mean	= 379	132	3%
	Nitrogen mean	= n.s.		

it was applied was believed to have sufficient silica, the calcium magnesium silicate was an effective amendment. Examination of stem borer counts, tiller number, height,

number of productive tillers, and other yield components did not reveal any significant differences that might be correlated with yields.

WEED CONTROL

Screening tests of more than 100 chemicals for weed control in upland and lowland rice, under a variety of cultural conditions, and in several seasons, were completed. Some chemicals, selected for further study, are being used in advanced combination and interaction tests as well as in management studies.

Of the materials that fall within the range of practicality on the basis of effectiveness in controlling weeds, minimum toxicity to rice and fish, and cost, MCPA¹ (potassium salt of 2-methyl-4-chloro phenoxyacetic acid) has the best record (Fig. 8). MCPA has been particularly effective in controlling sedges. As sedges constitute a major weed problem in the nonsoon areas of Asia, MCPA has consistently ranked in first place (Table 6). Although this chemical does not control

grasses well, it controls broad-leaved plants and sedges if applied when these are emerging from the water.

Fig. 8. This weed-free plot of BPI-76 rice was photographed 18 days after being sprayed with potassium salt of 2-methyl-4-chloro phenoxyacetic acid 22 days after transplanting. This treatment provided excellent weed control with little damage to the rice.

¹ Marketed as AGROXONE-4. The use of trade names in an Institute report is for identification and does not constitute an endorsement.

Table 6. Weed control (as percentage of initial count) by 13 promising herbicides in transplanted rice. Chemicals were sprayed 25 days after transplanting and were evaluated 13 days after spraying. Weeds were in 5-8 leaf stage; grasses were not a major problem; IRR1, 1962.

Herbicide group	Trade or common name	Rate of application (kg./ha.)	Control, in percentage		
			Broad-leaves	Sedges	Total
MCPA	Agroxone-4	1.0	95.7	94.9	95.6
Triazine	Ametryne	0.6	93.2	79.2	90.7
DPA	Stam F-34 ¹	3.0	95.4	76.8	90.4
BCMU (Neburon)	Kloben	2.0	95.2	67.1	89.6
Triazine	C-34690 ¹	3.0	92.5	71.1	88.3
MBA	Banvel-D ²	1.0	91.7	77.0	88.0
2, 4, 5-T	Shell 2, 4, 5-T	1.0	91.6	64.4	86.2
MCPA + MBA	Banlene	1.17,(1.0)	85.2	84.2	84.9
2, 4-D (Amine)	Hedonal	1.0	83.9	80.8	83.3
PCP	Santobrite	5.0	80.6	50.0	75.9
NPE	FW-925 (Grinding)	3.0	76.7	57.6	73.9
NPE	FW-925 (Florex)	3.0	78.9	37.7	72.4
Barban	Carbyne	0.5	76.1	41.0	70.2
Handweeded	—	—	100.0	100.0	100.0

¹ Moderate burning of leaves.

² Spreading of tillers.

Evidence of phytotoxicity to rice of other closely related growth regulating substances ("hormones" such as 2,4-D) was plentiful, but little such effect was observed with MCPA when applied at proper rates. Figure 8 shows the effects of application of MCPA at the recommended rate, while the photographs in Fig. 9 illustrate the symptoms of root damage resulting from an application of the amine salt of 2-methyl-4-chloro phenoxyacetic acid.

The relationship between weed classes and control measures applied at times approaching farmer practice is shown in Table 6. Although total weed production was high when not weeded, the proportion of grasses was less than 5 percent.

During the season, several dozen applications of DPA¹ (3,4-dichloropropionanilide) were made at widely varied rates, times, and environmental conditions. This chemical is used on large acreages of rice

¹ Marketed as Stam F-34 by Rohm and Haas Company.

in the United States and elsewhere, and it has proved to be selective and highly effective in controlling grassy weeds when applied to the drained rice crop at the 2-3

Fig. 9. The plant (58) sprayed with amine salt of 2-methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid shows typical toxicity symptoms similar to those described for 2,4-D. In comparison with the unsprayed plant (C), there is a loss of roots, swelling of leaf bases, and spreading of tillers. Scale divisions are 2 cm.

leaf stage of the weeds. Results at the Institute have ranged from excellent to poor, both in weed control and toxicity to rice. The most effective time for application is when the weeds are at the 3-4 leaf stage, as illustrated in Fig. 10. Toxicity was observed when DPA was applied at recommended rates on especially hot, sunny days, when water was not returned to the paddy on time, or possibly when sprayed immediately before or after sprays of insecticides. The dilution ratio was suspected, but this proved to be of no consequence at ratios from 1:5 to 1:50. When water was less than 10 cm. deep, the sedge control was inadequate.

A number of new herbicidal chemicals show substantial promise for lowland weed control. These include such market products as dichloropropionanilide, dichlorobenzonitrile, pentachlorophenol, 2,4-D, and methoxydichlorobenzoic acid com-

Fig. 10. Control of weeds in direct-seeded (dibbled) lowland rice by DPA was directly reflected in increased yield. When weeds were larger than 5-6 leaf size (20 days after planting), control at either 2 or 4 kg./ha. was not effective.

binations with MCPA. Other promising new materials still are experimental or newly commercial; these include MIN,

FIELD CREW APPLIES HERBICIDES in experimental plantings at nine different distances between rows.

increasing emphasis on use of higher amounts of fertilizers, losses from blast reach serious proportions in many areas where blast formerly was not considered serious.

Since use of increased amounts of nitrogenous fertilizer probably will continue, control of blast requires that resistant varieties be identified and distributed. If good resistant varieties are not available for any area, they must be developed. Some protection can be obtained with fungicides, but this presently is inconvenient and expensive.

The development of resistant varieties through breeding is complicated by lack of information in the tropics of (a) number and distribution of physiological races of the fungus, (b) sources of varietal resistance to important races, and (c) effective, simple techniques for testing for resistance or susceptibility.

Screening Varieties for Resistance

Identification of resistant varieties, for use as parents in crosses, is the primary step in breeding for resistance. Of the Institute's world collection of more than 9,000 varieties, more than 2,000 were tested in 1962 for seedling resistance to races occurring naturally in the Institute's fields. During 1963, an additional 4,000 were tested in cooperation with Varietal Improvement.

Notes on severity of attack on each variety were recorded, using a rating scale of 1 to 7 adopted during the year for international cooperative studies (Fig. 1). Of the 6,000 varieties tested, more than 1,000 were identified as resistant (ratings of 1 or 2) to the complex of races at Los Baños.

Intra-varietal Variation in Resistance

In the course of testing for seedling resistance in the Institute's nurseries, seedlings of many varieties did not react

uniformly. Within a single variety, some seedlings may be very resistant, others may be susceptible.

Seedlings of 60 varieties exhibiting variation in reaction were transplanted to the field to observe their plant characteristics at maturity. Some of the varieties were found to contain a number of plant types, undoubtedly the result of mixture or outcrossing. In others, the plants were uniform in morphological characteristics, and the differences in reaction were considered to be the result of continuing segregation for reaction to specific races.

Tjere Mas is a popular but susceptible variety in the Philippines. In the blast nursery, about .5 percent of the seedlings show high resistance. Several hundred of these resistant seedlings were transplanted singly, in pots and in the field, and were observed until maturity. About 35 percent were typical Tjere Mas plants, 50 percent were taller and had more compact panicles than is typical of Tjere Mas, and many others were intermediate types. About 15 percent had purple leaf sheaths while Tjere Mas normally is green. Among those having purple leaf sheaths, there also were differences in panicle characteristics. This seems to indicate that the resistant individuals originated from natural crosses. The resistant plants were given to the UPCA and to the Bureau of Plant Industry for such further selection and testing as seems desirable.

Physiological Races of Blast in the Philippines

The blast fungus consists of many physiological races which differ in their ability to infect specific varieties. Information on the number, prevalence, and distribution of specific races in each rice-growing region is essential if (a) plant breeders are to be able to combine in varieties resistance which will be effective over wide

PLANTING METHODS

A study of planting methods was initiated during the 1962 wet season. The *japonica* variety Chianung 242, and the Philippine *indicas*, Peta and BPI-76, were planted with eight different methods, then the plantings were subjected either to continuous flooding or to alternate flooding and drainage.

During this experiment, the direct-seeded plots consistently were 6-7 days ahead of the transplanted treatments in growth, although they were seeded at the same time. By harvest, this difference was reduced to 0-3 days.

Chianung 242 and Peta were infected, apparently uniformly, with a virus disease. This seriously reduced yields.

The drilled treatments yielded significantly more than those planted by other methods for two of the three varieties (Table 8). Peta, the tall, many-tillered *indica*, produced more when transplanted with wet-bed seedlings. The improved rice yields from drilled plantings may result in part, from the added protection the seed receives from birds, rats, and insects when placed deeply and covered with soil. Lodging in BPI-76 was reduced, and this may have increased the yield of that variety. Broadcasting on dry soil consistently was the lowest yielding practice.

The differences between the water treatments were not significant.

Table 8. Yields of three varieties with eight methods of planting, 1962 wet season.

Method of planting	Yields (ton/ha.) by variety and water treatment						Mean
	CHIANUNG 242		PETA		BPI-76		
	Continuous flood	Alternate flood	Continuous flood	Alternate flood	Continuous flood	Alternate flood	
Drilled in dry soil	4.3	3.7	3.9	3.7	5.7	6.0	4.6 ¹ a
Transplanted wet-bed seedlings	3.2	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.8	5.1	4.1 b
Transplanted dry-bed seedlings	3.1	3.4	3.7	4.1	5.2	5.0	4.1 b
Dibbled on mud	3.4	3.0	3.4	3.4	5.3	5.3	4.0 bc
Transplanted "Dapog" seedlings	3.1	3.0	3.9	3.6	4.9	5.2	3.9 bc
Broadcast in water	3.6	3.0	3.4	3.4	4.8	4.7	3.8 c
Broadcast on mud	3.1	3.3	3.4	3.3	5.0	4.7	3.8 cd
Broadcast on dry soil	1.7	2.0	2.4	2.5	3.4	3.6	2.6 d
Variety mean	3.1		3.5		4.9		
LSD:			0.50 ton				0.22 ton

¹ Method means followed by the same letter are not statistically different from each other.

CHEN CHENG, VICE PRESIDENT OF CHINA, discusses with the plant pathologist the work on the rice blast disease.

Plant Pathology

During 1963, the Institute's studies of the rice blast disease and of virus diseases were greatly expanded because of increas-

ing concern over seriousness of the losses they cause. Work also was initiated on the bacterial diseases of rice in the tropics.

RICE BLAST

The rice blast disease, caused by the fungus *Piricularia oryzae*, results in serious losses. It may destroy the crop if susceptible varieties are grown at high fertility levels and if rainfall is continuous at the stages of growth when rice is susceptible. Use of high plant populations per unit area and occurrence of long periods of cloudy weather also may predispose the crop to attack by the fungus.

In the past, blast apparently was not as

serious as it is at present in most of the tropical countries. If true, this may have been the result of (a) use of relatively resistant native varieties resulting from natural elimination of susceptible types as they appeared in farmer's fields, and/or (b) the relatively low levels of soil fertility and limited use of nitrogenous fertilizers. With the development of agronomically improved but blast susceptible varieties in some Asian countries, and with

increasing emphasis on use of higher amounts of fertilizers, losses from blast reach serious proportions in many areas where blast formerly was not considered serious.

Since use of increased amounts of nitrogenous fertilizer probably will continue, control of blast requires that resistant varieties be identified and distributed. If good resistant varieties are not available for any area, they must be developed. Some protection can be obtained with fungicides, but this presently is inconvenient and expensive.

The development of resistant varieties through breeding is complicated by lack of information in the tropics of (a) number and distribution of physiological races of the fungus, (b) sources of varietal resistance to important races, and (c) effective, simple techniques for testing for resistance or susceptibility.

Screening Varieties for Resistance

Identification of resistant varieties, for use as parents in crosses, is the primary step in breeding for resistance. Of the Institute's world collection of more than 9,000 varieties, more than 2,000 were tested in 1962 for seedling resistance to races occurring naturally in the Institute's fields. During 1963, an additional 4,000 were tested in cooperation with Varietal Improvement.

Notes on severity of attack on each variety were recorded, using a rating scale of 1 to 7 adopted during the year for international cooperative studies (Fig. 1). Of the 6,000 varieties tested, more than 1,000 were identified as resistant (ratings of 1 or 2) to the complex of races at Los Baños.

Intra-varietal Variation in Resistance

In the course of testing for seedling resistance in the Institute's nurseries, seedlings of many varieties did not react

uniformly. Within a single variety, some seedlings may be very resistant, others may be susceptible.

Seedlings of 60 varieties exhibiting variation in reaction were transplanted to the field to observe their plant characteristics at maturity. Some of the varieties were found to contain a number of plant types, undoubtedly the result of mixture or outcrossing. In others, the plants were uniform in morphological characteristics, and the differences in reaction were considered to be the result of continuing segregation for reaction to specific races.

Tjere Mas is a popular but susceptible variety in the Philippines. In the blast nursery, about .5 percent of the seedlings show high resistance. Several hundred of these resistant seedlings were transplanted singly, in pots and in the field, and were observed until maturity. About 35 percent were typical Tjere Mas plants, 50 percent were taller and had more compact panicles than is typical of Tjere Mas, and many others were intermediate types. About 15 percent had purple leaf sheaths while Tjere Mas normally is green. Among those having purple leaf sheaths, there also were differences in panicle characteristics. This seems to indicate that the resistant individuals originated from natural crosses. The resistant plants were given to the UPCA and to the Bureau of Plant Industry for such further selection and testing as seems desirable.

Physiological Races of Blast in the Philippines

The blast fungus consists of many physiological races which differ in their ability to infect specific varieties. Information on the number, prevalence, and distribution of specific races in each rice-growing region is essential if (a) plant breeders are to be able to combine in varieties resistance which will be effective over wide

areas, (b) farmers are to be informed of the genetics of resistance and the varieties which are safe or dangerous to grow in specific localities, and (c) studies of the nature or mechanism of resistance are to be useful.

Fig. 1. The seven degrees of reaction to blast used for classifying varieties. Scales 1 to 5 denote lesion types of increasing severity; scales 5 to 7 denote 25, 50, and 75-100 percent killing of the leaves.

Early evidence of the presence of different physiological races in the Philippines was obtained when Peta, which is resistant in Luzon, was severely damaged in the central islands of the Philippines. Collection of isolates from Leyte and subsequent inoculation of Peta at the Institute proved that the variety was very susceptible to the race collected (Table 1).

In 1963, a systematic study of the pathogenic races in the Philippines was initiated. More than 150 cultures of the fungus have been collected from various rice-growing regions, and single-spore stock cultures are being maintained for use in artificial inoculations. Each isolate is being inoculated to each of 110 prospective differential varieties. Included are 12 differential varieties from Japan, 16 from Taiwan, and 10 from the U.S.; the others are leading commercial varieties from southeast Asia and the U.S. This major study should lead to (a) the selection of a useful set of differentials for the Philippines and possibly for Asia, and (b) the identification of the major pathogenic races in the Philippines.

By late 1963, the 110 varieties had been inoculated with 40 of the isolates. To de-

monstrate the nature of the data being obtained, the reactions of 15 of the varieties to 12 isolates are presented in Table 1.

On the basis of the reaction of the 110 varieties to the first 40 isolates, at least a dozen races may be differentiated.

The varieties B401, H6 Cesariot, SLO 15, Chinsurah, Ginmasari, Aikoku, Aichi Asahi, Tjere Mas, Taichung Native 1, Tsai-yuan-chon, Woo-gen, Leuang Awn 29, Puang Nahk 16, and Khao-Teh-Haeng 17 are susceptible to all or nearly all 40 isolates. Tetep, CO 25, BJ 1, Jim Heung Suwon, Dular, Katakara DA2, Taichung 181, and Zenith were resistant to all or nearly all isolates. Varieties Taichung 65, Norin 29, and Norin 22 were resistant to most of the isolates.

Of the Philippine Seed Board varieties tested, Bengawan was resistant to all but a few isolates. Others were susceptible to several or many races.

International Uniform Blast Nurseries Program

The program of international uniform blast nurseries, initiated by FAO, now is

Table 1. Reactions of 15 varieties to 12 isolates of rice blast from each of six regions in the Philippines. Part of a study of reaction of 110 varieties to each of 150 isolates collected throughout the country.

Variety	Locality and isolate number													
	Isabela		Nueva Ecija			IRRI			Bicol		Iloilo		Leyte	
	I-31	I-107	I-7	I-25	I-42	I-1	I-9	I-8	I-101	I-129	I-98	I-104		
Katakara AD2	R ¹	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	
Bengawan	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	M	
Chianung 280	R	M	M	—	R	—	R	R	R	R	S	—	R	
Taichung 65	R	S	M	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	
FB 121	M	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	
FB 86	R	S	R	M	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	
Peta	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	
BE-3	S	S	R	S	R	M	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	
BPI-76	M	S	R	M	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	
FK 165	S	S	R	R	R	M	S	M	R	S	S	S	S	
Raminad str. 3	S	S	R	—	R	—	S	R	S	S	—	—	S	
Chianung 242	S	S	S	—	S	—	R	S	R	S	—	—	S	
Taichung Native 1	S	S	S	S	M	M	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	
Tjere Mas	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	M	S	R	R	S	
Kao Teh Haeng 17	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	

¹R = resistant; M = moderate or intermediate; S = susceptible.

being handled by the Institute. The purposes of this program are (a) to determine the race patterns in the rice-growing regions of individual nations and on a world-wide basis, (b) to identify sources of varietal resistance, and (c) to identify varieties of potential usefulness as international differentials.

At an international symposium on the rice blast disease, held at the Institute in July, the Institute was asked to assume responsibility for the program. Consequently, about 250 varieties were selected, including (a) the 38 differentials from Japan, the U.S., and Taiwan; (b) 100 varieties included in the 1962 FAO-IRC nurseries, and (c) other leading commercial varieties of southeast Asia which have distinct reaction types at Los Baños. Seed stocks have been purified and multiplied and are being supplied to 40 stations in 15 cooperating countries. The seed for each nursery is accompanied by detailed instructions for handling the test and by colored photographs which illustrate the seven degrees of reaction adopted for international use. By late 1963, 20 sets of seed had been shipped, and others will be sent at the times requested by the co-operators.

Relation of Leaf Blast and Neck Rot Resistance

There have been a number of reported cases of varieties resistant to leaf blast being attacked by the fungus at the flowering stage. This late attack results in development of lesions on the rachis, subsequent rotting, and failure of the panicles to produce seed. It is time-consuming, difficult, and costly to create satisfactory field conditions for testing reaction to neck rot. Consequently, it would help to know whether varieties resistant at the seedling stage also would be resistant to neck rot.

A series of field and artificial inocula-

tion studies are underway in an attempt to clarify the relationship.

Plants may be tested for resistance to neck rot by injecting spore suspensions into leaf sheaths containing emerging panicles (Figure 2). With an automatic syringe, a definite quantity of the suspension is injected when the panicles are half emerged. Thus, the peduncle remains in the sheath for 1 or 2 days. The speed of emergence differs among varieties.

By using different tillers of a single plant, its reaction to several isolates can be determined simultaneously. Or, the different tillers may be inoculated with a single isolate to obtain additional replicates.

Preliminary results indicate that no neck rot develops if the spores injected into the

Fig. 2. In the study of neck rot infection, a spore suspension is injected into the leaf sheath of an emerging panicle.

Table 2. Number of neck infections occurring when emerging panicles of five Peta plants were inoculated with isolates of blast fungus to which Peta was resistant or susceptible in the seedling stage.

Race	Seedling reaction of Peta	No. neck infections/No. panicles inoculated					Neck rot (%)
		Peta plant inoculated					
		1	2	3	4	5	
A	R	—	0/6	—	—	—	0
B	R	0/6	0/5	0/1	0/6	0/7	0
D	R	—	—	—	0/12	—	0
T	R	—	—	—	—	0/11	0
V	S	16/16	10/10	2/2	—	—	100
I	S	—	—	—	5/7	4/7	64

sheath are produced by a race to which the test plant is resistant at the seedling stage. However, if the spores are from a race to which the plant is susceptible as a seedling, neck rot probably will occur. This is illustrated by the partial results given in Table 2.

Seedlings of Peta had been found resistant to races A, B, D, and T. When spores from these races were injected into sheaths of Peta containing emerging panicles, no neck rot developed. Seedlings of Peta are susceptible to races V and I; these races also are capable of causing neck rot on Peta.

In another test, 36 panicles of the variety H-5 were inoculated with spores of five different isolates to which it is resistant in the seedling stage; with one possible exception, no panicles were infected (Table 3). When spores of races causing leaf blast in FK165 and Tjere Mas were injected into sheaths of developing panicles of these same varieties, a high percentage of infection occurred.

These results indicate that isolates to which the leaf stage of a variety is susceptible will infect the neck and pro-

duce neck rot, while isolates to which the leaf stage is resistant should not infect the neck. Similarly, if neck rot occurs on a variety in the field, it probably is caused by a race also capable of attacking the leaves.

More than one race may exist in a single locality. Peta normally is resistant to blast at the Institute, in fact, it is used as the resistant check in the blast nurseries. However, a few typical blast lesions occasionally occur on Peta during the later part of the year. Isolation of the fungus from these lesions and reinoculation to Peta seedlings resulted in severe infection.

Spore Production on Artificial Media

Large numbers of spores of individual isolates must be produced on artificial media for the many artificial inoculations required in physiologic race studies.

Since the fungus usually does not grow and sporulate well in synthetic media, more than 50 kinds of natural media, with or without vitamins added, have been tried with more than 50 isolates. Rice

Table 3. Number of neck infections occurring when emerging panicles of four varieties were inoculated with five isolates of blast to which the varietal seedling reactions were known.

Variety	Seedling reaction	No. neck infections/No. panicles inoculated					Neck rot (%)
		RACE					
		A	C	D	H	I	
Peta	R	—	—	0/3	—	—	0
H-5	R	1/13 ¹	0/6	0/2	0/10	0/5	2.8
FK165	S	—	5/6	—	7/8	8/9	87.0
Tjere mas	S	12/17	2/2	24/25	10/10	4/5	88.0

¹ Reaction in doubt.

polish, barley seed, germinating rice seeds, rice straw, "A" and "B" media of Takahashi, Misato's medium, etc., which other workers found favorable for spore production, were included.

The addition of biotin and thiamine to certain media, such as potato-dextrose-sugar (PDA), increased spore production. The addition of coconut milk to PDA permitted abundant sporulation of many isolates but not of others. Barley seed, oatmeal, rice straw, rice polish agar, and yeast plus PDA were good for some isolates, but poor for others. Banana stalk and leaf stalk of the water hyacinth have been favorable media for many isolates. The differences in the number of spores produced on some of the more favorable media are illustrated in Table 4.

Some isolates produced abundant spores in most of the media used; some produced few spores in all media tried. No single medium was suitable for all isolates for

spore production, although some were favorable for many isolates. Isolates of this fungus differ in requirements for nutrients and other factors affecting growth, and it may be assumed that different factors are required by different isolates for spore production. It also seems that the time required to produce the maximum number of spores varies with different isolates. Isolate No. 96 produced abundant spores in 5 days on PDA with coconut milk, while isolate No. 106 produced abundant spores in 38 days on banana decoction agar. A further study of the differences in physiologic responses among isolates is underway.

Airborne Population of *Piricularia*

The estimate collection of airborne conidia of *Piricularia* by spore trap was continued, and the data for a complete year from June, 1962, to May, 1963, are in Fig.

Table 4. Relative number of spores produced by isolates of *Piricularia oryzae* on various media.

Fungus isolate (No.)	Coconut milk & PDA	Barley seed	Rice Stem (node)	Banana stalk	Oat meal	Water hyacinth
1	++++			+++		
2	+				+++++	
5	+	+	++	+	+++++	
6	++		+++++	+++++	++	
7	+++++			+++++	+++++	
9	+++++	++	++	+++++		
11	++	+++++	+++++	+++++	++	
15	+		+++++		+++++	
16	+			+++	+	
19	++++		+++++	+++++	+++++	
22	+			(268) +	+	
42	++++	++++	+++++	+++++	+++++	
45	++++	+			+++	
66	+	+++++	++++	++++	++++	
93	+		++++			
94	++++					
96	+++++					
106	+		++++			+++++
119						++++
126						+++++
128						+++++
129						+++++

+ = 1-5 spores under one low-power microscope field
 ++ = 6-15 " "
 +++ = 16-35 " "
 ++++ = 36-150 " "
 ++++++ = 150 or more spores

Fig. 3. Number of conidia of *Piricularia* trapped on slides each month at Los Baños from June, 1962, to May, 1963.

3. There were more spores during the rainy than during the dry season, but spores were present all year. The amount of spores in the air was affected not only by the amount of precipitation but by the duration of rain, temperature, dew period, and other climatic factors, as well as by the amount of rice crop and varieties planted in the field.

Chemical Control of Blast

Phenyl mercuric acetate (PMA) and other organo-mercury compounds and blasticidin, and antibiotic preparation,

have been used extensively in Japan for blast disease control. The use of these and other chemicals in the tropics has encountered technical and socio-economical difficulties. The relatively low value of rice and the relatively high cost of chemicals render the application of chemicals much less profitable. The organic mercuries are known to be phytotoxic to many *indica* rice varieties. The frequent and heavy rain showers in the tropics greatly reduce the protective effect of chemicals. However, chemical control may be employed as an emergency measure.

Thirteen chemicals, including several antibiotic preparations and others (actidione, agrimycin, mycostatin, sabithane, actidione-thiram), together with PMA and blasticidin S, the two standard chemicals for blast control, were compared for their effect on spore germination, mycelial growth, phytotoxicity, as well as for effectiveness for field control. Actidione-thiram was comparable to PMA and blasticidin S, non-phytotoxic, but not effective for field control. Further studies indicated that decomposition by sunlight probably was the reason for the ineffectiveness of Thiram in the field.

PART OF THE BLAST NURSERY where varieties are screened for resistance to the rice blast disease.

VIRUS DISEASES

When the Institute was being organized in 1961, the opinion prevailed in south-east Asia that virus diseases of rice were relatively unimportant. Consequently, no initial provision was made for their study. However, the Institute's crops were badly damaged by virus diseases during the 1962 wet season, and, by necessity, a research program was started.

In the 1961-1962 Annual Report, the observation of mosaic, stunt (or dwarf), yellow dwarf, and one new and severe virus disease, were reported. It now appears that rice virus diseases found in the Philippines include (a) "orange-leaf," which was first described in 1962, (b) "tungro," (c) yellow dwarf, and (d) dwarf. A possible fifth virus disease is being investigated.

Further studies of the transmission of "orange leaf," yellow dwarf, and dwarf (stunt) were made during the past year to identify the viruses found on rice at the Institute and elsewhere in the Philippines.

"Orange Leaf"

Study of the "orange leaf" disease revealed that there actually are two viruses involved in this complex. One is "orange leaf," an apparently new virus on rice, and the other is "tungro," which has been observed and studied in the Philippines but apparently was confused with dwarf or stunt disease. "Orange leaf" and "tungro" often occur together, but may be separated by their symptoms and insect vectors.

The symptoms of the "orange leaf" disease are the characteristic orange color of leaves of the affected seedlings, gradual rolling of leaves as the disease advances and eventual death of the plants. Affected plants seldom survive. It is transmitted by the leafhopper *Inazuma dorsalis*.

"Tungro" affected plants have various shades of yellowing of leaves, usually associated with dark brown spots of various shapes, measuring 1-3 mm. Affected plants often are stunted, but in more resistant varieties, the stunting is not noticeable. The virus does not kill the affected plant, but at maturity it will have few and small panicles. It is transmitted by *Nephotettix apicalis*.

While a detailed survey of the two virus diseases was not made, they have been observed in various parts of the Philippines. The "tungro" disease seems to be common. Outside the Philippines, "orange leaf" was found in northern Thailand. "Tungro" also is common in Taiwan (China), and it possibly occurred in Italy (identified by specimen).

The details on the transmission studies are stated below.

During the past year, it was found that individual males, females, and nymphs of the leafhopper *Inazuma dorsalis* (Motsch.) transmitted the "orange leaf" disease of rice (Table 5). About 14 percent of the disease-free population was capable of transmission after feeding on diseased plants. No transmission was observed with the six other species of leafhoppers common in rice fields, including *Nephotettix apicalis* (Motsch.), the principal vector of the dwarf and yellow dwarf viruses of rice.

Table 5. Transmission of the "orange leaf" disease by *Inazuma dorsalis*.

Insects per cage (no.)	Insects previously fed on diseased plants			Disease-free insects		
	Total insects (no.)	Total plants (no.)	Total plants with symptoms (no.)	Total insects (no.)	Total plants (no.)	Total plants with symptoms (no.)
1	215	215	31 ^a	50	50	0
5	125	25	3	50	10	0
10	200	20	4	100	10	0

^a Transmitted by 12 females, 9 males, and 10 nymphs.

Fig. 4. Taichung Native-1, 70 days old, experimentally infected with the "tungro" disease. Left, healthy; center and right, infected at 35 days and 15 days of age, respectively.

"Tungro" Disease

In glasshouse experiments at the Institute, "tungro" has been repeatedly transmitted by *Nephotettix apicalis* (Motsch.) in different sequences among rice varieties. The two principal symptoms observed were stunting and partial yellowing of the leaves, extending from bright yellow to pale orange, starting from the tip of the leaf (Fig. 4). Sometimes, only stunting or yellowing was present, but susceptible varieties always show both (Table 6).

Table 6. Results of inoculations of four rice varieties with single leafhoppers (*N. apicalis*) previously fed on plants infected with the "tungro" disease.¹

Variety	Total plants (no.)	Number of plants showing symptoms of:		
		Stunting and partial yellowing	Stunting only	Partial yellowing only
Taichung Native 1	50	30	0	0
Palawan	40	19	0	3
Peta	45	0	0	4
FB-121	48	0	0	6

¹ Of 30 healthy control plants (Taichung Native 1) caged with disease-free insects, none showed either stunting or yellowing.

The leafhoppers acquired and transmitted the virus either as nymphs or adults but did so more readily as adults. About 60 percent of the virus-free population transmitted the disease after feeding on virus source plants.

"Tungro" often is associated with "orange leaf," as was observed at the Institute in 1962. It also occurs together with dwarf (or stunt) as reported earlier by investigators in the Philippines, and as recent transmission tests have shown.

Dwarf Disease

The dwarf disease which results in stunting but no yellowing has been known and studied in Japan for many years. The leafhoppers (*N. cincticeps* and *I. dorsalis*) are the only known vectors of the virus. The virus is transmitted from one generation to the next through the eggs.

In repeated glasshouse experiments, dwarf appeared to be transmitted by *I. dorsalis*. *N. apicalis* seems not capable of transmitting dwarf, but instead the inoculated plants show symptoms of "tungro" when the source plants were dwarf plants from the field. Further studies are underway to confirm these results.

Yellow Dwarf Disease

Yellow dwarf, an insect-transmitted virus disease of rice, was first observed at the Institute in 1962, although it probably was present in the area much earlier. Yellowing, stunting, and proliferation, typical symptoms of the disease, were noted (Fig. 5).

The methods of transmission of this virus have been investigated thoroughly in Japan. It is efficiently transmitted in Japan by the leafhopper *Nephotettix cincticeps* Uhler, but recent studies at the Institute indicate that *N. apicalis* transmitted the disease. The presence of *N. cincticeps* in the Philippines is not yet established.

Fig. 5. A ratoon crop of Tainan 3 in the field showing some plants infected with the yellow dwarf disease.

Search for Resistance

Losses from virus diseases can be minimized by (a) use of resistant varieties, and (b) control of the insect vectors. A field has been established at the Institute for testing varieties for resistance, particularly to the more prevalent "orange leaf" and "tungro" diseases. In addition, a limited number of varieties have been test-

Table 7. Preliminary results of greenhouse studies on the reaction of 12 Philippine varieties to the "orange leaf" and "tungro" diseases of rice.¹

Variety	"Orange leaf"		"Tungro"	
	Test plants (no.)	Infected (no.)	Test plants (no.)	Infected (no.)
Gjere Mas	32	8	32	4
Peta	32	0	32	3
Bengawan	32	1	32	8
BPI-76	32	6	32	12
FB-121	32	0	40	6
BE-3	24	4	32	9
Raminad Str. 3	24	1	32	8
SK-36 Str. 482	32	1	40	6
Azucena	32	3	32	11
Mangarez	24	2	32	10
Palawan	32	3	32	9
Dinalaga	24	1	37	7

¹ One insect per plant (3-4 leaf stage); insects remained on the plants until death.

ed by artificial inoculation. Partial results in Table 7 illustrate that most varieties tested probably are not highly resistant to "orange leaf" and "tungro" and a few appear quite susceptible; however, these limited data do not establish varietal differences in reaction. Such differences must be established with larger populations, over seasons.

BACTERIAL DISEASES OF RICE

Bacterial leaf blight, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*, and bacterial leaf streak, caused by *X. oryricola*, are the two most destructive bacterial diseases of rice presently known. The former is widely distributed in all rice-growing countries in Asia, while the latter is common in tropical Asia, but not present in Japan.

Bacterial leaf blight has been studied in Japan, but the available information is restricted to rice varieties and the causal bacteria in Japan. Little is known about the disease in the tropics.

These two diseases differ primarily in the symptoms produced (Fig. 6). In

bacterial leaf blight, pale greenish or white lesions occur in waves along one or both margins of the leaf. This is a typical vascular disease. In bacterial leaf streak, water-soaked, dark-green streaks form at first, then expand, and turn yellowish brown. The causal bacteria attack the parenchyma tissues.

Bacteriophages, which generally are quite specific in the strains of bacteria they attack, are useful in differentiation of races of the bacteria, in classification of bacterial species, and in forecasting outbreaks of bacterial diseases.

Fig. 6. Symptoms of bacterial leaf blight (left) and bacterial leaf streak (right).

Phage Typing of Causal Bacteria

Six types of bacteriophages, differing in reaction to strains of bacteria and in plaque morphology, have been isolated using blight and streak organisms. The history and plaque morphology of each are shown in Table 8.

Table 9 shows the results of classification of 43 blight isolates and 51 isolates of streak organisms based upon their reactions to the six bacteriophages.

Although the phage reaction was clear in most cases of blight pathogens (Fig.

7), the degree of lysis caused by SP2 and SP3 phages considerably varied with the kind of isolates in streak pathogens. Whether this results from the difference in plaque-forming efficiency or by the phage mutants is a matter for future study.

One isolate from leaf blight produced only streak symptoms on the inoculated plant. This indicates that this isolate is the streak organism from a leaf attacked by both blight and streak pathogens. Also, one isolate from leaf blight reacted to phage from streak, and four isolates from streak reacted to phage from leaf blight. Inocu-

Table 8. History and plaque morphology of six bacteriophages used in studies, 1963.

Phage type	Source	Locality	Plaque morphology
BP1	Field water	IRRI	2.0-3.0 mm. in diameter, circular, clear, no halo.
BP2	Canal water	"	1.0-1.5 mm. in diameter, clear, circular, no halo.
SP1	Diseased leaf	"	1.0-2.0 in diameter, circular, clear, sometimes with halo.
SP2	Diseased leaf	"	Minute dots, (about 0.1-0.2 mm. in diameter), circular, clear, no halo. Plaques are sometimes obscure when plated with plenty of bacteria.
SP3	Diseased leaf	"	0.5-2.0 mm. in diameter, conspicuous halo with small clear center of 0.3-1.0 mm. in diameter. Sometimes halo looks like rings around clear center.
SP4	Diseased leaf	Thailand	1.5-2.5 mm. in diameter, circular, clear, no halo.

Table 9. Virulence of six phage types on lysotypes of bacterial blight and streak organisms, and frequency of isolation of the lysotypes in Luzon, Philippines.

BLIGHT PATHOGEN							
Bacterial lysotype	Phage Type						Isolates (No.)
	BP1	BP2	SP1	SP2	SP3	SP4	
1	+++	+++	-	-	+++	-	25
2	-	+++	-	-	-	-	5
3	+++	+++	-	-	-	-	5
4	+++	+++	-	+++	+++	-	2
5	+++	+++	+++	-	+++	-	1
6	+++	+++	-	+++	-	-	1
7	-	-	-	-	+++	+++	1
8	-	-	+++	+	+++	+++	1
9	-	-	-	-	-	-	2

STREAK PATHOGEN							
Phage lysotype	Phage Type						Isolates (No.)
	BP1	BP2	SP1	SP2	SP3	SP4	
1	-	-	-	+++	-	+++	11
2	-	-	+++	+++ ¹	+++	+++	14
3	-	-	-	- ₂	-	+++	8
4	-	-	-	-	+++	+++	2
5	-	-	-	+++ ³	+++	+++	13
6	-	-	+++	++	-	+++	3

+++ = strongly attacked; ++ = moderately attacked; + = weakly attacked.

- = not attacked by phage type indicated.

¹ = 5 isolates were weakly attacked by SP2 (+).

₂ = 4 isolates were lysed weakly by both phages of SP2 and SP3 (+), and 2 by SP2 alone.

³ = 4 isolates were weakly lysed by SP2 alone.

lation tests will indicate whether they are leaf blight or streak organisms.

To determine the presence and population of the bacterial leaf blight pathogen in water of paddy fields and canals, attempts were made to isolate bacteriophage from 95 plots throughout the Institute. The bacterial culture used as indicator was isolate B8 from leaf blight (Fig. 7), the pathogenicity of which has been proved. The number of phages usually indicates the relative number of the bacteria. The results were:

No. of phage plaques per ml. of sample (relative number of bacteria)	Number of plots
0	28
1-100	26
101-1,000	23
1,001-10,000	12
10,001 and above	6

These results show a high bacterial population in many of the plots and, whenever climatic conditions are favorable, an outbreak of leaf blight may be expected. The phage population indicated above varied a great deal with the location where the samples were collected. In the same plot the number of phages may vary from 0 to 3,250 in one test.

A high population usually was found in plots where the leaf blight disease was present, as in the case of the plot of BPI-76 (Table 10). The phage population also changed greatly from day to day. Table 10 also shows typical changes of phage populations in water collected every day at the same place in fields and canals.

Fig. 7. Top, plaques of phage BP1 on bacterial blight isolate, B8. Plaques are transparent; black color is the background. Bottom, phage reaction of some lysotypes of the streak organism. Of six bacteriophages, three produced transparent plaques; black color shows through.

Varietal Resistance to Blight and Streak Diseases

Varietal reactions to the blight and streak diseases in the Varietal Improvement breeding plots varied from severe infection to slight or no infection, but reactions varied somewhat from plot to plot.

The reactions of a small number of varieties when artificially inoculated with the two diseases revealed differences in behavior. For example, Varieties 221/

Table 10. Daily change of phage population in water from the fields and canals.

Date	Weather at time collected	Population in numbers	
		BPI 76 blighted plot	East side small canal
September			
11	Cloudy	9,250	23
12	Cloudy	130	100
13	Cloudy	350	160
14	Cloudy	1,500	5
15	Fine	—	—
16	Fine	2,500	900
17	Fine	95,000	85
18	Fine	56,200	95
19	Fine	2,700	15
20	Fine	44,000	280
21	Fine		1,000
26		35,000	3,050
27		44,000	225
30	Cloudy		43,000
October			
1		50,000	450
2	Fine	21,300	600
3	Fine	40,000	970
4	Fine		18,800
7		5,250	270
8	Cloudy	1,000	350
9	Fine		2,000
10	Fine	17,200	80
11	Fine	850	70

BCIV/178/8 and Hsinchu 55 were relatively resistant to leaf blight, while Yuan-li was susceptible. Varieties Hsinchu, 55, Hsinchu 54, and Kaohsiug 53 were resistant to streak, and 221/BCIV/178/8 and Yuan-li were susceptible. These results coincide well with the field observations, especially in resistance to the streak disease.

EACH SEASON, 1,000 VARIETIES from the world collection are screened for their resistance to the rice stem borer.

Entomology

The rice stem borers constitute one of the major problems in rice cultivation in most parts of Asia. Stem borers occur regularly, infest plants from seedling to maturity, and, in areas where variations in annual temperatures are slight and multiple rice cropping is practiced, maintain fairly high populations throughout the year.

In experiments at the Institute in 1963, plots receiving the most effective insecticidal treatments yielded 87 percent more grain than untreated controls during the dry season and 97 to 102 percent more during the wet season. Other insect pests probably accounted for some loss, but the general correlation between stem borer infestation and yield indicates that major losses were caused by stem borers.

Present methods of borer control are not satisfactory because of the high population of the insect in overlapping generations,

the larval habit of boring inside the plants shortly after hatching from the eggs, and the short insecticidal residual periods resulting from frequent rains, high humidity, and warm temperature. Effective control requires repeated applications of insecticides, something farmers are rarely able to do. Thus, a significant percentage of the crop is lost to this insect every season.

The research projects in entomology are aimed at developing better methods of borer control. These can be broadly classified into (a) Varietal resistance to stem borer infestations, and (b) insecticidal control. The first is primarily a preventive measure and, depending on the degree of resistance, may act as a principal control measure or as a supplement to other measures.

Insecticidal studies are directed at finding ways to improve present control methods by using better insecticides at pro-

per times of application and, also, to determine whether there is any approach, other than use of foliar applications, which may help improve the control efficiency and reduce the frequency of the treatments.

Three species of stem borers, *Chilo suppressalis* Walker, *Tryporyza incertulas* Walker (formerly known as *Schoenobius incertulas* W.), and *Sesamia inferens* Walker, have been recorded in the area of the Institute.

The percentages of these species, as determined from the larval population, are presented in Fig. 1. Light trap data on moth populations are also maintained. It is evident that 90 percent of the total stem borer population was constituted by *Chilo suppressalis* W. throughout the year, except in August when *Tryporyza incertulas* W. formed 58 percent of the total. Furthermore, the populations of *Chilo suppressalis* W. and *Tryporyza incertulas* W. seemed to develop in negative correlation with each other. The population of *Sesamia*, however, remained low. Therefore, in all field experiments reported here, *Chilo suppressalis* W. has been the major test insect. All the laboratory and greenhouse tests, including artificial infestations in the field, were limited to this species.

The mass rearing of the stem borers remains a major factor limiting controlled experiments. A simple technique developed at the institute works efficiently, except that the changing of stalks every fifth day

Fig. 1. Seasonal variations in percentages of larval populations of different species of stem borers.

consumes time. Studies are underway to determine whether the insects may be reared through the entire larval period without changing the food materials. These methods include rearing on sterilized rice stems, with and without addition of insect nutrients, and on a synthetic diet. Sterilized plants supplemented with nutritive solutions may provide a satisfactory medium for this purpose.

VARIETAL RESISTANCE TO THE STEM BORER

Screening for Varietal Resistance

A total of 2,231 varieties have been tested for their field resistance to rice stem borer infestations. These tests are made simultaneously under field and greenhouse conditions. Under the current procedures, 1,000 varieties are tested each season.

Two 5-meter rows of each of the test varieties are planted in each of three replications. In the earlier work, two rows of a borer susceptible variety were planted around each experimental plot. These rows were found not to be necessary, and they were abandoned in later tests. Simi-

Fig. 2. Differences between two varieties in stem borer susceptibility. The varieties did not receive any insecticidal treatments.

larly, later tests indicated that results of almost the same efficiency may be obtained from two test rows as from four.

These varieties were exposed to natural infestation of the rice stem borers (Fig. 2). To be sure that none of the varie-

ties escaped infestation, one hill in each row was artificially infested with stem borer eggs by attaching an egg mass to the leaves. The larvae hatching from these eggs also migrated to adjoining hills, the number varying with the susceptibility

Fig. 3. Varieties differ in their susceptibility to the rice stem borer. When infested with 10 freshly hatched larvae, some varieties were heavily damaged within a few days after infestation.

of the varieties.

The percentages of dead hearts and white heads were observed, and the plants were graded for their general freedom from borer infestation. The averages of these observations were added to form an index of infestation for each variety. The individual tillers of varieties with the lowest index numbers, together with a few of those having higher index numbers, were dissected for recording infested stalks and the stem borer population.

The varieties with lower indices of infestation and lower percentages of infested tillers, together with a few susceptible types, were selected and tested more thoroughly for resistance by implanting egg masses on several hills in the field. In the greenhouse, three replications of four plants each were infested with 10 freshly hatched rice stem borer larvae per plant (Figs. 3 and 4). Numbers of dead hearts and white heads were observed, and finally, the plants were dissected to determine the percentages of infested tillers, the proportion of insect gallery to plant height, and the number of borer larvae.

During the first general screening, 237 varieties, representing leading commercial

Fig. 4. Although infested with 10 freshly hatched larvae at the same time as the varieties in Fig. 3, other varieties lost their resistance during the later stage of plant growth.

varieties from around the world, were tested in the field and in the greenhouse. From these, 81 were selected and were retested in replicated trials in the greenhouse and in the field. Finally, 37 varieties were selected. These are being further tested for stem borer susceptibility at the Institute and at two other experiment stations. From the second general screening, another

Table 1. Variation in rice stem borer susceptibility among some of the 988 varieties of rice, January-May, 1963.

Variety	Percentages of:			Average number larvae/hill
	Dead hearts	White heads	Infested tillers	
Chang Li	2.9	3.1	14.1	0.2
Pe Be Fun	3.1	1.0	32.3	1.4
Yen Tu	3.0	2.3	36.2	2.4
Bolibod	3.3	3.2	43.8	1.6
Saba	3.5	6.3	71.7	9.1
Hsiao Wu Tsu Tsi	3.6	2.9	19.2	1.6
6517	3.9	1.4	37.1	1.5
Thailand	5.1	1.2	31.9	1.1
Hugh Pee Gook	5.4	6.9	24.6	0.5
SLO 2	5.6	1.4	40.8	3.9
CI 45	5.8	0.9	31.8	1.2
Gendjah Ratji	6.9	4.4	82.5	7.3
Inilang-ilang x Fortuna	15.1	7.9	83.6	16.4
Inabaca	16.0	10.1	62.9	11.1
Storm Proof	20.2	10.2	65.3	3.7
Creole Bred (I-529)	22.4	12.1	65.5	12.9
Perurutong (nb)	23.4	8.8	74.5	5.9
Chung Chang	27.7	3.2	63.9	9.1

Table 2. Variations in rice stem borer susceptibility among some of the 1,000 varieties of rice tested. June-October, 1963.

Variety	Percentages of:		
	Dead hearts	White heads	Infestation
Sekitori	0.2	0.8	5.3
Su won (Sui geng) PI 162300	0.6	1.9	7.8
Su won (Sui geng) PI 162302	0.7	1.9	7.9
Vulgaria	0.7	0.8	8.2
Balillo	0.8	1.6	13.2
Wase-shirage	0.9	0.9	10.0
CI 9498	0.9	1.9	12.4
Originario	1.1	0.8	9.5
Tung Ting Yellow	1.1	2.8	12.1
Koahsiang	1.2	0.6	13.9
Bmt. 53 R-3556	1.8	2.4	35.8
T. Patna sel. (Dwarf)	1.9	5.5	46.8
CI 9122 x Rexoro	2.3	17.9	32.8
Americano 1600 (231174)	4.9	2.6	65.9
Hill medium rogue	10.4	0.8	43.5
Kinai Wase No. 161	12.9	2.3	53.4
Criollo de Victoria	14.7	2.5	54.4
CI 2474-3	22.9	2.9	45.6

set of 132 varieties was selected and has been planted in three replications in the field for further tests of resistance.

The results for some representative varieties from the general screening tests are in Tables 1 and 2. The level of stem borer infestation varied widely, being evident in the ranges of 0.17 to 28 percent for dead hearts, 0.52 to 18 percent white heads, and 5 to 84 percent infested stems.

In general, *japonica* varieties had lower infestations than the *indica* types (Fig. 5). This difference was more pronounced in the earlier stage of crop growth, but for white head formation, many *japonica* types became more susceptible than *indica* types. There was no correlation between dead heart and white head formations in different varieties. The early maturing varieties generally were less infested than those maturing late. There were many late-maturing varieties with low infestations; conversely, many early-maturing varieties were heavily infested.

Morphological Characters and Stem Borer Susceptibility

To determine whether variations in stem borer infestation are associated with any

plant characters, 33 varieties of diverse morphological characters were tested in the field. The correlations between degree of infestation and various plant characters were determined.

These tests show that height of the stalk, length of the flag leaf, width of the flag leaf, size of stalk, and size of lumen all directly correlated with the percentages of infested tillers (Figs. 6 and 7). There was no correlation between infestation and the thickness of the stem walls, and the percentage of infested tillers was negatively correlated with number of tillers per hill (Fig. 8).

Development of Borer Larvae on Different Hosts

The host plants play a vital role in the survival and developmental potential of the rice stem borers feeding on them. These effects result from various factors, one of which is the food value of the host plants.

In both field and greenhouse tests, the size of the stem borer population varies greatly with variety. To determine whether this variation in larval survival is associated with variations in chemical con-

Fig. 5. Variations in dead heart and white head formation in *indica* and *japonica* varieties. In general, *japonica* types were less susceptible to dead heart formations.

stituents of the plants, the development of freshly hatched larvae was studied on cut stem pieces of different varieties. Cut stems were used to remove the possibility of larval mortality caused by the toughness of the tissues or the thickness of the stem walls.

Five 3-inch pieces of rice stems were placed in glass vials with fine mesh screen lids. Each was infested with eight freshly hatched larvae. These vials then were incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. At 5-day intervals, the stem pieces were changed with fresh ones and the number of living and

Fig. 6. The external and internal diameter of rice stalks were positively correlated with the percentages of tillers infested with stem borers.

Fig. 7. Wider flag leaves in rice plants render them more susceptible to stem borer infestations.

dead larvae were recorded. For caging larvae beyond the second instar of development, single stems were used for each larva.

Ten varieties, five highly resistant and five highly susceptible, were selected for these studies. The survival of the larvae was significantly lower on varieties found

resistant in the field and greenhouse testings than on susceptible ones.

It also was found that the apical parts of the resistant plants caused higher mortality of the larvae than the basal parts, but this was not true for susceptible varieties.

Further, it appeared that the resistance of the plants varied with the stage of plant growth. Therefore, the resistant varieties, Chianan 2 and Taitung 16, and the susceptible varieties, Sapan Kwai and Rexoro, were tested for larval survival at different stages of plant growth. On plants beyond 45 days of age, the larvae were caged separately on apical and basal parts.

Larvae also were caged on undetached stems of these plants in the greenhouse. In this series, plants at 15, 30, 45, 60, and 75 days of growth were used.

The freshly hatched larvae had slightly higher mortality on resistant than on susceptible plants particularly on young plants. The larvae when reared on stem pieces in the laboratory had significantly lower survival on apical parts than on basal parts of both resistant varieties. The survival of the larvae increased significantly on the apical parts of the resistant plants with an increase in plant age, but

Table 3. Survival of freshly hatched *Chilo suppressalis* W. larvae caged on stem pieces from apical and basal parts of resistant and susceptible plants.¹

Variety	Plant parts used	Age of plants							
		45 days				75 days			
		Number of living larvae after:							
		5 days	10 days	15 days	20 days	5 days	10 days	15 days	20 days
RESISTANT VARIETIES:									
Chianan 2	Apical	12.0	4.0	0.4	0.4	23.6	16.4	10.4	10.0
	Basal	23.6	16.4	10.4	10.0	23.2	12.4	10.0	8.0
Taitung 16	Apical	12.8	2.8	0.1	0.1	17.6	7.6	4.4	1.6
	Basal	26.4	20.4	16.4	14.4	19.2	8.0	6.8	2.0
SUSCEPTIBLE VARIETIES:									
Rexoro	Apical	18.8	8.4	8.0	6.4	16.0	10.8	6.8	6.0
	Basal	26.8	16.8	14.4	13.2	25.2	21.6	17.6	13.6
Sapan Kwai	Apical	14.8	4.0	3.2	3.2	17.6	10.8	7.2	4.0
	Basal	13.2	6.8	6.8	6.8	14.0	9.6	9.2	8.4

¹ Forty larvae were caged on each treatment, and the figures represent average of five replications.

Fig. 8. The average number of tillers per hill in a variety was negatively correlated with the percentage of infested tillers. The correlation was highly significant.

this was not true either on basal parts of resistant plants, or on apical or basal parts of susceptible plants (Table 3). This indicates that the apical parts of resistant plants at 60 days of age are not suitable hosts for stem borer larvae. When caged on intact plants, the larvae had higher mortality on the apical parts of most varieties. On 75-day-old plants, the larvae had lower survival on the apical parts of all the plants; however, the survival on resistant plants was much lower than on susceptible varieties.

Varietal x Insecticidal Interactions In Borer Control

As is evident from the above information, Taitung 16 and Chianan 2 had consistently lower infestations in the field and, in laboratory and greenhouse studies, developed lower stem borer populations than did Sapan Kwai and Rexoro. To study the possible role of plant resistance in controlling stem borers, 25 plots were planted

to each of these four varieties. These 3 x 5 meter plots were protected from insect infestation during different stages of plant growth by spraying with 0.04% endrin to determine whether (a) varietal resistance and insecticide act cumulatively to reduce insect infestation, and (b) resistance or susceptibility of these varieties changes with plant growth.

All varieties were planted and harvested on the same day, except Rexoro, which was harvested 6 days later. Four different insecticidal treatments were made, the details and results of which being given in the accompanying graphs (Fig. 9). The experiment was block randomized, and replicated five times.

On 40-day-old plants, the percentages of dead hearts in the two resistant varieties were much lower than in the susceptible varieties, whether protected or not (Fig. 9a). The same was true for the percentages of infested tillers. These ranged from 1.4 to 5.4 percent for resistant, and 9 to 22.8 percent for susceptible varieties. The total number of eggs laid also was higher on susceptible varieties than on resistant ones. All these differences became more apparent with the 95-day-old plants.

The infestations in plots protected with endrin sprays ranged from 10 to 20 percent in the case of resistant varieties, but 37 to 50 percent with susceptible varieties. The infestations in all the varieties increased with the reduction of insecticidal sprayings (Figs. 9b and 9c). Infestations never reached as high a level in resistant varieties as in susceptible ones. It should be noted that the total infested tillers in resistant varieties without any insecticidal treatment was lower than the infestation in susceptible varieties even when protected with the insecticide.

Both resistant varieties yielded about twice as much as the susceptible varieties (Fig. 9d). The yield of Chianan 2, when treated with insecticides, was higher than

Taitung 16, but, without insecticidal treatments, Taitung 16 yielded better than Chianan 2, indicating that Chianan 2 is more susceptible. In earlier stages of growth,

Fig. 9. Yield, and percentages of infested tillers, dead hearts, and white heads, of the resistant varieties Chianan-2 (C) and Taitung 16 (T) and of the more susceptible Rexoro (R) and Sapan Kwai (S), when unprotected or protected with an insecticide during the indicated periods of growth.

Chianan 2 had a lower insect infestation, but as the crop grew older, Chianan 2 became somewhat more susceptible and developed a significantly larger number of white heads than Taitung 16. These indications of changes in susceptibility with age generally agree with the laboratory findings reported above.

The development of stem borer populations on the susceptible varieties was several times higher than on the resistant varieties (Fig. 10), indicating that cultivation of resistant varieties might eventually bring about a reduction in insect populations.

There evidently are real differences among varieties in natural resistance to stem borer infestation, and such resistance may contribute importantly to yield. It also is interesting that the persistent spraying with endrin resulted in relatively small gains in yield in this test.

Fig. 10. Differences in populations of various species of stem borer on two resistant and two susceptible varieties in the field.

CHEMICAL CONTROL OF STEM BORERS AND OTHER RICE PESTS

Generally, an insect population in a particular area undergoes a dormant stage or diapause sometime during the year. Thus, at the end of diapause, the insects start their development from one particular stage and appear in definite broods throughout the period of their activity. The factors mainly responsible for this dormant stage are adverse climate and non-availability of food plants.

In those parts of the tropics where fluctuations in temperature are slight and rice is grown all year, the stem borer population remains fairly high throughout the year. This, combined with short durations of larval stay outside of the plants and the frequent rains reducing insecticidal residues, often results in poor stem borer control even with frequent sprayings. The Institute program of insecticidal studies is

oriented towards obtaining satisfactory control with a minimum number of treatments.

Laboratory Screening of Insecticides

The stem borer larvae remain on plant surfaces only for short periods during their entire active feeding stages. It is essential, therefore, that the insecticides used possess a strong larvicidal action by direct contact as well as contact by residual films. Since the eggs are most liable to come in direct contact with insecticides, an insecticide with ovicidal effects will be more efficient in borer control. A large number of compounds are being tested for ovicidal and larvicidal efficiencies.

In an experiment, 24 insecticides were tested in the laboratory on egg masses at the whitish stage and blackhead stage and

Table 4. Effectiveness of insecticides when sprayed on egg masses and freshly-hatched larvae of rice stem borer, *Chilo suppressalis* W., IIRRI, 1963.

Treatment	eggs killed (%)		Larvae killed (%)	
	Whitish mass	"Blackhead" mass	After 24 hours	After 48 hours
.04% Folidol M50	100	100	96.0	0
.04% α -BHC	100	100	54.8	8.0
.03% Diazinon 20E	100	100	89.2	1.2
.06% Imidan	100	100	93.2	0
.04% Zectran	100	90.5	37.2	4.0
.04% Sumithion	100	99.1	90.4	2.4
.15% Lebaycid	100	85.8	38.8	2.4
.04% Folithion	100	98.5	98.4	0
.06% Roxion	100	56.0	10.4	4.0
.04% Mepaton	82.9	76.8	98.4	0
.04% Gusathion	69.2	51.6	93.2	2.4
.02% Thimet	63.5	28.5	26.8	2.8
.10% Ekatin	63.0	59.6	12.0	6.4
.03% Endrin	47.2	91.7	98.4	1.2
.06% Perfekthion	35.4	76.0	41.2	5.2
.05% Trithion	32.9	64.7	2.4	0
.06% EPN-300	28.9	53.9	100	—
.10% Metasystox	26.4	73.8	16.0	2.4
.10% Tedion	26.0	21.0	8.0	0
.07% Maladrin	4.6	88.4	40.0	5.2
.03% E.I-43064*			16.0	1.2
.10% Sevin*			48.0	0
.05% Thiodan*			40.0	5.2
.04% Meptox 50*			100	—
Control	10.3	11.6	1.2	1.2

* Tests made with larvae only.

on freshly hatched larvae. Eggs at the whitish stage are those in which the embryos are still developing, while at the blackhead stage, the larvae are ready to hatch.

Each of three replications consisted of four egg masses or 25 freshly hatched larvae in a petri dish. The desired quantity and concentration of the insecticide was sprayed directly on the test insects from a Potter's Spray Tower at a pressure of 10 lbs./sq. in.

Many compounds were effective as ovicides as well as larvicides (Table 4). However, several others tested were effective only on one stage of the insect.

Field Screening of Insecticides

During the dry and wet seasons, 1963, several insecticides were tested for their efficacy in controlling stem borers and other insects in the rice fields (Fig. 11).

These insecticides were applied as foliar sprays at the rate of 400 to 500 gallons per hectare by using knapsack sprayers. The sprayings were started 2 weeks after transplanting and were repeated every tenth day until crop maturity. The treatments were replicated four times. During the wet season, 1963, each insecticide was sprayed in four additional replications with a 0.2% tenac solution (methyl cellulose), a sticker. This was to determine whether stickers prevent the insecticides from being washed off the plants during rains.

It is evident from the data in Tables 5, 6 and 7 that the plots treated with the most effective insecticides yielded 87 to 102 percent more than the control plots. In Table 5, the infestations in all treatments, except with imidan, were 29 percent or higher, indicating that, in spite of repeated insecticidal treatments, the infestations build up within the plants. This is

Fig. 11. Field trials of insecticides against insect pests of rice.

mainly caused by the lower residual effects of insecticides and overlapping broods in insect population. There were significant differences in percentages of dead hearts, white heads, and infested tillers and in total yield in plots treated with different compounds. Imidan, endrin, and lebaycid gave best results in this test. One of the significant points was the almost equal efficiency of imidan and endrin during the earlier stages but the far greater efficiency of imidan in controlling the insect population beyond the booting stage.

Gusathion, telodrin, endrin, folidol,

and lebaycid significantly increased the yield and lowered infestations when used with stickers (Table 7). The sticker improved the efficiency of several insecticides, but resulted in lower yields and higher infestations with imidan and diazinon and to a lesser extent, with EPN and folithion. When used without stickers, the imidan, endrin, and EPN treated plots produced the highest yields (Table 6). The plots treated with imidan had the lowest infestations; this indicates constancy in its performance during the dry season. Stickers are inert materials and should not interfere

Table 5. Efficiency of various insecticides for rice stem borer control when sprayed on Milfor 6 at 10-day intervals, IRRI, January-May, 1963; plots 2.7 x 5 meters, four replications.

Treatment	2 months after transplanting			At harvest time			Yield (kg./ha.)
	Dead hearts (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average number tillers/hill	White heads (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Ave. number productive panicles/hill	
.04% Endrin	2.1	4.6	18.6	2.5	29.6	17.3	6,555
.04% Folidol	7.8	9.1	19.4	6.6	59.2	15.6	6,222
.09% Imidan	2.3	3.8	18.3	0.8	9.5	18.2	7,650
.05% Lebaycid	3.6	6.4	17.9	6.8	65.9	16.3	6,560
.09% Sevin	5.1	8.2	21.2	8.1	74.1	15.1	6,453
.05% Thimet	8.8	12.6	17.8	9.7	66.8	16.1	5,328
.09% Zectran	14.4	17.9	19.5	12.2	75.0	13.5	5,262
Control	12.1	21.5	21.3	17.0	65.0	12.7	4,082
LSD	6.3	9.0	—	4.9	13.0	—	968

Table 6. Effect of various materials for rice stem borer control when sprayed on Milfor 6 at 10-day intervals, IRRI, June-October, 1963; plots 2.7 x 5 meters, four replications.

Treatment	45 days after transplanting			85 days after transplanting				Yield (kg./ha.)
	Dead hearts (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average tillers per hill	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average number productive panicles/per hill	
.09% Imidan	1.3	1.6	10.1	1.8	5.6	17.8	11.1	3,555
.04% Endrin	0.8	4.6	11.2	0.9	5.2	29.5	11.6	3,575
.04% Folidol	1.7	3.4	11.0	2.5	9.9	33.5	10.5	2,820
.05% Lebaycid	1.4	2.8	11.0	4.8	10.5	38.2	9.4	3,020
.09% Sevin	1.1	2.1	10.4	5.1	12.0	35.4	9.9	2,340
.05% EPN	1.5	6.2	11.2	3.5	8.0	28.4	10.6	3,455
.04% Mepaton	2.5	3.4	12.4	4.4	8.5	32.3	11.3	2,790
.04% Sumithion	2.2	2.8	9.8	3.7	9.8	30.6	10.0	2,400
.04% Diazinon	1.2	6.5	11.7	3.6	7.1	24.2	12.2	2,855
.04% Folithion	1.5	4.7	11.7	3.4	7.6	28.4	10.8	3,010
.04% Meptox	1.2	5.5	10.0	3.8	7.2	23.3	10.5	2,825
.04% Hexalin	2.6	8.2	11.4	4.9	8.6	44.5	10.3	2,545
.04% Gusathion	0.6	4.6	10.3	2.7	9.4	26.8	10.8	2,870
.02% Telodrin	0.3	1.0	9.2	1.8	4.4	23.6	10.9	3,310
Control	3.1	5.5	11.6	10.6	10.6	35.6	10.2	1,805
LSD	1.4	—	—	2.6	3.6	—	—	791.6

with insecticidal properties. Further experiments will be designed to determine the causes of this apparent antagonism.

Two important considerations became evident from these tests:

(a) None of the insecticides applied as foliar applications were capable of killing

the insect population within the plants.

(b) There was some period of no residual effect during the interval between sprayings which permitted infestations to build up in plots treated with each of the insecticides tested.

These considerations suggest intensive

Table 7. Effect on rice stem borer control of spraying at 10-day intervals with different insecticides in .02% tenac solution, IRRI June-October, 1963.

Treatment	45 days after transplanting			85 days after transplanting				Yield (kg./ha.)
	Dead hearts (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average number of tillers per hill	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average number productive panicles/hill	
.09% Imidan	1.1	3.1	13.0	5.4	10.6	35.9	11.2	3,280
.04% Endrin	0.5	2.3	12.1	2.4	3.3	18.3	12.2	4,145
.04% Folidol	1.2	5.8	13.0	4.9	3.2	14.8	12.4	3,575
.05% Lebaycid	1.6	1.7	11.4	3.9	6.4	26.7	11.1	3,380
.09% Sevin	1.8	6.5	11.6	6.0	8.3	31.7	9.9	2,885
.05% EPN	1.8	4.0	11.7	4.3	6.5	16.1	11.9	3,280
.04% Mepaton	1.6	6.2	12.6	6.3	5.4	24.8	12.4	3,100
.04% Sumithion	1.3	4.1	12.4	3.3	4.4	18.7	12.4	3,505
.04% Diazinon	1.7	2.8	11.7	7.5	7.4	38.5	10.2	2,640
.04% Folithion	1.1	6.8	10.9	11.1	6.6	19.2	11.2	2,795
.04% Meptox	1.6	3.9	10.2	5.2	5.8	26.0	13.2	3,200
.04% Hexalin	0.9	3.3	11.2	8.7	5.8	41.1	11.4	2,715
.04% Gusathion	1.2	3.1	12.8	6.1	6.9	22.4	11.6	3,530
.02% Telodrin	0.5	3.5	11.7	3.8	3.0	22.9	11.4	3,460
Control	3.1	8.4	11.6	10.7	9.4	25.2	10.9	2,045
LSD	—	—	—	4.13	2.91	14.3	—	617.9

spraying schedules which farmers no doubt would find impractical. Hence another project was established to determine whether the number of sprayings may be reduced without sacrificing yields.

Timing of Insecticidal Applications

As the rice stem borer population does not seem to have pronounced broods, the applications of insecticides cannot be timed to meet the peak of moth emergence or hatching of the larvae from the egg masses. However, applications might be timed to protect rice plants at certain more vulnerable stages of growth, should these exist. To obtain this information, an experiment was designed in which the crop was not sprayed for 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11 weeks, respectively, after transplanting but, after the spraying were initiated, they were repeated every tenth day till maturity of the crop. The variety (Milfor 6) and general layout of the experiment were the same as for the screening of insecticides.

In a test conducted during the 1963 dry season, 0.04 percent folidol sprays at 14-day intervals were used as insecticidal treatments (Table 8). The general trend of infestations in various treatments indicated that the 14-day interval probably was too long for residual effects of folidol. There were, however, significant differences in the percentages of white heads and dead

hearts and in yields with various treatments. The yields obtained did not differ significantly among treatments started up to 9 weeks after transplanting. With no protection beyond this period, there was a sharp fall in yield.

Similar results were obtained in the wet season (Table 9). There were no significant differences in yields among treatments until 7 weeks after transplanting, then yields declined sharply if the crop was not protected. In this experiment, 0.04 percent endrin spray was used as the insecticidal treatment, and the sprayings were repeated at 10-day intervals.

These preliminary results suggest that insecticidal treatments may be initiated between 5 to 7 weeks after transplanting without much loss in rice yields. This would bring about a reduction of at least three sprayings from the total required if treatments are started 1 or 2 weeks after transplanting. Considering 7 weeks as an appropriate first spraying, future experiments will test whether the number of later treatments can be reduced.

Systemic Insecticides

It is evident from the above results that foliar applications of insecticides could not kill the insects within the plants and had short residual periods, making several treatments essential for satisfactory control.

Table 8. Effect on rice stem borer control of timings of .04% folidol spraying, IRRI, January-May, 1963.

Time spraying started after transplanting:	2 months after transplanting			At harvest time			Yield (kg./ha.)
	Dead hearts (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average number tillers/hill	White heads (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average number productive panicles/hill	
1 week	8.4	9.4	15.7	2.7	50.3	14.4	5,471
3 weeks	7.8	9.7	15.6	3.8	56.2	14.1	5,173
5 weeks	15.9	19.3	14.4	7.4	58.8	13.8	5,522
7 weeks	9.7	10.7	16.4	3.5	54.6	15.3	5,651
9 weeks	14.5	19.7	15.4	4.8	51.5	15.5	5,470
11 weeks	15.1	19.6	14.3	5.8	53.6	13.6	4,708
13 weeks	16.9	19.5	15.5	7.5	46.4	15.1	4,351
Control	11.8	16.5	15.0	7.3	51.9	14.0	3,926
LSD	2.1	6.7	—	2.8	—	—	943

Table 9. Effect on rice stem borer control of timings of .04% endrin sprays, IIRI, June-October, 1963.¹

Time spraying started after transplanting:	45 days after transplanting			85 days after transplanting				Yield (kg./ha.)
	Dead hearts (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average number tillers/hill	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Ave. number productive panicles/hill	
1 week	0.8	3.5	10.7	0.7	4.0	15.6	13.4	4,080
3 weeks	1.1	3.3	10.4	0.9	5.9	23.9	12.7	3,465
5 weeks	2.1	2.3	10.2	1.0	1.0	3.0	12.6	4,135
7 weeks	1.3	4.6	9.7	0.8	2.6	6.2	12.8	3,980
9 weeks	1.8	4.3	11.1	4.9	7.6	17.7	12.4	2,760
11 weeks	1.5	2.4	9.8	6.2	7.7	23.4	13.2	2,765
13 weeks	1.8	3.3	11.4	4.8	7.9	24.4	12.1	2,485
Control	1.5	5.1	11.0	7.4	7.1	26.7	11.2	2,770
LSD	—	—	—	3.2	3.7	11.6	—	477

¹ The sprayings were repeated at 10-day intervals, and each figure represents an average of four replications.

The use of systemic insecticides often will kill all or most of the insects infesting the plants and protect them from future infestations throughout their effective residual periods.

During the year, several compounds were tested for their systemic actions when used as seed treatment, when placed in the furrows at the time of seeding, when sprayed on the seedlings, and when mixed with irrigation water in transplanted crops. The dosages used were the maximum amounts the plants could tolerate without showing pronounced phytotoxic effects.

In tests during the dry season, thimet and γ -BHC (hexalin), when used either as

seed treatment or in the furrows before seeding, protected the seedlings from infestations of stem borers, stem maggots, mole crickets, and other insects for a period of about 20 days after treatment (Fig. 12). Some residual effects seemed to remain for a longer period, and the treated seedlings appeared healthier than untreated ones. The same compounds were not effective when used as foliar sprays. Many other compounds were not effective.

When applied with irrigation water, both compounds excellently controlled rice stem borers on 2-month-old crops (Table 10). The treated plots had no stem borer population even 3 weeks after treatment, while

Fig. 12. Protection of rice seedlings from different insects by the use of systemic insecticides. Some of the plots were heavily damaged by rice shoot fly, stem borers, and mole crickets.

Table 10. Effect on rice stem borer control of single applications of three systemic insecticides, IRRI, January-May, 1963.¹

Treatment	3 weeks after application			At harvest time			Yield (kg./ha.)
	Dead hearts (%)	Average number tillers/hill	Average number larvae/5 hills	White heads (%)	Infested tillers (%)	Average number productive panicles/hill	
Thimet	0	19.2	0	2.5	64.1	13.2	6,563
Hexalin	0	16.7	0	1.6	32.3	13.7	5,887
Metasystox	0	15.4	0	5.6	70.4	14.4	5,721
Control	13.5	16.8	9.25	9.6	66.2	12.8	4,171
LSD	—	—	—	2.7	18.0	—	691

¹The insecticides were mixed with irrigation water at the rate of 8 kg. active material per hectare 2 months after transplanting.

in control plots the larvae averaged 9.25 per five hills. A single application of thimet at this stage gave as high a yield as 10 sprayings with several promising compounds (Table 5). At harvest time, 2 months after treatment, the plots treated with hexalin had lower stem borer infestations but yielded less than those treated with thimet. The possible factors for this

are being investigated. All these compounds, however, failed to bring about any significant reduction in stem borer populations when applied under identical conditions on a crop at the heading stage. Further studies are underway to determine whether these compounds can also be effectively used to protect crops in the booting stage.

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN STEM BORER INFESTATIONS AND YIELD

Dead hearts and white heads are the only symptoms which become apparent in rice stem borer infested plants. These do not represent total infestations in a field, however, and it is desirable to learn whether correlations exist between these and total infestation and yields.

The interrelationships between percentages of dead hearts, infested tillers, infested hills, number of insects per hill, and white heads were studied using data obtained during the year. In many experiments, these were significantly correlated with each other, but the correlation seemed to vary with the experimental conditions and with the number of varieties involved. Observations made on several hundred varieties did not reveal any correlation between dead hearts and white heads. This also was true in observations made on a single variety.

Highly significant correlations were found, however, between white heads and

yield in Milfor 6 in a series of experiments carried out during the dry and wet seasons. The slopes of the lines representing the correlation in all these tests were similar, indicating more or less a definite relationship between white head and yield even under different experimental conditions. These correlations indicate that for each percentage of increase in white heads there was a 2.29 to 3.85 percent loss in the crop yield. This information may help in surveying losses, particularly, in the absence of any other standard procedure for such estimations.

Experiments conducted with four other varieties, two resistant, Chianan 2 and Taitung 16, and two susceptible, Sapan Kwai and Rexoro, did not reveal any correlation between white head and yield. Therefore, it may be necessary to determine correlation values for each variety separately.

BOGGING AND REARING limit use of standard wheel tractors in wet soils.

Agricultural Engineering

Agricultural engineering research activities are primarily concerned with (a) machinery for wet land rice production, (b)

irrigation losses and use, and (c) analysis of plant growth curves, especially on plant reaction to physical conditions.

MACHINERY FOR WET LAND RICE PRODUCTION

Machinery is used in rice production primarily to prepare land, to plant, and to thresh. These activities all require equipment that will move in wet fields. The threshing operation is the least mobile in that the thresher is stationary when operating. Land preparation requires mobility and a large amount of power, but less precision than planting which requires little power.

At present, manpower is sufficient for planting and is difficult to equal for precision placement of seed on a mud surface. Agronomic studies on quantities and placement of pre-germinated seed are needed to permit the design of appropriate planting equipment.

Combines and Threshers

In 1961 and 1962, commercially available threshers and combines of possible use for harvesting rice were reviewed. An International Harvester D8-62 combine, made in Germany, was purchased and used in field operations.

The unit has not been successful in harvesting tall, leafy tropical rice, which usually has a high moisture content (25-29 percent), because (a) the forward speed is too high, making the feed rate excessive, (b) the cutter platform cannot be raised high enough and too much straw enters the combine, and (c) when the straw is wet, the rasp bar cylinder causes excessive hulling and cracking of the grain at all cylinder

Fig. 1. Rear view of cone-type thresher fabricated at the Institute.

speeds and concave settings. Furthermore, excessive grain is carried out with the straw.

The combine has performed well with lower yielding (1,000-3,000 kg./ha.) crops of low moisture content (18-23 percent).

Discussions with farm machinery dealers, rice growers, and agricultural workers indicate the need for a simple low-cost high-capacity contractor type of thresher. Information was obtained on a cone-type thresher patented by W. F. Buchele while he was at Michigan State University, and a model was designed and fabricated in the Institute shops (Figs. 1 and 2).

Tests with rice show that the principle of the cone-type thresher is sound. It has a minimum of moving parts and threshes gently without cracking or hulling the grain. The maximum output obtained to

Fig. 2. Side view of cone-type thresher fabricated at the Institute.

date is approximately 300 kg./hr. of rough rice with a 6 h.p. engine. Several changes will be incorporated in a future model to allow a higher feed rate, to improve separation, to reduce choking, and to simplify the construction so that the thresher may be mounted on, and powered by, a tractor.

Soil Measurements

The utility of power tillers and tractors is largely limited by their bogging down in soft flooded soils, by balling of mud in sticky plastic soils, and by their inability to pulverize hard, dry soils. Field measurements of soil characteristics are needed to facilitate the exchange of information among scientists, machinery design and sales workers, and farmers.

During 1963, the Institute determined the Atterberg limits, the cone index, and the shear vane index of each of a number of rice soils. Engineers have widely used the Atterberg limits as a simple field measurement of clay characteristics. Gill and Reeves of the USDA Tillage Laboratory found high correlations between the Atterberg limits and other physical properties of clays. Large areas of the Institute farm are highly plastic clays with upper plastic limits of 70-90 and lower limits of 30-40, with a plastic index of 30-50. Upland areas, formerly in coconut or sugar cane, are non-plastic or have a low plastic index of 16-30.

The non-plastic soils are easy to plow when dry and may be cultivated 3 to 5 days after a rain. The highly plastic soils must be plowed either when extremely dry (at the end of the dry season) or when flooded. These soils are tough and sticky at intermediate moisture conditions so that upland plowing or cultivation ranges from difficult to impossible.

As time permits and samples are available, Atterberg limits will be determined for the rice soils of Asia. Soils from Darwin, Australia, have been found to have plastic limits of 24-32, liquid limits of 62-75, and

plastic indexes of 38-43. Soils from the Kouk Trap Experiment Station in Cambodia were non-plastic.

The U. S. Army Waterways Experiment Station, Vicksburg, Miss., has developed and used a 30-degree one-half square inch cone penetrometer to measure soils and to predict vehicle performance. A modified hydraulic cone penetrometer, fabricated in the Institute shops from readily available materials, has a 1½-inch diameter which is well suited for soft soils.

The cone is pushed into the soil (Fig. 3) and the pressure in psi indicates the soil resistance. The resistance at a depth equal to one-third the wheel diameter is of greatest importance. The cone index values and Atterberg limits for the Institute fields are shown in Table 1.

Previous reports indicate that the cone size is not critical if the soil resistance is measured in psi. Next year a comparison will be made of the standard one-half square inch cone and the 1½-inch diameter cone used in these tests.

Fig. 3. Field measurement of soil characteristics with the cone penetrometer. Note the shear vane awaiting test.

Table 1. Physical properties of soil on the Institute farm.

Property	Range
<i>Atterberg Limits</i>	
Liquid Limit	42 to 89
Plastic Limit	30 to 43
Plastic Index	non-plastic to 52
<i>Resistance to cone penetrometer, wet season</i>	
at 9 inch depth	7 to 50 psi
at 12 inch depth	10 to 64 "
at 15 inch depth	16 to 100 "
<i>Resistance to cone penetrometer, dry season</i>	
at 9 inch depth	18 to 1000+ psi
at 12 inch depth	30 to 1000+ "
at 15 inch depth	64 to 1000+ "

A simple durable shear vane also was made in the Institute shops (Fig. 3). The vane width and depth are such that a torque wrench reading of 1 foot-pound is equivalent to 0.1 psi. A 0-50 foot-pound torque wrench is used to cover the 0-5.0 psi shear strength encountered in wet clay soils.

The vane is pushed into the soil to the mid-point of a 6-inch increment and twisted with a wrench. The torque reading is observed at failure and as the core is slowly turned. Most of the undisturbed flooded soils at the Institute fall in the 1.5-3.5 psi range of shear indexes. Tractors usually bog down or spin when the shear vane reading under the wheel is less than 2.0 psi. Shear vane values exceeding 3.0 psi in the wheel track indicate a fairly firm soil.

Plans of the shear vane and cone penetrometer and instructions for their use are available.

Dry Land Preparation

Plowing, harrowing, and rotovating of hard soil at the end of the dry season are difficult or impossible with animal-drawn equipment because of the high power requirements. Power tillers are better than animals in preparing hard, dry soil, but

equipment breakage may be excessive. Standard tractors perform well on dry soil as the additional traction largely offsets the higher draft of the plow or disc. The major advantage of dry land preparation is that the land may be planted as soon as the first rains occur. This permits a longer cropping season. Major disadvantages are the high power requirements and the difficulty in controlling initial weed growth.

Wet Land Preparation

Plowing, harrowing, rotovating, and leveling of flooded rice soils is standard practice where water is available and power is limited. The flooded soil is soft and lubricated so that the draft of the carabao is sufficient. Standard tractors are least effective on flooded soils as the rubber tires spin. Performance is improved somewhat by the use of (a) a rotovator which tends to push the tractor, and (b) cage wheels which give flotation and traction (Fig. 4). Standard tractors with cage wheels work well on firm soils with a cone index above 40 psi at a 12-inch depth; but, at a cone index below 30 psi at 15

Fig. 4. A 36-horsepower tractor with special lug wheels rotavating on firm soil.

inches, the tractor's front end rises and the rotovator is buried in the ground, causing bogging.

Two tractors were connected with the front wheels removed to form a tandem unit (Fig. 5). Tandem tractors have four-wheel drive, power steering, a center pivoting action, and weight balance to prevent elevation of the front end. Other workers have used the tandem trac-

Fig. 5. Two 36-horsepower tractors in tandem pulling a 4-meter wide disc harrow.

Fig. 6. A 4 hp. Japanese power tiller with wheels for paddy soils.

Fig. 7. An 8.5 hp. Japanese power tiller with wheels for paddy soils.

tor for plowing drylands with approximately a 30 percent increase in efficiency. In soft, flooded soils, the tandem unit seems particularly promising as it performs well under conditions in which a single tractor will not work. Commercial

models are needed.

Japanese power tillers in the 4-8.5 h.p. range have been used for the 1963 farm operations. These tillers have special wheels for flooded rice soils (Figs. 6 and 7). With a cone index above 30 psi at

Table 2. Partial results of field tests of tractors and power tillers, IRRI, 1963.

Characteristic	Iseki KT-400 4.0 HP	Iseki KF-850 8.5 HP	I-H D-436 w/ standard cage wheels 36 HP	Two units I-H D-436 w/ cage whls. in tandem 72 HP
Surface water depth, inches	2 to 3	2	6	4
Vegetation	Plowed	Rice stubble	Heavy weeds	Heavy weeds
Average cone index, psi	32.4	33.3	36.5	42.3
Cone index when bogged, psi	—	26 to 31	—	—
Average shear vane index, psi	1.9	1.9	3.2	3.0
Shear vane index when bogged, psi	—	1.9	—	—
Average wheel sinkage, inches	5.4	8.5	8.6	10.2
Whl. sinkage when bogged, inches	—	11.5	—	—
Whl. diameter & width, inches	15 x 30	32 x 8	54 x 13 48 x 16	54 x 13 48 x 16
Total weight of operator, tractor and implement, kg.	128	347.6	2248	4712
Projected ground pressure, psi	0.55	3.08	4.6	4.5
Implement used	Comb harrow	Rotary tiller	Rotary tiller	Disc harrow
Width & depth of operation, cm.	122 x 15	60 x 16	165 x 15	390 x 15
Traction of tractor w/ implement raised, kg.	—	—	377	960
Total draft of implement, kg.	—	—	(-121)	532
Rolling resistance of tractor w/ implement raised, kg.	—	—	560	950
Rate of work, sq.m./hp-hr	569	72	96	181

9 inches, the tillers work well, but if the cone index is below 20 psi at 9 inches, bogging may occur.

Rate of land preparation depends on the soil condition, fineness of cut, vegetation, and power available. Timed tests at the Institute indicate that a carabao may be expected to plow from 100 to 200 square meters per hour. Power tillers and tractors plow from 20 to 180 square meters per hour per rated horsepower. It appears that one engine horsepower should permit preparation of 100 to 150 square meters of flooded rice land per hour of work. If less than 70 to 100 square meters per hour are prepared, the equipment is performing poorly.

Wheel size, shape, and construction are important considerations. In numerous tests of equipment at the Institute, the wheel type, implement, soil, vegetation, power, weight, and other notes were recorded. Partial results are in Table 2.

Tractors having wheels with low ground pressures work better in soft soils than those with higher pressures. Data on the ground pressure of the projected wheel area indicate that small tillers with large wheels (Fig. 6) have ground pressures of

Fig. 8. Track-type tractor with 3'x16"x24' board for land leveling.

0.5 to 0.7 psi. Tractors with cage wheels (Figs. 4 and 5), larger tillers (Fig. 7) and wide-track type tractors (Fig. 8) have ground pressures of from 3 to 4.5 psi. Standard tractors on rubber tires alone have ground pressures of 10 psi or more.

Draft of Carabao

Measurements of maximum pull were made on 20 carabaos to determine a design load which would prevent breakage of animal-drawn tools. The maximum pull

Table 3. Speed developed on grass sod when 13 carabaos pulled sleds with horizontal draft approximately one-fifth, one-eighth, and one-tenth of the weight of the test animal; IRRI, May-June, 1963.

Age (yrs.)	Carabao		One-fifth Body Weight		One-eighth Body Weight		One-tenth Body Weight	
	Body weight (kg.)	Draft (kg.)	Speed (kph)	Draft (kg.)	Speed (kph)	Draft (kg.)	Speed (kph)	
6.5	532	106	4.26	62	4.04	49.8	4.12	
8.5	561	106	5.05	66	4.54	52.6	4.39	
12.0	455	84	3.38	53	4.22	42.3	4.76	
3.0	360	67	4.39	42	4.04	33.8	3.75	
4.0	467	87	3.57	54	4.22	43.3	4.18	
3.0	329	62	4.30	38	4.22	30.1	4.01	
5.0	400	75	3.86	47	4.01	37.6	4.07	
8.0	431	81	3.67	51	3.78	40.4	3.49	
7.0	517	—	—	61	3.60	47.0	3.12	
5.0	395	—	—	46	3.19	40.4	3.09	
7.0	416	66	3.60	—	—	38.5	3.60	
5.0	461	72	2.74	54	2.85	43.3	2.90	
8.0	543	84	3.35	—	—	51.7	3.46	

recorded was 410 kg., and six sets of harness were broken in the tests. The harness broke at 140 to 330 kg. pull. Most of the carabaos would stop when the pull exceeded 120 to 180 kg., but if disturbed, the animals would exert more force. A design value of 500 kg. should protect most carabao-drawn implements against breakage.

In a second test, the pulling capacity of 13 carabaos was tested on grass sod, by

measuring the speed at which each animal could draw a sled with horizontal draft approximately one-fifth, one-eighth, and one-tenth of its body weight. The horizontal draft corrected for angle of pull and the speed developed in each test are in Table 3.

The average horizontal pull was 54.7 kg., and the average speed was 3.75 km./hr. The average horsepower developed was 0.75, with a range of 0.4 to 1.2.

IRRIGATION WATER LOSSES AND USE

Irrigation water is a major factor controlling land preparation, weed control, plant growth, and yield. Any improvement in water management requires information on the amount actually used and the amount wasted or lost. The total water requirement for rice presently used by irrigation design engineers is 1 liter per second/ha., or 8.64 mm./day. Requirements of 6 to 16 mm. total water per day are reported in the literature; the average is about 8.8 mm./day.

To determine the amount of water lost through evaporation and evapotranspiration, tanks were constructed (Fig. 9). Weekly solar radiation in thousands of gram-calories/cm² (kg.-cal./cm.²) and

weekly evapotranspiration in cm. were found to be closely related (Fig. 10). After computing the theoretical limits, it was concluded that most of the solar radiation measured actually was utilized in the evapotranspiration observed. The evapotranspiration ranged from 3.38 to 7.42 cm. of water per week, or 4.8 to 10.6 mm./day, during the period February 18-June 14. Maximum evapotranspiration occurred at heading time and under conditions of maximum solar radiation during the dry season.

During the rainy season when solar radiation was less, a second experiment was conducted with 16-meter diameter plots planted to rice and with seepage reduced to a minimum by metal levees.

Fig. 9. Sectioned views of evaporation and evapotranspiration tanks.

Fig. 10. Relation of weekly evapotranspiration to solar radiation, IRRI, February 18—June 14, 1963.

The average daily evapotranspiration measured was 5.02 mm./day, with a range of 1.93 to 7.82 mm./day.

Water losses caused by seepage and percolation were measured during 1963 on three 16-meter diameter plots each with 200 square meters area and 50 linear meters of levee. The deep percolation averaged 0.5 mm./day. The seepage through the levee varied greatly with the

levee material and depth of water. A metal levee extending 15 cm. into the soil permitted seepage of only 0.17 liter per hour per linear meter when the water was 5 to 8 cm. deep. An earth levee permitted seepage of 10.9 liters per hour per linear meter. Experiments on the effect of levee construction on seepage are being continued, but present data indicate that metal levees effectively conserve water.

Irrigation projects will require extensive land leveling when plot sizes are increased for mechanized agriculture. Figure 11 shows a pole attached to a tractor for wet leveling. The fluid mud is moved as a wave and allowed to settle out in the deeper water. The tractor moves in reverse to carry more material and leave a finished level condition.

Fig. 11. Track-type tractor with 10-meter pole for land leveling.

DEVELOPMENT OF PLANT GROWTH CURVES

It seems desirable to obtain precise data on response of rice plants to physical phenomena, thus allowing development of accurate growth curves and the mathematical equations describing them. By developing response curves under a variety of conditions, it might be possible to predict performance, mathematically, for any

given combination of a set of variables. It is known that yield depends upon an interaction of such variables as variety, spacing, fertility level, and climatic factors.

As an initial approach to the problem, a spacing experiment was used in which the variety, soil fertility level, and climate were held constant.

The experiment was planted September 13, 1962, using the variety Milbuen 5(3). A template was used which permitted seed to be dropped through holes in a definite pattern as indicated in Fig. 12. Each of 9 replicates measured 6 x 6 meters and provided 29 spacing distances with 100 plants per spacing. The square shape

was used to minimize effects of soil variability within replicates.

The relationship of grain yield to unit area per plant for this variety and this particular set of conditions is in Fig. 13. Curves for four other characteristics are in Fig. 14.

Fig. 12. Planting plan for an experiment involving 29 spacings with 100 plants per spacing in a 6x6 meter plot.

Fig. 13. Relationship of grain yield in kg./ha. (Y_3) for Milbuen 5(3) to unit area per plant (x^2) under upland conditions, IIRRI, September, 1962 — January, 1963.

Fig. 14. Effect of varying unit area per plant (x^2) on characteristics of Milbuen 5(3), under upland conditions, IIRRI, September, 1962 — January, 1963. Lower left, plant height (Y_4); upper right, bearing panicles per plant (Y_6); middle right, grain weight per plant (Y_{8u}); lower right, grain weight per panicle (Y_9).

MEASUREMENT OF STRAW STRENGTH

A technique for measuring strength of straw was tested (Fig. 15). The panicle and flag leaf are removed, and a chain of known weight per link is attached to the upper end of the culm to measure the critical straw strength (P). Inner diameter (d_i) and outer diameter (d_o) of the culm are measured at a point 1 cm. above the first elongated internode; this can be done easily with the device shown in Fig. 16. The length of culm (L) can be measured with a pocket rule. The ratio of the critical straw strength (P) to the modulus of elasticity (E) is:

$$\frac{P}{E} = \frac{0.121(d_o^4 - d_i^4)}{L^2}$$

Fig. 15. A technique for measuring straw strength. The ratio of critical straw strength (P) to modulus of elasticity (E) appears to be negatively correlated with lodging susceptibility.

Table 4. Percentage lodged plants, inside and outside basal culm diameters, plant height and P/E ratio¹, for Peta grown under lowland conditions with various distances between rows, March 2-July 30, 1963.

Distance between rows (cm.)	Percentage lodged	Number of bearing tillers per M ²	Average stem diameter		Plant height L (cm.)	$\frac{P}{E}$ mm ² x 10 ⁻⁵
			Inside d_i (mm.)	Outside d_o (mm.)		
5	97	239	3.47	5.08	122	4.24
10	96	222	3.77	5.48	123	5.58
20	96	175	3.84	5.50	123	5.63
30	95	151	4.11	5.90	125	7.23
40	92	150	4.16	6.08	129	7.77
50	89	128	4.46	6.38	134	8.41
60	87	123	4.56	6.50	137	8.66
70	80	108	4.64	6.54	135	9.03
80	67	112	4.68	6.47	138	8.41
90	58	100	4.80	6.71	137	9.65
100	46	85	4.67	6.53	137	8.66
110	36	88	4.74	6.59	136	9.08
122.5	28	77	4.62	6.47	137	8.39
140	26	72	4.64	6.50	135	8.76
150	22	66	4.57	6.42	138	8.07

¹ $P/E = 0.121 (d_o^4 - d_i^4)$

L^2

The relationship of the ratio P/E to percentage of non-lodged plants of Peta at row spacings of 5-150 cm. during the 1963 wet season is illustrated in Fig. 16. In this particular test, P/E values were obtained by measuring only d_o, d_i , and L; to obtain the value for E, the critical straw strength would be determined. It appeared that P/E values lower than 8 were associated with severe lodging (Fig. 16 and Table 4).

Fig. 17. Relationship between the ratio critical straw strength (P)/ modulus of elasticity (E) to percentage non-lodged plants of Peta, March 2-July 30, 1963 when only inside and outside culm diameters and plant height were measured. Plants with a critical straw strength (P) of 21.21 grams* did not lodge.

★ ★ ★

For Inside Diameter:

For Outside Diameter:

Fig. 16. Device for measuring rice stem diameters.

BLAST SYMPOSIUM PARTICIPANTS from Thailand, Japan, and Indonesia inspect the long-term rotation study on the Experimental Farm.

Experimental Farm

The 80-hectare experimental station was maintained in a satisfactory condition throughout the year. Weeds on the levees and sides of the water reservoirs were controlled by regular sprays with PCP. Weeds on some levees were controlled by planting bush sitao which, besides controlling weeds, produced income. This also reduces the cost of maintaining levees, particularly since the price of PCP has increased 30 percent.

For the wet season lowland rice crop, 1963, 35.5 hectares were prepared and planted for the various departments, as follows: Agronomy, 9.9; experimental farm, 8.5; varietal improvement, 7.3; entomology, 3.5; plant physiology, 2.1; plant pathology, 1.9; agricultural engineering, 1.7; and chemistry, .5. These plantings in-

cluded multiplication of 250 varieties for use in the international blast nurseries, and 98 varieties for the Chemistry Department's studies of rice quality. BPI-76 was the only variety planted for certified seed production.

The Experimental Farm, in cooperation with Agronomy, is conducting a long-term rotation experiment. The first crop of Chianung 242 was harvested and a second crop of the same variety was planted in October, using the same plots and treatments.

To enable all departments to use pure seed in experiments, seed of Taichung Native No. 1, Milfor 6, Chianung 242, Century Patna 231, Tainan 3, and Peta was produced. Some 500 panicles from each of these varieties were selected, treated

with hot water to control nematodes, and planted in rows 10 meters long, one panicle to the row, to permit discard of off-types.

Data on the performance under upland conditions of 10 varieties were taken, namely: Palawan, Mangarez, Azucena, Miltex, Milpal, Chianung 242, Century Patna 231, PI-215,936, Milfor 6, and HBDA.

A study on the production of three rice crops per year in one field was initiated.

A rat control campaign in early 1963 was successful, and rats no longer are considered a serious pest in the rice fields. The decline in rat population has resulted from the continuous use of poisoned baits and regular inspection of the fields. The men doing the control also extend their work to adjacent fields to make sure that

rats do not transfer to the experimental plots.

During 1963, 23.3 hectares were planted to upland crops, including upland rice, green manure legumes, sesbania, sorghum, corn, bush sitao, and soybeans, to restore soil uniformity and control weeds. The first crop of corn, although badly damaged by typhoons, yielded fairly well, producing 8,680 kg. of dry shelled corn on 3 hectares.

In a trial planting of 12 varieties of sorghum obtained from the U.P. College of Agriculture, Shrock produced the highest yields, followed by Saccaline and New Grain. Shrock was planted again on a larger area for commercial production, following upland rice.

Three hectares of a second crop of sweet corn were planted in October.

BUSH SITAO, GROWN ON LEVEES and between paddies, helps to control weeds and produces income.

JAPANESE AND FILIPINO SCIENTISTS conduct research in biochemistry.

Chemistry

BIOCHEMISTRY

The main aspects of research in biochemistry are (a) enzymatic mechanism of starch biosynthesis in ripening rice grains, (b) nitrogen metabolism of rice leaves with particular reference to the enzymatic nature of the so-called Fraction I protein, and (c) chemistry of flavonoid pigments in rice leaves.

Starch Biosynthesis

Starch constitutes 70-80 percent of the matured rice grain, higher than in most agricultural plants. During the year, the biochemists attempted to elucidate the nature of the enzymatic mechanism of starch formation in rice grains during the ripening stage, using conventional enzyme assays and radioisotopic techniques.

It long has been believed that phosphorylase is engaged in starch synthesis in plants; Aimi and his associates in Japan found that during the ripening stage, a parallel relationship exists between starch synthesis and phosphorylase activity in

rice grains. They also noted that pH changes which favored phosphorylase activity occurred within the grain cells. From an initial pH of 4.0 to 5.0, the pH rose to about 6.2 in 4 days after the onset of flowering. Despite these observations, mechanisms other than phosphorylase reaction for starch formation may exist. Accordingly, the Institute group investigated an alternate pathway of starch biosynthesis catalysed by UDPG-starch transglucosylase (I)

which has been studied quite extensively by Leloir and his group. This enzyme system also was studied in the hope of establishing a relationship, on the enzymatic level, with the mechanism of sucrose-starch interconversion. There still is no concrete experimental evidence for the latter system in plants, although sucrose has been found to be synthesized

by UDPG-sucrose transglucosylase (II). The reversal of reaction (II) would provide the UDPG necessary for reaction (I).

In the presence of UDPG-sucrose and UDPG-starch transglucosylases and UDP, there was a definite transfer of glucose from sucrose-C¹⁴ to starch molecules (Table 1). Thus, the linking of reactions (I) and (II), through the reversal of the second reaction, does occur, and the overall reaction may be written as (III).

It also was shown by radioisotopic experiment that fructose, the other half of the sucrose molecule, is eventually converted to glucose-1-phosphate through the initial step of the phosphorylation reaction. Glucose-1-phosphate is finally converted to UDPG by the UDPG-pyrophosphorylase reaction. The enzymatic conversion of fructose to glucose-1-phosphate is represented in Fig. 1. Hence, the overall reaction of sucrose-starch conversion may be written as (IV). The experimental results on hand now confirm the presence of a cyclic enzymatic mechanism governing sucrose-starch

conversion in ripening rice grains (Fig. 2)

Table 1. Relationship between the amount of starch granules and the rate of glucose transfer from sucrose-C¹⁴ to starch.

Experiment	Starch granules added (mg)	C ¹⁴ in starch (c.p.m.)	C ¹⁴ Incorporation (%)
1	2	1,070	0.47
2	4	1,290	0.57
3	6	2,440	1.07
4	8	3,060	1.34

Sucrose-C¹⁴ added: 2.28 x 10⁵ c.p.m.

Fig. 1. Enzymatic conversion of fructose to glucose-1-phosphate.

The transfer of glucose-C¹⁴ from both types of glucose donors, namely UDPG and sucrose, into the amylose and amylopectin fractions may indicate that the α(1→4) type structure of the starch

Fig. 2. Enzymatic mechanism of starch synthesis.

Fig. 3. Ion exchange column chromatography of nucleotides in ripening rice grains.

molecule is synthesized by the same enzymatic reaction, but the mechanism of branching of the starch molecule awaits further elucidation.

Recently, the group completed a study of the nucleotide composition in ripening rice grains (Fig. 3). The compounds were identified by spectrophotometric absorption (ultraviolet region), chemical analysis and degradation experiments, and paper chromatography. The presence of UDPG serves as evidence that the above-discussed mechanism truly operates in the starch formation of rice grains. However, a far more interesting finding is of a new nucleotide, adenosine diphosphate glucose (ADPG) and its subsequent isolation from rice grains (fraction V of Fig. 3). Its structure is:

Independently, Leloir's group recently isolated this nucleotide from corn, the first instance of its isolation from higher plants. The same group previously observed that chemically synthesized ADPG was about 10 times more active than UDPG in starch synthesis which is catalyzed by transglucosylase, and the presence of this nucleotide in rice grains may indicate its important role in the biological process. Preliminary experiments at the Institute also show that naturally isolated ADPG is much more actively utilized in starch synthesis. The biochemical mechanism of ADPG synthesis and its function in starch formation in rice are currently being investigated.

Enzymatic Study on Fraction-I Protein

Wildman and Bonner, in 1947, first described a single, electrophoretically homogeneous protein, designated as Fraction I, which constituted about 75 percent of the total proteins of spinach leaf cytoplasm. Several studies have since confirmed the presence of a major protein component which constitutes a large portion of the total soluble proteins in green

plant leaves. Furthermore, this protein has been implicated in photosynthetic carbon dioxide fixation.

In work preliminary to the study of protein metabolism in rice plants, the Institute group observed a major protein band among the other leaf proteins on starch gel electrophoresis. Suspecting that the major protein component of rice leaves might be Fraction I, the group undertook to purify this particular protein and to study its enzymatic nature.

Young rice plants of Taichung Native 1, an *indica* type, were harvested at the 3.5 to 4-leaf stage. The third leaf from the top of each plant was taken, pooled, and used as starting material. The leaves were minced and ground with buffer and the extract was subjected to successive centrifugations to remove any particulate material, including the ribosomes. The clear extract was then passed through Sephadex columns, from which the major protein component was partially purified.

The proteins obtained during the fractionation procedure were characterized by

Fig. 4. Protein patterns of the clarified extract (A) of young rice leaves and of the different fractions obtained from sephadex columns (B through G).

Fig. 5. Radioautogram of 3-phosphoglyceric acid formation by partially purified Fraction I protein of rice leaves.

starch gel electrophoresis. Figure 4 illustrates the protein patterns of the clarified leaf extract (A) and the different fractions obtained from the Sephadex columns (B through G). Of particular interest is the pattern obtained from a purified fraction (D) where only the predominant band *a* and an accompanying band *a*₁ are discernible. The latter band is believed to be an aggregation product of the former. Thus, it was possible to obtain fractions which contained only the major protein component.

The fixation of ¹⁴CO₂ using ribose 5-phosphate as substrate in the system was definitely catalyzed by the isolated major protein component. The main product of ¹⁴CO₂ fixation was 3-phosphoglyceric acid, as confirmed by ion-exchange chromatography of the incubation mixture. Furthermore, paper chromatography and subsequent radioautography revealed one main spot, although

rather diffuse, in the region where 3-phosphoglyceric acid may be expected to appear (Fig. 5).

In the fixation of $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ into ribose 5-phosphate and the subsequent reactions leading to the formation of 3-phosphoglyceric acid, three enzymes are involved, namely, phosphoriboisomerase, phosphoribulokinase, and ribulose 1,5-diphosphate carboxylase. In view of the findings described above, it is probable that all three enzymatic activities can be ascribed to Fraction I. Whether the partially purified protein preparation could catalyse the reactions beyond 3-phosphoglyceric acid poses a question. This, along with a more rigorous investigation into the presence of the three enzymatic activities on the same individual protein molecule, currently is being studied.

Flavonoid Chemistry

The distribution of flavonoid pigments in rice leaves was examined to determine whether such study might lead to a taxonomic index of so-called *indica* and *japo-*

nica rice varieties. The group found that paper electrophoretic separation of rice leaf pigments was far superior to that of the commonly used paper chromatography (n-butanol- $\text{NH}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$, 5:1:4 by vol. as a solvent). More than 10 distinct fluorescent pigments, believed to be flavonoids from their several chemical properties, were detected. A prominent fluorescent pigment was found to exist in *indica* rice leaves, but it is weak in *japonica* varieties almost without exception. Appropriate analytical studies on the crystallized product show that this substance is glucotricin, as previously isolated and determined by Oshima's group in Japan.

This is the first reported case of the isolation of glucotricin in a crystalline form, and some accurate analytical data are considered useful for future flavonoid chemistry. By using this pure specimen of glucotricin, the Institute group also established an assay for glucotricin in rice plant tissues. Analytical study of glucotricin in rice leaves of several varieties (*indica* and *japonica*) and its relation to growth is now underway.

CEREAL CHEMISTRY

The work in cereal chemistry is concerned with the complex nature of the nutritional, processing, and cooking and eating qualities of rice grown in the tropics and sub-tropics. This includes studies of the influence of variety and environmental factors, such as climate, soil fertility, and storage conditions, on the physical and chemical (physicochemical) properties of rice. Of particular interest in Asia, where rice is the staple food and diets are deficient in protein, is the possibility of improving the protein content of rice through changes in agricultural practices or the growing of high-protein varieties.

Physicochemical Properties of Rice

In preliminary studies of 16 varieties of nonwaxy (nonglutinous) *indica* and *japonica* rice grown at the Institute during the 1961-1962 crop year, chemists found significant correlations among varieties for chemical composition of rough, brown, and milled rice. In general, brown rice from the wet season crop had higher protein content and greater 100-grain weight than did that of the dry season crop. The *indica* varieties varied more in physicochemical properties than the *japonica* varieties.

Starch composition (amylose and amylopectin contents), protein content, and gelatinization temperature have been reported to be correlated with rice quality. Amy-

lose content has been directly related to flakiness and volume expansion of milled rice when cooked. Varieties which are high in protein content are reported to be flaky. Gelatinization temperature has been directly related to the cooking period of milled rice. Of the 16 varieties studied early this year, the gelatinization temperature of rice starch was not significantly correlated with protein or amylose content. Presumably, these three factors are independent.

The amino acid composition of milled rice of the dry season crop, as determined by ion-exchange column chromatography, varied significantly among the 16 varieties (Table 2). Most important to human nutrition were the significant negative corre-

lations between protein content and lysine, threonine and methionine contents. Lysine is the most limiting essential amino acid of rice proteins. Rice proteins are also reported deficient in threonine and methionine.

The nutritive and cooking quality of rice in southeast Asia has not been studied comprehensively. People in each country associate various physical properties of rice with quality. To determine the feasibility of improving the nutritional (protein) level and to express in chemical terms the quality of rice in this region, chemists are surveying some physicochemical properties, including protein and amylose contents and gelatinization characteristics, of 55 varieties. Rough rice samples of recommended varieties indigenous to each of the five co-

Table 2. Amino acid composition of milled rice, calculated to 16.8 grams of nitrogen for 3 *indica* varieties, the average composition of 4 *japonica* varieties, and correlation coefficients between protein content and percentages of the individual amino acids for 12 *indica* and 4 *japonica* varieties analyzed.

Amino acid	Indica varieties			<i>Japonica</i> Mean (4 var.)	Overall Mean (16 var.)	r ¹
	Peta	Taichung 1	Rexoro			
Alanine	6.2	6.5	6.1	6.2	6.3	-0.09
Arginine	8.4	9.3	9.2	9.0	8.9	+0.61 ³
Aspartic Acid	10.8	10.9	10.5	10.6	10.9	-0.27
Cystine	1.4	1.2	1.1	1.0	1.1	-0.09
Glutamic Acid	24.0	23.0	21.1	23.3	23.2	+0.05
Glycine	5.7	5.2	4.9	5.0	5.1	-0.37
Histidine	2.7	2.6	2.6	2.5	2.6	+0.05
Isoleucine ²	4.8	4.9	4.8	4.4	4.7	+0.08
Leucine ²	9.7	9.6	9.4	9.2	9.5	+0.55 ³
Lysine ²	4.9	4.4	3.8	3.9	4.0	-0.64 ⁴
Methionine ²	2.8	2.1	1.4	1.8	2.0	-0.72 ⁴
Phenylalanine ²	5.8	6.2	6.0	6.0	6.1	+0.34
Proline	5.5	5.6	5.2	5.5	5.3	-0.43
Serine	5.8	5.7	5.4	5.9	5.7	-0.18
Threonine ²	4.5	3.9	3.8	3.9	4.0	-0.65 ⁴
Tyrosine	2.9	3.9	4.1	3.4	3.6	+0.89 ⁴
Valine ²	6.6	6.6	6.1	6.1	6.2	+0.02
Ammonia	2.4	2.6	2.9	2.6	2.5	+0.38
Crude Protein % dry wt.	6.50	10.19	12.55			

¹ Correlation coefficient between protein content and individual amino acid values (n = 16).

² Nutritionally essential to man.

³ Significant.

⁴ Highly significant.

Table 3. Some physicochemical properties of representative varieties of rice in southeast Asia.

Variety	Rough rice			Polished rice					
	Length mm.	Width mm.	Protein* (N x 5.95) %	Amylose ¹ %	Cel. Temp. ² °C	Alkali values S, C ³	Peak B.U. ⁴	Amylograph viscosity Drop at 94°C B.U. ⁴	Setback B.U. ⁴
INDONESIA									
Bengawan	9.7	2.8	7.41	22.8	69	4.9,3.9	890	495	-170
Sigadis	8.9	2.9	8.22	27.8	69	4.9,3.9	1,000	345	+200
Benong 130	7.0	3.3	8.40	24.2	69	5.9,4.9	820	460	-140
MALAYA									
Seraup 50	8.0	3.0	8.00	30.1	69	5.0,3.8	710	140	+280
Anak Naga 21	8.9	2.6	9.23	27.7	69.5	5.0,3.6	700	200	+260
Acheh Puteh	7.2	2.8	7.56	30.3	70	5.0,3.7	750	190	+450
PHILIPPINES									
Peta	9.0	2.8	7.58	25.3	69.5	4.8,3.4	840	210	+390
BPI-76	8.1	2.9	8.66	21.4	70.5	3.8,3.0	830	400	-160
Azacena	9.8	2.8	7.21	19.6	69.5	4.6,3.8	730	360	-90
Malagkit Sungsong	7.2	3.5	6.77	5.0	60	6.0,5.1	675	365	-235
THAILAND									
Nahang Mon S-4	10.6	2.9	6.48	26.2	58.5	7.0,6.0	660	210	+240
Leuang Yai 34	9.7	2.9	6.80	31.2	58	7.0,6.0	850	40	+620
Khao Dawk Mali 105	10.0	2.3	7.81	17.3	57.5	6.8,5.8	1,085	625	-405
Khao Niaw Dam	9.0	3.0	10.98	5.7	57.5	6.0,5.0	550	225	-125
VIETNAM									
Puang Ngeon	9.1	2.5	7.39	28.2	69.5	4.9,3.6	830	165	+450
Trang Doc	8.5	2.9	8.47	22.7	70	4.8,3.8	815	420	-145
Lua Tieu Hanoi	7.4	3.2	6.91	26.4	68.5	5.7,4.6	840	270	+200

¹ Dry basis; ² Gelatinization temperature; ³ Spreading, clearing values; ⁴ Brabender units.

Century Patna 231

BPI-76

Ve Veng

Nahng Mon S-4

Spreading 2
Clearing 1

Spreading 4
Clearing 3

Spreading 6
Clearing 5

Spreading 7
Clearing 6

Fig. 6. Varieties differ in the digestibility of whole kernels of milled rice after 23 hours in dilute alkali solution.

operating countries were obtained through their agricultural ministries. At the same time, the Institute grows these varieties under uniform conditions at Los Baños.

Of the 55 varieties, 51 were nonglutinous

(nonwaxy) and 4 were glutinous (waxy). Representative values for selected varieties are in Table 3. Amylose contents ranged from 2.9-31.8 percent; protein, 5.74-10.98 percent; and gelatinization temperature,

Fig. 7. Amylograms of aqueous rice powder suspensions are influenced by the amylose content and the protein content of the varieties.

56.5°-71°C. Length and width dimensions of rough rice are not significantly correlated with protein and amylose contents. The study also verified the results on Institute-grown nonwaxy samples, i.e., protein content, amylose content, and gelatinization temperature were not significantly correlated. Varieties from Thailand were confirmed to have lower gelatinization temperatures than their high amylose contents would suggest. This same property was noted on Institute- and Taiwan-grown Tai-chung Native 1.

Alkali spreading and clearing values of whole milled rice kernels may be used as a qualitative measure of gelatinization temperature (Fig. 6).

The Brabender amylograph facilitates the continuous measurement of pasting viscosity of rice powder suspensions during heating, cooking, and cooling (Fig. 7).

Amylograph peak or maximum hot-paste viscosity was significantly negatively correlated with protein content, but was not significantly correlated with amylose content. The decrease in viscosity from peak viscosity, on cooking for 20 minutes at 94°C. in the amylograph, was highly significantly negatively correlated with amylose content. This value is related to the resistance to disintegration of gelatinized starch granules. Setback value (difference in viscosity on cooling to 50°C. and peak viscosity) was highly significantly positively correlated with amylose content (Fig. 8).

The pasting characteristics and the amylose contents of these samples were closely related to the cooking and eating qualities of these varieties in their countries of origin. In countries such as Malaya, Vietnam, and most of Thailand, where people prefer rice which is flaky and which has

Fig. 8. Amylograph setback values and amylose content of polished rice of 51 southeast nonwaxy varieties were highly significantly correlated.

high volume expansion when cooked, the rice samples had more than 25 percent amylose and high positive setback values. In the Philippines and Indonesia, the main criterion is softness in cooked rice even when cold, although some people also desire flakiness and high volume expansion. The varieties of choice in these countries had less than 25 percent amylose and low setback values, as hardening of gelatinized starch is caused mainly by amylose retrogradation. Obviously, these lower amylose varieties may have less flakiness and lower volume expansion than the high amylose rices.

Increased Protein Content and Rice Quality

Unintentional delayed planting of four varieties in the 1962 wet season produced grain with higher protein. Further inves-

tigations of eight varieties in a date-of-planting experiment revealed that samples planted in November, 1962, had, on the average, 4.5 percent higher protein contents in brown rice than those planted in December, 1962 (Table 4). The durations and yields of the two crops were comparable. (A similar difference in protein content was noted in a related experiment for another set of eight varieties planted and grown during the same periods.)

Studies of these eight pairs of samples indicated that the length and width and the hulling percentage of rough rice were not affected by the increase in protein content. The protein levels of the December, 1962, samples were normal. The effect of increased protein content on amylose content was not consistent for the samples. However, the high protein samples had lower gelatinization temperatures and amy-

Table 4. Some physicochemical properties of two crops of rice of eight varieties differing in protein content.

Variety	Month planted ¹ 1962	Brown rice		Milled rice				
		Protein ² %	Protein ² %	Amylose %	Gel. Temp. ³ °C	Amylograph viscosity		
						Peak B.U. ⁴	Drop at 94°C B.U. ⁴	Setback B.U. ⁴
BPI-76	Nov.	14.72	14.34	27.2	69	680	305	- 20
	Dec.	8.99	8.86	26.0	70	820	400	-100
Peta	Nov.	11.64	10.96	31.0	65.5	605	100	+420
	Dec.	7.70	6.80	30.0	68	815	195	+235
Raminad Str. 3	Nov.	12.42	12.21	23.5	69.5	790	380	- 80
	Dec.	8.43	8.36	21.8	72	1,050	670	-370
Siam 29	Nov.	13.27	13.02	31.4	69	730	110	+335
	Dec.	7.86	7.30	31.2	70	950	250	+300
Taichung 1	Nov.	13.83	12.54	31.2	62.5	745	10	+735
	Dec.	9.10	7.68	31.2	64.5	920	140	+700
Tjere Mas	Nov.	12.26	11.77	26.2	67	810	110	+420
	Dec.	7.78	6.40	30.0	69.5	980	280	+210
59-368	Nov.	12.24	11.12	32.2	70	480	135	+235
	Dec.	7.45	7.08	31.4	70.5	650	220	+250
Chia-nan 8	Nov.	10.43	9.27	23.2	62	595	250	0
	Dec.	7.50	6.15	20.0	64	725	345	-85
Mean	Nov.	12.60	11.90	28.2	67	680	175	+255
	Dec.	8.10	7.33	27.7	68.5	865	310	+140
Analysis of variance (interaction)								
Least significant difference (5% level)		0.15	0.09	1.64				

¹ Seeded first of month, transplanted after 20 days, one plant per hill, 25 x 30 cm.apan

² N x 5.95.

³ Gelatinization temperature.

⁴ Brabender units.

logram peak viscosities. Preliminary study of fertilizer effects on the Chianung 242 produced in a maximum yield experiment, 1962 wet season, also showed reduced peak viscosity with increasing protein level. In most of the samples, setback values were higher for the high protein samples. Milled high protein rice was more flinty but less white in color than the samples with normal protein content.

Chemical Constituents of Rice

Generally, rice is cooked and consumed as a whole grain, unlike wheat and other cereals which are ground into flour. Consequently, scientists believe it important to study the distribution in the grain and the properties of its various carbohydrates, proteins, and other substances. Such studies, until now, have been hampered by the lack of suitable methods of isolation, purification, and characterization.

Gas chromatographic analysis of the methyl esters of rice bran and milled rice lipids of two waxy and two nonwaxy varieties indicated that the principal fatty acids were oleic, linoleic, and palmitic (Table 5). The mean polyunsaturated or essential fatty acids content of bran lipids was 38 percent, but only 19 percent for milled rice lipids.

Study of the composition and distribution of rice protein and its fractions, as influenced by protein level, is in progress. It has been reported that the amino acid composition of the rice protein fractions, albumins, globulins, prolamins, and glutelins, are essentially constant, and any variation in amino acids composition is caused by a change in the ratio of these various fractions. Also, increased protein content has been reported to be mainly an increase in glutelin. Fractional extraction of rice proteins was successfully done by the percolation method of Maes.

On the basis of amylose content and gelatinization temperature, rice starch may be classified into five types (Table 6): (a) Glutinous or waxy starch, with low amylose and low gelatinization temperature, and four types of nonwaxy starches: (b) low (less than 25 percent) amylose and low (63-68°C.) gelatinization temperature, including the *japonica* and "bulu" varieties; (3) low amylose but high (74°C. or higher) gelatinization temperature, exemplified by Century Patna 231; (d) high (25 percent or higher) amylose with low or intermediate (63-73°C.) gelatinization temperature, such as the Indonesian and Philippine varieties, and (e) nonwaxy rice with gelatinization temperature below 63°C., such as Taichung Native 1 and the varieties from Thailand.

Table 5. Mean iodine value and fatty acid composition of lipids of brown rice, rice bran, and milled rice of two waxy and two non-waxy varieties.

	Brown rice lipids	Rice bran lipids	Milled rice lipids
Iodine value (Wijs Method)	86.6	90.5	62.0
Fatty Acid Composition, % ¹			
Myristic	0.4	0.3	0.6
Palmitic	20.4	18.3	33.8
Palmitoleic	0.2	0.2	0.4
Stearic	1.6	1.4	2.7
Oleic	41.3	41.0	43.3
Linoleic	34.5	37.1	18.0
Linolenic	1.0	1.1	0.6
Arachidic	0.6	0.6	0.4

¹Percentage of weight of total acids. Mean of three gas liquid chromatography determinations. Less than 0.1 percent lauric acid present.

Table 6. Representative types of rice starch based on amylose content and gelatinization temperature¹.

	Subspecies	% content ² Amylose	Gelatinization temperature °C
Waxy:			
Type a			
Malagkit Sungsong Puti	<i>Indica</i>	3.3	63.5
Taichung Glutinous 46	<i>Japonica</i>	6.1	60.5
Nonwaxy:			
Type b			
Taichung 65	<i>Japonica</i>	16.7	67
Chia-nan 8	<i>Japonica</i>	17.3	65.5
Baok	"Bulu"	23.2	67.5
Type c			
Century Patna 231	<i>Indica x japonica</i>	13.5	76.5
Type d			
Peta	<i>Indica</i>	30.2	72
Tjere Mas	<i>Indica</i>	29.0	67
Sigadis	<i>Indica</i>	27.8	69
Type e			
Taichung Native 1	<i>Indica</i>	27.7	62
Nahng Mon S-4	<i>Indica</i>	24.1	55
Leuang Awn 29	<i>Indica</i>	25.5	55

¹ Data from Institute grown samples.

² Percentage of dry weight of milled rice.

Preliminary x-ray diffraction studies on purified rice starches indicate differences in their degree of crystallinity. Chemists are determining the relative molecular weights and intrinsic viscosities of the starch and starch fractions of representative samples of each rice starch type as the probable causes of observed differences in starch physicochemical properties of different varieties.

Taste Panel Evaluations of Factors

Since amylogram determinations are made on milled rice powder, the role of cell wall constituents on the cooking properties is minimized. Besides, objective laboratory tests complement but cannot replace

taste panel evaluation. Thus, to determine the practical role of protein, amylose, and gelatinization temperature, the Home Technology Department, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, is evaluating selected samples. These include the high- and normal-protein rice samples of the same varieties, and samples of different varieties which essentially differ only in amylose content or gelatinization temperature.

Preliminary results indicate that high protein samples require more water than normal protein samples to cook to the same consistency. This results in greater volume and weight of cooked rice. At the same water level, the high protein samples were harder in texture.

Changes During Rice Storage

Conditions of storage of rough rice influence the cooking and eating qualities. In a study of the hygroscopic equilibria of rough rice of two nonwaxy and two waxy varieties, relative humidity influenced the moisture content of rice more than temperature did. Moisture contents of the four varieties were essentially the same at any relative humidity below 75 percent at a given temperature.

Storage studies of two varieties indicated that glutamic acid decarboxylase activity (GADA) of the grain, as determined by a Sandstedt and Blish pressuremeter, more reliably indexed the viability of stored rice than did fat acidity (Fig. 9). GADA decreased faster at the moisture contents of 16-17 percent than at 12-13 percent and at 40° and 30° C. than at 4°C. during storage. The decreases in GADA were essentially identical in both air and nitrogen atmospheres. The products of enzymic hydrolyses during 8 months of storage were followed and correlated with GADA. Free amino acids, reducing sugars and fat acidity were negatively correlated with GADA, whereas, nonreducing sugars were positively correlated with GADA.

Fig. 9. Glutamic acid decarboxylase activity (GADA) was a reliable index of the viability stored seed of two varieties. 1 = Peta; 2 Chianung 242.

Analyses of the composition of the free amino acids, sugars, and free fatty acids of rice of two varieties were made by column, paper, and gas-liquid chromatography, respectively. The principal free amino acids were serine, glutamic acid, and alanine. Sucrose was the principal non-reducing sugar in milled rice. The reducing sugars were mainly hexoses. The free fatty acids analyzed by gas-liquid chromatography of their methyl ester were principally palmitic, oleic, and linoleic.

In another storage study in progress of two nonwaxy and two waxy varieties, marked increases in the amylograph viscosities were noted after 6 months of storage, accompanied by decreased α - and β -amylolytic susceptibilities of the starch preheated in water at 50°C. Gelatinization temperatures also increased.

Methods for Testing Rice Quality

Rice quality evaluations are not standardized, and each investigator uses his own procedures. This prevents the comparison of results of various laboratories. Because of the confused state of quality terms and tests for rice, the International Association of Cereal Chemistry last year created a Study Group on Test Methods for Rice. The cereal chemists maintain liaison with this study group, as well as with the Rice Quality Laboratory at Beaumont, Texas.

A rapid colorimetric assay for protein is sought. Extraction methods are hampered by the inherent poor solubility characteristics of rice proteins in neutral solvents. Adsorptions by rice proteins of dyes such as Amido Black 10B was highly significantly correlated to Kjeldahl nitrogen but this colorimetric method is tedious and has a higher coefficient of variability than the Kjeldahl method.

Agricultural Economics

The agricultural economics program of the Institute was instituted with the addition of an agricultural economist to the staff in May. Initial activity focused primarily on (a) preparation of a statement outlining the proposed agricultural economics research and training program at the Institute, and (b) preparation of a syllabus to be used with trainees from other departments who plan to include economic evaluation in the analysis of their research results.

In addition, work was initiated on three specific projects dealing with (a) the contribution of increased area planted and increased yields to growth of rice output in southeast Asia, (b) the economic analysis of the results of insecticide experiments, and (c) the implications of national rice marketing and pricing policies in southeast Asia.

The head of the agricultural economics program is a consultant to the Vietnam

Ministry of Rural Affairs and the Ministry of National Economy on a study of rice marketing and pricing policy. The study is sponsored by the two ministries and the United States Agency for International Development.

As part of the process of becoming acquainted with national economic development and agricultural economic research in southeast Asia, the head of the department visited government and university economics research divisions and departments in the Philippines, Vietnam, Malaya, and Thailand.

He also conducted a graduate course, "The Economics of Technological Change in Agriculture," during the first semester, 1963-64, at the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture. He will present a graduate course, "Agricultural Resource Development," during the second semester.

STAFF MEMBERS AND SCHOLARS confer with the agricultural economist.

STUDENTS ENROLLED IN STATISTICS compare judgment vs. probability sampling procedures for selecting rice panicles.

Statistics

The Department of Statistics (a) consults with research workers on the design and analysis of experiments and surveys and provides computational service in the analyses of data; (b) provides instruction

on statistical concepts and techniques with special emphasis of their application to rice research, and (c) conducts theoretical and experimental studies on statistical problems associated with research on the rice plant.

INSTRUCTION

After a preliminary study of courses in statistics and mathematics at the College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, a series of three courses in statistics was instituted into the graduate curriculum and will be presented by the statistician: Design and Analysis of Experiments; Probability and Elementary Statistical Methods; and Sampling and Survey Design. These courses will serve the

needs and requirements of IRRI research scholars and research assistants as well as graduate students in the biological, social, and economic fields of agriculture at the UPCA.

A book manuscript, "Statistics in Rice Research," was prepared. These notes may be published as a book by December, 1964.

STUDIES OF STATISTICAL PROBLEMS

Variability and Size of Sample

The usual measure of variability is the coefficient of variation of a sample mean ($\bar{x}$) which is given by

$$cv(\bar{x})\% = (s / \sqrt{n} \bar{x}) 100 \\ = cv(X)\% / \sqrt{n}$$

where

s is the sample standard deviation,

$\bar{x}$ is the sample mean,

n is the size of sample for the desired level of precision, and

$cv(X)\%$ is the coefficient of variability of a single observation.

In the study of several varieties or several treatments, this simple measure of variability is not enough. Data from greenhouse and field experiments indicate that a linear relationship exists between s and $\bar{x}$ ($s = a + b\bar{x}$), and four simple forms may be derived. Forms A, B, and

C are in Tables 1 and 2 for greenhouse and field experiments, respectively, for seven characteristics. The last column in Tables 1 and 2 is the coefficient of variability of a single observation, $cv(X)\%$, which is a function of a sample mean $\bar{x}$ for forms A and C and is a constant for form B. Figure 1 illustrates Form A, Table 2, for grain yield. Figure 2 illustrates Form B, Table 2, for weight of straw, while Fig. 3 illustrates Form C, Table 2, for 100-grain weight. Form D exhibits a negative value for a . This particular form was not observed but is illustrated in Fig. 4.

For any given sample mean $\bar{x}$ or range of $\bar{x}$ of the experimental units, the $cv(X)\%$ curve may be used to derive the size of sample n needed to maintain a desired level of $cv(\bar{x})$ equal to $a = 1, 5$ or 10 percent by solving the equation

$$n = cv(X)\% / a^2$$

Table 1. Forms of relationship of the standard deviation (s) and the coefficient of variation $cv(X)\%$ to the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) by plant characteristic at harvest; greenhouse experiments, IRRIL, 1963.

Form	Characteristics	Form of equation for	
		s	$cv(X)\%$
A	Grain yield (gm.)	$s_b^{**} = 2.50 + 0.2382\bar{x}$	$(250/\bar{x}) + 23.82$
		$s_w^{***} = 2.46 + 0.1762\bar{x}$	$(246/\bar{x}) + 17.62$
	Number of grains per panicle	$s_b = 11.39 + 0.0968\bar{x}$	$(1139/\bar{x}) + 9.68$
		$s_w = 9.88 + 0.0662\bar{x}$	$(988/\bar{x}) + 6.62$
B	Plant height (cm.)	$s_b = 0.0634\bar{x}$	6.34
		$s_w = 0.0575\bar{x}$	5.75
	Plant height (cm.) time series (Peta)	$s_b = 0.0516\bar{x}$	5.16
		$s_w = 0.2253\bar{x}$	22.53
	Number of tillers	$s_b = 0.2151\bar{x}$	21.51
		$s_w = 0.2907\bar{x}$	29.07
	Number of mature panicles	$s_b = 0.1853\bar{x}$	18.53
		$s_w = 0.1747\bar{x}$	17.47
Weight of straw (gm.)	$s_w = 0.1697\bar{x}$	16.97	
C	100-grain weight (gm.)	$s_b = 0.090$	$(9/\bar{x})$
		$s_w = 0.073$	$(7.3/\bar{x})$

** s_b is the between pots variability
 *** s_w is the between plants variability

Table 2. Forms of relationship of the standard deviation (s) and the coefficient of variation $cv(X)\%$ to the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) by plant characteristic at harvest; field experiment on yield duration of 40 varieties, IRRI, 1963.

Form	Characteristics	Form of the equation for	
		s	$cv(X)\%$
A	Grain yield (gm.) (Fig. 1)	$s = 4.05 + 0.1544\bar{x}$	$(405/\bar{x}) + 15.44$
	Number of mature panicles	$s = 1.34 + 0.160\bar{x}$	$(134/\bar{x}) + 16.0$
B	Plant height (cm.) 7 weeks after trans- planting, $n = 45$	$s = 0.1038\bar{x}$	10.38
	Number of tillers	$s = 0.2036\bar{x}$	20.36
	Number of grains per panicle	$s = 0.0994\bar{x}$	9.94
	Weight of straw (gm.) (Fig. 2)	$s = 0.2630\bar{x}$	26.30
C	100-grain weight (gm.) (Fig. 3)	$s = 0.093$	$9.3/\bar{x}$

where

$cv(X)\%$ is obtained from the corresponding figure or equation of the characteristic under study,

and

α is the desired level of precision of $cv(\bar{x})$ in percentage.

These results also indicate that for wide ranges of $\bar{x}$, there is a need to transform the original data by either the square root or logarithmic transformation to validate the use of the analysis of variance tech-

Fig. 1. Relationship of the standard deviation (s) and coefficient of variation $cv(X)\%$ to the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) for grain yield in grams. Field experiment on grain yield of 40 rice varieties of varying maturity.

Fig. 2. Relationship of the standard deviation (s) and coefficient of variation $cv(X)\%$ to the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) for weight of straw in grams. Field experiment on grain yield of 40 rice varieties of varying maturity.

nique in comparative experiments. The result for 100-grain weight indicates that this is the only characteristic studied which exhibits equal variance for all varieties and/or treatments.

Sampling Plant Height and Tiller Count

Results of these sampling studies indicate that for plant height and tiller count, the sample plants or hills may be taken from the outer rows or from the outer hills in the rows of the experimental plot proper after removal of guard rows or hills. The sampling schemes or positions are considered as ordinary effects and these effects are compared using the classical F-test with the mean squares from the analysis of variance. No significant differences were observed in all tests for plant height and tiller count.

If the collections of height and tiller count data will be in a form of a time series, sampling the outer rows or outer hills will be advantageous since this technique

Fig. 3. Relationship of the standard deviation (s) and coefficient of variation $cv(X)\%$ to the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) for 100-grain weight in grams. Field experiment on grain yield of 40 rice varieties of varying maturity.

Fig. 4. Form D with the s -intercept (a) as negative and the slope (b) positive.

not only will provide a precise estimate of the same parameter as those obtained from the inner portion of the experimental plot but also eliminates the entrance to the plot. This avoids the introduction of extraneous factors which will magnify the experimental error for tests of significance on components of yield and other important characteristics.

Sampling for Stem Borer Attack

Results of experimental studies on the development of efficient sampling procedures for characteristics of stem borer resistance show the various magnitudes of variability which are contributed within the ultimate plot. These variations will indicate the optimum combination of the number of hills (h) in the cluster, number of clusters (c) in the plot; and the number of replications (r) which will be needed to reduce the variance of a variety mean to a given level.

For this study, 20 varieties out of the 243 varieties tested for stem borer resistance (wet season, 1962) were chosen systematically with a random start. The design was a simple randomized block in three replication ($r=3$) with subsampling in each replication involving four rows or clusters ($c=4$), each cluster consisting of five hills ($h=5$). This scheme gave a total of 60 observations per variety on percentage

Table 3 Coefficient of variation of $\bar{x}$, $cv(\bar{x})$, in percentage for varying values of h' , c' and r' ; August sampling, IRRI, 1962.

Number of hills, h'	Number of clusters, c'		
	4	6	8
$r' = 3$ replicates:			
5	16	15	14
10	15	14	13
15	15	13	13
$r' = 4$ replicates:			
5	14	13	12
10	13	12	11
15	13	12	11
$r' = 5$ replicates:			
5	13	11	11
10	12	11	10
15	11	10	10

dead hearts on a hill basis or 1,200 observations for the 20 varieties under test. The objective is to obtain estimates of each of the components of the variance of a variety mean and on the basis of these estimates develop an efficient sampling scheme. The analysis of variance was used to isolate these components.

Preliminary analysis of the mean squares (MS) components for replications (R), varieties (V), and the interaction (R x V) indicate that these estimates from the 20 varieties are the same as those obtained for the total of 243 varieties. Thus, the more detailed study of the effects of the number of hills (h), number of clusters (c), and number of replications (r) needed to maintain a certain level of variability of a variety mean ($\bar{x}$) was conducted using only 20 varieties.

The analyses of variance is used to give unbiased and precise estimates of the components of variance. These estimates are

Table 4. Estimates of components of variance from the analysis of variance for percentage of dead hearts on a hill basis; July and August sampling, IRRI, 1962.

Sampling dates 1962	Estimates of component of variance			Variety mean	Coefficient of variation of $\bar{x}$, $cv(\bar{x})$, in percentage
	2^2_{h} (hill)	2^2_{c} (cluster)	2^2_{e} (plot)		
July	63	12.8	1.3	6.6	24
August	79	20.4	5.3	13.3	16

used to derive the coefficient of variation of a variety mean ($\bar{x}$) for varying values of number of hills (h'), number of clusters (c') and number of replications (r'). The results are in Table 3. From this table, the $cv(\bar{x})$ may be reduced to 10 percent by using 5 replicates ($r' = 5$), 6 clusters ($c' = 6$) and 15 hills ($h' = 15$).

These estimates will be tested with other estimates in a time series, and if found appropriate, pooled estimates will be used to design future experiments on stem borer resistance. In addition, these estimates may be tested and used in the design of sampling surveys to obtain objective measures of stem borer incidence in farmer's paddy field and the possible effects of incidence on the rice crop losses.

For comparative purposes, the analyses of variance for the July, 1962, sampling also was obtained to have estimates of the components of variance for percentage of dead hearts. The estimates for July and August samplings are in Table 4.

Note that although the components of variance $s^2_{h'}$, $s^2_{c'}$ and $s^2_{e'}$ are relatively smaller in the July sampling than in the August sampling, the $cv(\bar{x})$ in percentage is larger in July than in August. These results suggest that a more intensive sampling will be needed in the earlier than in the later period to maintain a given level of precision.

Estimation of Loss from Rice Stem Borer

Data from an experiment on the efficiency of various insecticidal sprayings on

rice borer control were used to illustrate the technique of estimating the losses incurred from stem borer incidence in replicated field experiments. This particular experiment consisted of eight insecticidal treatments, replicated four times, or a total of 32 observations from experimental plots. Milfor 6 was used and the incidence of stem borer was taken 2 months after transplanting (March 18, 1963) and at harvest time (May 20, 1963).

The data enabled derivation of the relationships between infested tillers in percentage and dead hearts in percentage 2 months after transplanting with yield of grain in ton/ha. At time of harvest, the relationships between infested tillers in percentage and white heads in percentage with yield in ton/ha. also were computed. From these relationships were derived the yield loss curve by a transformation of the yield curve into percentages (Table 5).

It is pertinent to state that positive and significant correlation exists between percentage of dead hearts and percentage of infested tillers at 2 months after transplanting ($r = 0.931$, $P < .01$) and between percentage of white heads and percentage of infested tillers at harvest time ($r = 0.680$, $P < .01$). These indicate that the percentage of infested tillers may be predicted from data on dead hearts and/or white heads.

From Table 5, it is possible to predict that as early as 2 months after transplanting there will be a reduction of 1.65 percent in total yield for every 1 percent in dead hearts, and if infested tillers are used, there will be a reduction of 1.28 percent in total yield for every 1 percent of infested tillers. At harvest time, the relationships are 2.29 percent reduction in yield for every 1 percent of white heads and 0.37 percent reduction for every 1 percent of infested tillers.

Results of these sampling studies may be used to estimate the incidence of stem borer in farmers' paddy fields in a given locality or in a given region. With yield data obtained from crop cutting and/or interview surveys, these estimates on stem borer incidence will provide objective methods for estimating losses which are incurred from the various levels of stem borer attack.

Ratio Estimators for Grain Yield

In experimental plots which are generally small or medium in size, the harvesting may involve cutting the plant a few centimeters below the neck of the panicle. After this operation, the harvested material is threshed, winnowed, cleaned, and weighed. This operation consumes time and results in certain losses which may mask the effects of the treatments. An efficient and precise method of estimating

Table 5. Relationships of yield of clean grain and incidence of stem borer in replicated field experiments.

Yield of clean grain in:	Two months after transplanting	
	Dead hearts(X) (%)	Infested tillers(X) (%)
Ton/ha. (Y)	$Y = 6.829 - 0.1125X$	$Y = 6.988 - 0.0898X$
Percentage, P(Y)	$P(Y) = 100 - 1.65X$	$P(Y) = 100 - 1.28X$
	At harvest time	
	White heads(X) (%)	Infested tillers(X) (%)
Ton/ha. (Y)	$Y = 7.396 - 0.1695X$	$Y = 7.611 - 0.0281X$
Percentage, P(Y)	$P(Y) = 100 - 2.29X$	$P(Y) = 100 - 0.37X$

grain yield from the plot must be devised.

Also, in crop cutting which involves small size cuts, a ratio estimator is in order. This estimator uses the concomitant variable, panicle weight in g. (Z_i), and the grain weight (Y_i) in the panicle for n panicles. The panicle weight for the whole plot (Z) is obtained. The estimator for grain yield is

$$\hat{Y} = (\text{ratio}) Z$$

where the ratio may be termed mean of ratios or the ratio of means and Z is the total of the concomitant variable. The mean of ratios may be made unbiased by adding a correction term. Thus, the empirical results which are useful for experimental plots will be used as a statistical framework for devising a simple but efficient objective method of estimating grain yields from paddy fields or for larger rice crop areas. It is important to supplement the resulting estimates with interviews on yield, hectarage, and other relevant facts about the farm business which could not be obtained by such a method as crop-cutting.

The ratio estimators—mean of ratios, ratio of means, and the unbiased ratio estimators—are compared with the regular unbiased estimator and the results from six

varieties show that gain in statistical efficiency ranges from 800 percent to 32,000 percent. The correlation ($\hat{\rho}$) between panicle weight and grain weight on a panicle basis ranges from 0.942 to 0.999 which explains the observed gains in statistical efficiency. From these initial results, sampling studies were conducted to isolate the components of variance from different plots under different cultural managements such as equally spaced hills and/or rows, drilled, and broadcast under lowland and upland conditions.

Empirical results indicate that the correlation between panicle weight (Z_i) and grain weight (Y_i) for hills (cuts or sub-areas), rows (or areas), plots, and treatments range from 0.94 to 0.99 for all stages. These correlations will result in considerable gain in precision in the use of ratio estimators in the estimation of grain yield at all stages of sampling.

It may be concluded that panicle weight can be used as a concomitant variable in the estimation of grain yield, and these estimates can be used as the variable for comparison in the test of significance. Also, these results can be used in the estimation of grain yield in a farmer's paddy field or in a larger rice crop area.

THIS PLOT-SIDE VISUAL DISPLAY of factors influencing lodging drew many favorable comments at the first invitational field day.

Office of Communication

The Institute's Office of Communication was established with the arrival of its head on April 1, 1963. In his first months, he delineated the functions of the office, ascertained and ordered appropriate equipment, employed and trained personnel, and established policies and procedures for the operation of the office in relation to the purposes and needs of the Institute.

In addition to providing the scientific and administrative staff with editorial,

publication, photographic, and audio-visual services, the Office of Communication is concerned with (a) developing and evaluating means of effectively disseminating the results of the Institute's research programs, (b) providing and developing communication training opportunities for the Institute staff, scholars, and others, and (c) research on the communication processes and other factors associated with technological and social change.

DISSEMINATION OF RESEARCH DATA

The office directed primary attention to establishing policies, procedures, and means for disseminating the research findings of the Institute to at least three groups: (a) working scientists, (b) government officials, administrators and educators, and (c) interested segments of the general public.

Communication to Scientists

The principal means of communication at present are scientific articles written by senior staff members and submitted to established scientific and technical journals. Upon publication, the Institute distributes reprints to supplement the circulation of the particular journal in the rice-

growing areas. To this end, the Office of Communication, in cooperation with the scientific and administrative staffs, developed procedures for processing journal manuscripts within the Institute.

Two other Institute activities, international symposia and translation services, make available a great range of significant rice research data in the English language. The first symposium-based book, including the 21 papers presented in the Symposium on Rice Genetics and Cytogenetics, will be published in early 1964 by the Elsevier Publishing Company, Amsterdam, The Netherlands. Upon completion of the editorial work presently underway, the office expects to publish the book based on the 28 papers presented in the Symposium on the Rice Blast Disease. Present plans are to publish the translations in a Rice Research Translations series.

Communication to Administrators, Educators and Others

The Institute recognizes its responsibilities and opportunities to communicate with leaders and professional workers in governmental, educational, and commercial activities in the rice-growing countries.

The Office of Communication has cooperated with various Philippine agencies and the Agency for International Development in creating a Communications Coordinating Committee for the Philippines. Among its objectives, the CCC attempts to facilitate the flow of agricultural research information from the scientist to the educator and extension worker, and from them to rice growers and farmers. At the same time, the CCC hopes to provide professional improvement programs in communication for relevant personnel in the various agencies, to promote research on communication problems, and to stimulate more cooperation and efficiency in the use of facilities, equipment and personnel.

In September, the Office of Communication helped organize and conduct the Institute's first field day. This was an invitational event, with the heads of various government, educational, and business organizations being invited to send designated numbers of people from their staffs. The 116 who registered for the event included 49 from government bureaus and agencies, 47 from educational institutions, and 20 from commercial organizations.

Preliminary returns from a follow-up study of the registrants provide data which will be useful in planning future events. For 43 of the 60 persons returning questionnaires in the first month following the field day, the aspect of the day with which they were most satisfied was the opportunity to see the field experiments and demonstrations, with lodging and stem elongation, varietal improvement, and control of stem borer being mentioned most frequently. Visual aids and exhibits, when used adjacent to the demonstration plots, drew frequent favorable comment.

Among the field day visitors were several staff members of the Farm and Home Development Office, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, who, the following day, with the help of a few Tagalog-speaking members of the Institute staff, conducted a field day for some 800 Filipino farmers.

These activities illustrate some of the ways the Institute attempts to facilitate the communication of information about improved methods of rice culture from existing governmental agencies and educational institutions to commercial groups, landowners, and rice growers. The problem becomes more complex, however, outside the Philippines, and necessitates development of other avenues of communication. These will be actively explored in the year ahead.

Communication to the Public

The Institute attracts considerable mass media and general public attention both within and outside the Philippines. To date, the Office of Communication has limited its operations in this area to fulfilling requests for material or assistance. These arise principally from Manila newspapers and magazines or from the United States Information Service for material for regional publications.

Institute photographers and editors assisted a reporter-photographer team from *LIFE* Magazine with a major feature on

rice, worked with a motion picture crew making a film on rice for The Rockefeller Foundation, prepared photographs and copy for use in a Colombo Plan exhibit and brochure and furnished material for a television program in Australia.

The Institute attracts thousands of visitors each year, both professional and lay. Many of these are high school and college students who make a day's outing to the Institute and the adjacent College of Agriculture. Standing exhibits and displays, to supplement the Institute film, which most groups now see, are being developed.

TRAINING AND RELATED ACTIVITIES

Concentration on the dissemination activities left little time for organizing or conducting communication training activities within the Institute. During the period, however, the head presented two seminars. A list of books and journals in the relevant social sciences was prepared and forwarded to the Library for procurement. Similarly, the office borrowed certain training films through the Communications Media Officer, USAID, Philippines.

Other activities of the Office of Communication supported the responsibilities described above or served the needs of the organization in other ways. These included the development of mailing lists and assisting with conferences. In addition to

editing, reproducing, and circulating the papers for each of the international symposia and conferences, the office improved communication within each of these events. To this end, a conference "Question and Comment" form was prepared, the public address facilities reworked, and the seminar room arrangements changed.

Believing that good internal communication is essential to an organization, the office in mid-year initiated a weekly publication which circulates to the staff and scholars. The principal contents are notices of Institute events and visitors for the coming week, along with administrative announcements and items of general cultural and recreational interest.

COMMUNICATION RESEARCH

Preliminary activities in the area of communication research included attempts to identify and establish exchange relationships with organizations and institutions engaged in research and evaluation of programs concerned with innovation of technological and social change. Within the Philippines, these activities included relevant activities of the University of the Philippines; the Community Development Research Council; Institute of Philippine

Culture; Research Institute for Mindanao Culture; the Philippine Sociological Society, and associates of the Council on Economic and Cultural Affairs.

Outside of the Philippines, efforts were launched to establish and maintain cooperative relationships on research projects and information with organizations, institutions, and, primarily, specific individuals interested in or engaged in research in one or more of the related social sciences.

THE LIBRARY READING ROOM, with scientific periodicals and a wide range of standard references, serves the Institute staff, visiting scientists, and the academic community.

Library and Documentation Center

Development and expansion of existing projects and the establishing of new research programs necessitated the acquisition of many standard texts and journals associated with the new programs. These activities also contributed to the development of the world's most comprehensive collection of technical literature on rice research and in the supporting sciences.

ACQUISITIONS

Library materials classified and cataloged reached a total of 8,431 volumes, representing books, pamphlets, and reprints. During the year, 13,000 cards were produced.

The number of translations available reached 514, of which 133 were accomplished by the Institute's translators in Japan. Aside from these, the Institute uses the translation services of the John Crerar Library, the Commonwealth Bureau of Soil in Harpenden and local tal-

ent. One of the significant acquisitions was the translation from Russian to English of the Roschevitz critical botanical review of species of rice.

The Library receives 937 periodicals; 363 of these are subscriptions, 437 are gifts, and the rest are obtained on exchange arrangements. To fill the gaps in periodical runs, the Library continues to use the U.S. Book Exchange, a free distribution and exchange agency.

Donors during the period included Mr. Bessel D. van't Woudt, irrigation service specialist of the University of Hawaii; and the Library of the Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University.

CIRCULATION AND REFERENCE

This library activity has steadily increased in proportion to size of the staff and the number of research scholars and fellows.

The total number of periodicals, books, pamphlets, translations, and records loaned during 1962-63 exceeded that of 1961-62 by more than 3,000. This figure does not reflect use of publications on the open stacks, nor of microfilms.

Requests for information were received from Thailand, Malaya, Taiwan, The Netherlands, and the United States. To answer these and other inquiries, selected bibliographies were compiled and photocopies of articles supplied.

To bring the most recent rice literature to the attention of the scientists, the Library routed content tables of journals. Similarly, lists of acquisitions (monographs, new serial titles and translations) are issued monthly.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

A bibliography of the world's rice literature, covering the period 1951-1960, was released in late 1963. The microfilm collection, corresponding to the 10-year bibliography, already has been mounted in aperture cards, duly numbered, and are being serviced and used.

The first supplement to the major bibliography is being prepared, with publication tentatively set for April, 1964.

BINDERY

The total bindery output during the year was 3,394 representing periodical volumes and pamphlets. The Bindery also served other departments by making pamphlet files and conference folders.

MICROFILM READER-PRINTER in the Institute Library will produce a copy of any page of microfilm at the push of a button.

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To bring the most recent rice literature to the attention of the scientists, the Library routed content tables of journals. Similarly, lists of acquisitions (monographs, new serial titles and translations) are issued monthly.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

A bibliography of the world's rice literature, covering the period 1951-1960, was released in late 1963. The microfilm collection, corresponding to the 10-year bibliography, already has been mounted in aperture cards, duly numbered, and are being serviced and used.

The first supplement to the major bibliography is being prepared, with publication tentatively set for April, 1964.

BINDERY

The total bindery output during the year was 3,394 representing periodical volumes and pamphlets. The Bindery also served other departments by making pamphlet files and conference folders.

MICROFILM READER-PRINTER in the Institute Library will produce a copy of any page of microfilm at the push of a button.

August, 1 year of research on the phosphate status of southeast Asian soils. His project was described in the 1961-1962 Annual Report.

Dr. Ellis F. Wallihan, associate profes-

sor of agricultural chemistry, University of California, Riverside, left in August after completing a year's work primarily on the critical nitrogen level in rice leaves.

REGULAR AND SPECIAL SEMINARS

The Institute's seminar series are intended to stimulate inter-disciplinary research on rice, to inform the staff of the Institute and other interested scientists of current progress in all disciplines, and to acquaint young scientists with the research programs of all departments.

Each Saturday morning, all trainees and research assistants, plus some students and faculty members of the College of Agriculture, met for 1½ hours to learn about and to discuss some important rice topic. Each seminar period is the responsibility of one of the senior scientists; usually he arranges for his assistants or scholars to present a review of, and new information on, one of the current research projects. Visits to field experiments often are included.

These seminars provide each year an orderly presentation of Institute information. During two semesters, scholars and assistants may register for graduate credit; however, they are requested to attend whether registered for credit or not. Many consider the seminar as one of the Institute's most valuable training activities.

Each Thursday afternoon, and occasionally at other times, seminars are held at which distinguished visitors or senior scientists on the staff present scholarly papers. These seminars are open to anyone interested, and some seminars attract as many as 200 persons. The following list of titles and speakers for 1963 reflects the wide range of interests of the staff and visitors:

The rice stem borers and their control. *Dr. Pathak*

Some interesting biochemical studies of rice. *Dr. Akazawa*

The rice breeding program of the College of Agriculture. *Dr. Pedro Escuro*, head, Department of Agronomy, UPCA

Some problems in the classification of rice soils. *Dr. Ichiro Kanno*, pedologist, National Kyushu Agricultural Experiment Station, Japan

An analysis of the impact of the present rice and corn production program. *Mr. Eugenio C. Cruz*, director, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines

Some aspects of phosphorus in paddy soils. *Dr. Tyner*

Science documentation services. *Dr. Ralph Shaw*, dean of Graduate School of Library Science, Rutgers University

Rice kernel composition and its relation to quality. *Dr. Juliano*

Statistical methods in rice research. *Dr. Oñate*

Some important aspects of plant virus disease investigations. *Dr. Glenn S. Pound*, chairman, Department of Plant Pathology, University of Wisconsin

Adaptability of rice varieties to different environments. *Dr. H. I. Oka*, plant breeder, National Institute of Genetics, Japan

Clonal propagation of rice and other recent approaches to rice genetics. *Dr. R. H. Richharia*, director, Central Rice Research Institute, India

SENIOR SCIENTISTS WORK CLOSELY with research scholars in laboratory and field studies. Here, scholars from Indonesia and Thailand discuss stem borer research with the entomologist.

International Activities

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To permit the review of problems of international importance, to aid in the development of sound research objectives, to provide rice scientists with opportunities to exchange ideas directly, and to facilitate development of effective cooperative research, the Institute initiated in 1963 a series of invitational conferences. These will be continued in 1964.

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- Utilization of heterosis in plant breeding. *Dr. Glenn W. Burton*, principal geneticist, Georgia Coastal Plain Experiment station, USA
- Illustrated introduction to Cambodia. *Mr. Charles D. Crocker*, agricultural advisor and soil expert, US AID, Cambodia
- Influence of root zone temperature on growth and nutrient absorption by corn and oats. *Dr. Nyle C. Brady*, project leader, UP-Cornell Team
- Methods of nitrogen fertilizer application to rice plants. *Dr. Yoshiaki Goto*, Dean of the Faculty of Agriculture, Nagoya University, Japan
- Modern trends in soil microbiology. *Dr. MacKae*

STAFF PUBLICATIONS

Accepted for Publication

- T. Akazawa, T. Minamikawa and T. Murata. Enzymic mechanism of starch biosynthesis in ripening rice grains. *Plant Physiology*. (In press)
- Gloria M. Bautista, J. C. Lugay, Lourdes J. Cruz, and B. O. Juliano. Glutamic acid decarboxylase activity as a viability index of artificially dried and stored rice. *Cereal Chem.* Manuscript 561.
- T. T. Chang. 1963. Report on the symposium on rice genetics and cytogenetics. *Int. Rice Comm. Newsletter* 12(1): 5-10.
- T. T. Chang. Report of a poll on *Oryza* species. *Proc. Symposium on Rice Genet. & Cytogenet.*, 1963, IRRI. (In press).
- T. T. Chang. The International Rice Research Institute as an information and communication center for rice genetics, cytogenetics and breeding. *Proc. Symposium on Rice Genet. & Cytogenet.*, 1963, IRRI. (In press).
- T. T. Chang, M. K. Wang, K. M. Lin, and C. P. Cheng. Breeding for blast resistance in Taiwan. *Proc. Symposium on the Rice Blast Disease*, 1963, IRRI (In process)
- T. T. Chang and N. E. Jodon. Monitoring of gene symbols in rice. *Int. Rice Comm. Newsletter*. 1963 (In press).
- Peter R. Jennings. Plant type as a rice breeding objective. *Crop Science*. 1963. (In press)
- Peter R. Jennings. Problems of rice blast requiring further attention. A concluding survey to the symposium on the rice blast disease. *Int. Rice Comm. Newsletter*. 1963 (In press). Also in *Proc. Symposium on the Rice Blast Disease*, 1963, IRRI. (In process)
- Lloyd Johnson. Report on the conference on agricultural engineering aspects of rice production. *Int. Rice Comm. Newsletter*. 1963. (In press)
- B. O. Juliano, Gloria M. Bautista, J. C. Lugay, and Aurora C. Reyes. Rice Quality. Studies on the physicochemical properties of rice. *J. Agr. Food Chem.* Manuscript Ag-37.
- B. O. Juliano. Hygroscopic equilibria of rough rice. *Cereal Chem.* Manuscript 560.
- Leticia Mendiola and T. Akazawa. Partial purification and the enzymatic nature of fraction I protein of rice leaves. *Biochemistry*. 1963. (In press)
- T. Murata, T. Minamikawa and T. Akazawa. Isolation of adenosine diphosphate glucose from rice and its role in starch synthesis. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Comm.* (In press).
- Burton T. Oñate. Multi-stage sampling for a time series. *Proceedings Issue, Philippine Sociological Review*. June, 1963.
- S. H. Ou. The symposium on the rice blast disease. *Int. Rice Comm. Newsletter*. 1963. (In press).
- S. H. Ou. Varietal reactions of rice to blast. *Proc. Symposium on the Rice Blast Disease*, 1963. IRRI. (In process)
- S. H. Ou. A proposal for an international program of research on the rice blast disease. *Proc. Symposium on the Rice Blast Disease*, 1963. IRRI. (In process).
- N. Parthasarathy and S. H. Ou. An international approach to the problem of blast. *Proc. Symposium on the Rice Blast Disease*, 1963. IRRI. (In process).
- C. T. Rivera and S. H. Ou. Transmission studies of the orange-leaf disease of rice. *Plant Disease Reporter*, USDA. Dec. 15, 1963.
- M. Rosero, J. Manuel, D. Oscar, K. Sohm, and Peter R. Jennings. Prácticas de cultivo en arroz. *I. Arroz* (Colombia) XI(130): 12-14. 1963.
- M. Rosero, J. Manuel, D. Oscar, K. Sohm, and Peter R. Jennings. Prácticas de cultivo en arroz. *II. Arroz* (Colombia) XI(131): 28-29. 1963.

Submitted for Publication

- B. O. Juliano, Gloria B. Cagampang, Lourdes J. Cruz, and Remedios G. Santiago. Some physicochemical properties of rice in southeast Asia.
- J. C. Lugay and B. O. Juliano. Fatty acid composition of rice lipids by gas-liquid chromatography.
- A. Tanaka and S. A. Navasero. Loss of nitrogen from the rice plant through rain or dew.
- B. S. Vergara, R. Lilis and A. Tanaka. Relationship between length of growing period and yield of rice plants under a limited nitrogen supply.

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tute expects they will train others and help find reliable solutions to their nations' rice-growing problems.

In many countries, research on problems related to rice production receives relatively little encouragement or financial support, even though increased rice production is a major goal of virtually every rice-growing nation. The opinion is widespread that the information needed to increase production already is available in each country and that production can be increased rapidly by supplying the farmers with the present information, with agricultural chemicals and fertilizers, or with incentives.

Results obtained by the Institute in the first 2 years, however, indicate that much information presently accepted as correct is not reliable or valid, and there is a

real need in each country to develop adequate varieties, to evaluate chemical and fertilizer usage, to reappraise cultural practices, and to identify remedies for other problems. The Institute hopes that its results will stimulate similar activities in each rice-growing area. Institute scientists travel to other countries to exchange information, and other rice scientists and agricultural leaders are encouraged to visit the Institute.

To further international cooperative work among rice scientists and to encourage outstanding research efforts elsewhere, the Institute provides modest financial support for a limited number of projects.

These activities, described in more detail in the following sections, are supported largely with a 3-year grant of \$750,000 from the Ford Foundation.

THE TRAINING PROGRAM

One of the major objectives of the Institute is the post-graduate training of staff members for other educational or research organizations concerned with increasing rice production. Research scholars or fellows serve as temporary staff members of the Institute and gain experience under the close supervision of the senior scientists.

Most of the 65 scholars and fellows in residence in 1963 were university faculty members or research workers from rice experiment stations of Asian countries. Their training periods varied from 1-2 months for those acquiring skill in specific techniques, to 1 year for those obtaining experience and training in a general field of research, to 2 years or more for those working toward a master of science degree.

The master of science program requires about 1 year for necessary course work at the College of Agriculture, University of

the Philippines, plus 1 year of full-time work at the Institute during which scholars complete special research problems and theses for graduate credit, with Institute scientists as advisors. The degrees are awarded by the University of the Philippines.

Candidates for training normally are recommended to the Institute by the organizations employing them, and the organizations must give assurance that positions will be available for the scholars upon completion of the training period. An Institute staff member interviews each prospective scholar in his home country to determine his qualifications, the specific kind of training he needs, and his proficiency in English.

The Institute provides scholars with quarters and meals, modest stipends of 110 pesos (about \$30 U.S. dollars) per month, and excellent facilities for study and work. Each scholar receives a set of reference books for his personal use, and

INSTITUTE SCHOLARS ATTEND SEMINARS, enroll in classes, and write examinations regularly.

the Institute pays the cost of studies at the College of Agriculture. Stipends for research fellows are \$60 and \$100 (U.S.) per month for persons with a M.S. or Ph.D. degree, respectively.

Short-Term Training

Mr. H. Siregar, director, Cereals Research Institute, Bogor, Indonesia, and Mr. Truong Phuoc Nien, My Tho Experiment Station, Vietnam, each spent approximately 3 months at the Institute reviewing research results and techniques of potential value at their home stations.

To date, six persons have received specialized training of 2-3 months in field techniques for testing varietal reactions to the rice blast disease. These include Lagrimas Belda and Angelina Baldeo, Maligaya Experiment Station; Fe Divinagracia, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station; Orencio Lawas, Cagayan Valley Rice and Corn Experiment Station; and Felicito Tidon, Visayas Rice and Corn Experiment Station. All are employees of

the Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Sai Chu Lau, plant pathologist, Agriculture and Forestry Department, Hongkong, received similar training.

Mohamed Zain Karim, plant physiologist, University of Malaysia, spent a month reviewing recent research in physiology and outlining a research program to be developed at the university.

Miss Sri Bunga Lubis, Indonesia, studied library procedures for 3 months. Warren McNeely, a U.S. Peace Corps volunteer, assisted the statistician for 6 weeks. Abraham Medina, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines, spent 3 months developing techniques for rat control.

Research Scholars

To date, the Institute has accepted 43 research scholars for training for periods of 1 to 2 years. Of these, three have completed their training and have returned to their home institutions.

The scholars, their home institutions, and their major areas of research, are:

Agronomy

- MARCELO ASPIRAS, assistant irrigation supervisor, Irrigation Service Unit, Department of Public Works and Communications, Philippines. *Major research:* Dates of planting; nitrogen placement.
- AGUINALDO BUENO, agronomist III, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. *Major research:* Chemical weed control; spacing x variety x nitrogen level interaction.
- ISAAC CAGANPANG, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Crop rotation and straw management; herbicide testing.
- SHUEH-KUN CHANG, junior agronomist, Taichung District Improvement Station, Taiwan. *Major research:* Water stress and water management.
- ISIDRO DOMINGO, agronomist I, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. *Major research:* Weed control in upland rice.
- WILFREDO ESPADA, instructor, Central Philippine University, Iloilo, Philippines. *Major research:* Delayed transplanting; silica fertilization.
- OWAHT JOOTANON, junior lecturer, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Variety x spacing x fertility interaction.
- ALBERTO LANUZA, research assistant, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Decomposition of green manures.
- ROMEO OBORDO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Methods of planting rice; rates of broadcasting major varieties.
- JOSE ONA, assistant instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Weed control in upland rice; fertilizer x weed control interaction.
- CLEOFAS RODRIGUEZ, agronomist III, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. *Major research:* Improved rice production practices for Mindanao.

Agricultural Engineering

- ABRAHAM CAOILI*, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Study of the drainage lines of the UPCA sub-surface drainage areas; test of a knapsack sprayer in the rice field; evapotranspiration, seepage, and percolation of water from a rice field.
- REYNALDO LANTIN, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Air-flow pressure relationships when drying rice in sacks; bio-energetical study on the Philippine work animal.

* Training completed.

SCHOLARS IN AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING construct scale models before building operating models of experimental equipment and tools.

PAIRAJ LAOWHAPHAN, Agricultural Office, Design and Workshop Section, Rice Department, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Measurement of capacities of various types of small tractors; measurement of experimental plots of various shapes.

METHA RAJATAPITI, chief, Design Workshop Section, Rice Department, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Solar drying for wet paddy; rice cone thresher tests; pneumatic grain conveying.

RODOLFO REYES, research aide, Department of Agricultural Engineering, IRRI. *Major research:* Effect of spacing on upland rice (Establishing equations for effect of spacing on rice yield, tillers, plant height, bearing panicles.)

Entomology

ARIFIN DJAMIN, instructor, Raja Agricultural High School, Medan, Indonesia. *Major research:* Varietal resistance to stem borer infestation.

AMADOR FRANCES, pest control officer, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. *Major research:* Ovicidal and larvicidal effects of various insecticides on the rice stem borer, *Chilo suppressalis* Walker.

SOMPORN PATANAKAMJORN, instructor, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Differential resistance to stem borer (*Chilo suppressalis* Walker); infestation in rice varieties and its associations with various plant characters.

KHEMKHANG SITATHANI, instructor, Kasetsart University, Bangkok Thailand. *Major research:* Assessment of losses caused by insect pests of rice.

Plant Pathology

JOSE BANDONG, research assistant, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Physiologic races of *Piricularia oryzae* in the Philippines.

URAI KOOT-IN^o, junior instructor, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Host range of *Piricularia oryzae*.

MRS. IMELDA QUINTANA^o, assistant instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Chemical control of the blast disease.

LUANSARK WATHANAKUL, agricultural officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Host range of "orange leaf" and "tungro" diseases of rice.

Plant Physiology

NGUYEN THI DIEM, assistant chief, Soil Fertility Section, Soil Service, Directorate of Agricultural Research, Vietnam. *Major research:* Training in greenhouse pot experimentation.

TEOFILO EUGENIO, agronomist III and acting superintendent, Cagayan Valley Experiment Station, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. *Major research:* Comparison of greenhouse and field fertilizer experiments.

SHEN LIAN, junior specialist, Department of Agricultural Chemistry, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taiwan. *Major research:* Physiological characters of rice varieties related to nitrogen response.

CHAI PRECHACHAT, second grade official, Breeding Division, Rice Department, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Germination of rice seeds under various water conditions.

SANER PURANABHAVUNG, second grade official, Technical Division, Rice Department, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Photoperiodic response of rice varieties.

Soil Chemistry

RUBEN ASPIRAS, research assistant, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Ammonification in flooded soils and its bearing on nitrogen nutrition of rice.

DIOSDADO CARANDANG, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines.
Major research: Segregation and evaluation of the direct and indirect effects of flooding on the growth and yield of rice.

WEN-LIAN HUANG, soil specialist, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taiwan. *Major research:* Isolation and characterization of the substance or substances causing "suffocation" disease of rice in slate alluvial soils.

MAI THI MY-NHUNG, assistant chief chemist, Directorate of Research Studies on Agronomy, Forestry and Animal Husbandry, Vietnam. *Major research:* Chemical and physicochemical properties of acid sulfate soils.

SUMON SRISUMBOON, agricultural officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand. *Major research:* Chemical analysis of reduced soils.

WEN-LIN YUAN, instructor, Department of Agricultural Chemistry, Taiwan Provincial Chung Hsing University, Taichung, Taiwan. *Major research:* Retardation of reduction of slate alluvial soils.

Varietal Improvement

MANEE CHUAVIROJ, technician, San Pahtong Experiment Station, Chiangmai, Thailand.
Major research: Partial sterility in *indica* x *japonica* hybrids.

ANACLETO GUEVARRA, research assistant, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. *Major research:* Internode elongation in rice varieties of reduced plant stature.

CHENG-SENG HUANG, junior specialist, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taipei, Taiwan, *Major research:* Some quantitative characters of rice; reciprocal translocation of chromosomes in rice.

PATRICIO LAYSA, agronomist III, Bureau of Plant Breeding, Philippines. *Major research:* Varietal performance under direct seeding and transplanting.

TEA NEANG, controller of agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture, Cambodia. *Major research:* General rice breeding.

SUKHEE SORNCHAI, technician, Sakunakhon Experiment Station, Sakunakhon, Thailand.
Major research: Effect of lodging on yield loss in rice.

PAIBOOL TRACHOO, technician, Pimai Experiment Station, Nakhon Rajsima, Thailand.
Major research: Yield component studies; effect of spacing in *indica* varieties.

YU-LONG WU, junior specialist, Kaohsiung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan Provincial Department of Agriculture and Forestry, Kaohsiung, Taiwan.
Major research: Effect of cultural practices on resistance to lodging in rice.

RESEARCH FELLOWS and scholars participate in a departmental seminar with the plant physiologist.

RESEARCH FELLOWS

Thirteen scientists from India, Japan, the Philippines, and Vietnam conducted advanced research at the Institute during all or part of 1963.

MR. SADA O SAKAMOTO, National Institute of Genetics, Japan, spent 5 months assisting with the establishment of a living collection of wild and cultivated species of *Oryza*, studying chromosome numbers of these species, and in preparing and identifying herbarium specimens.

MR. TAKAO MINAMIKAWA, Biochemistry Department, Nagoya University, Japan, completed a year of work on the isolation of flavonoids from rice plants and on starch biosynthesis.

MR. TAKAO MURATA, research scientist, Tohoku National Agricultural Experiment Station, Japan, is engaged in a 2-year study of starch biogenesis. He also participates in work on nitrogen metabolism.

MR. KAZUO KAWANO, graduate student, Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University, is spending a year studying the relationships between plant type and photosynthesis in an attempt to develop a clearer

understanding of the nature of varietal response to nitrogen applications.

DR. JOSEFINA LUCAY, faculty member, University of Santo Tomas, Philippines, is engaged in a 1-year study of X-ray diffraction of rice starches and its relation to other physicochemical properties.

MR. MINORU MOROOKA, technical officer, Kyushu National Agricultural Experiment Station, Japan, is spending a year analyzing the results of the international cooperative study of climatic factors affecting rice production in Asia.

MR. AND MRS. TATSUO SUGIYAMA, graduate students, Nagoya University, Japan, are spending a year with the biochemistry group in studies of starch biosynthesis and nitrogen metabolism, respectively.

MR. KIYOTA TATENO, graduate student, Kyushu University, Japan, is engaged for a year in identification of genetic mutants and wild species, development of trisomics, and development of haploid plants.

MR. TRUONG-DINH PHU, chief, Soil Service, Department of Rural Affairs, Vietnam, is conducting a 9-month study of, some

mineralogical properties of paddy soils in the major deltaic areas of southeast Asia.

DR. MASAO GOTO, instructor, Faculty of Agriculture, Shizuoka University, Japan, is studying, for a year, the bacterial diseases of rice in southeast Asia.

DR. V. T. JOHN, University Botany Laboratory, University of Madras, India, is studying (a) the relationships among rice viruses, utilizing serological techniques, (b) effect of temperature on virus

vectors and the host plants, (c) trans-ovarial transmission of "tungro" and "orange-leaf" viruses, and (d) possible alternate hosts of rice viruses.

DR. L. RAMAKRISHNAN, University Botany Laboratory, University of Madras, is investigating the nature of resistance to the rice blast disease, with particular reference to effects of temperature, levels of nitrogen, and sources of nitrogen, on levels of resistance.

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

One of the year's significant achievements was the initiation of a series of technical conferences on subjects of international importance to rice research and production. The Institute sponsored three such events, covering these topics: Rice genetics and cytogenetics, the rice blast disease, and agricultural engineering aspects of rice production.

The three conferences were similar in certain respects. They were planned 6-8 months in advance and specific objectives were established for each. The invited participants and observers were all scientists actively engaged in research. In the case of the genetics and blast symposia, each participant prepared, in advance, a major paper reviewing the world's knowledge on a specific assigned aspect of a problem on which he had pioneered.

These papers, after preliminary editing, were reproduced and furnished to the participants and observers prior to or at the start of each symposium. After discussion, supplementation, and further review, the genetics and blast symposia papers are being published as books. The Institute expects these to become important reference volumes on these significant subjects.

These conferences not only brought together in a common language the significant literature, but provided opportunities, frequently for the first time, for many Asian scientists to meet face-to-face and discuss, across the conference table and informally, their professional activities, concerns, and problems.

At year's end, plans were nearly complete for a fourth conference, this to be a symposium on the mineral nutrition of the rice plant, scheduled to be held at the Institute the last week in February, 1964. Preliminary arrangements are in progress on a symposium on the rice stem borer and other major insect pests of rice, tentatively scheduled for September, 1964.

The three sections which follow constitute brief reports on the three international conference activities held in 1963.

Rice Genetics and Cytogenetics

A symposium on rice genetics and cytogenetics, held February 4-8, 1963, was the first international conference solely devoted to a discussion of rice genetics, cytogenetics, and taxonomy. A total of 102 scientists and students from nine countries attended the meeting. Twenty-one invitational papers were read by rice scientists from India, Japan, Taiwan, the United

DR. N. PARTHASARATHY, regional rice specialist, FAO, addresses the opening session of the Symposium on Rice Genetics and Cytogenetics.

States, and a representative of the FAO. The moderator was Dr. H. H. Kramer, University of Nebraska.

Objectives of the symposium were (a) to determine the present status of research achievements in the fields of rice genetics, cytogenetics and taxonomy, (b) to review areas of agreement and disagreement, and (c) to identify the problems on which future research is most needed.

Discussions and papers emphasized five subjects, as follows:

On Taxonomy – “Taxonomy of the Genus *Oryza*” (Tuguo Tateoka) and “The Genus *Oryza*: its Taxonomy” (S. Sampath);

On Gene Symbolization and Nomenclature – “Early History of Genic Analysis and Symbolization in Rice” (K. Ramiah); “Gene Symbolization and Nomenclature-FAO’s Interest and Role” (N. Parthasarathy); “Toward Uniformity of Gene Symbolization in Rice Genetics” (N. E. Jodon); and “The International Rice Research Institute as an Information and Communication Center for Rice Genetics, Cytogenetics and Breeding” (T. T. Chang).

On Chromosome Morphology in Oryza Species – “Further Studies on the chromo-

some Morphology of *Oryza sativa* L.” (C. H. Hu) and “New Approach to the Study of Rice Karyomorphology” (S. V. S. Shastry).

On Genetic and Cytogenetic Evidence for Species Relationships – “Pattern of Interspecific Relationships and Evolutionary Dynamics in *Oryza*” (H. I. Oka); “Cytogenetical Investigations on *Oryza* Species” (T. Morinaga); “Cytogenetical Studies at the Louisiana Agricultural Experiment Station on Species Relationships in *Oryza*” (M. T. Henderson); “Chromosome Structural Differentiation, Isolation Mechanisms and Speciation in *Oryza*” (S. V. S. Shastry); and “Studies on Genetic and Cytogenetic Evidence for Species Relationships in the Republic of China” (H. W. Li).

On Nature of Intervarietal Hybrid Sterility in Oryza sativa – “Cytogenetical Studies at the Louisiana Agricultural Experiment Station on the Nature of Intervarietal Hybrid Sterility in *O. sativa*” (M. T. Henderson); “Is Sterility Genic in *japonica-indica* Hybrids?” (S. V. S. Shastry); “Considerations on the Genetic Basis of Intervarietal Hybrid Sterility in *O. sativa*” (H. I. Oka); and “The Significance of Hybrid Sterility in Rice” (S. Sampath).

On Inheritance Studies, Gene Markers and Linkage Groups – “Genetic Segregation and Linkage – Important Phases of Rice Research” (N. E. Jodon); “Certain Considerations on Genic Analysis and Linkage Groups in Rice” (R. Seetharaman); and “Linkage Groups and Gene Schemes of Some Striking Morphological Characters in Japanese Rice” (M. Takahashi).

In the closing session, the conferees agreed that the following areas merit attention in the future: extensive genetic analysis of physiological and quantitative traits of economic importance; development of more complete linkage maps through the use of improved testers, translocations and trisomics; extension of genome analysis to sections other than *Sativa* and the cooperative collection of additional experimental material in Africa and elsewhere; intensive studies on the nature of hybrid sterility; investigation of the inheritance of resistance to major diseases and pests; genetic studies of hybrid populations, and interspecific transfer of desirable traits; continuing search for varieties having characters of interest to rice scientists in various disciplines; the cooperative pooling of genetic material, with the Institute serving as a germplasm bank; the channeling of genetic information on testers and symbols through the IRRI. It also was unanimously agreed that the symposium was highly useful in promoting the exchange of ideas and information and that similar meetings should be held in the future.

Reports on the symposium have appeared in several publications, including *The AIBS Bulletin*, 13:3, June, 1963, and the *IRC Newsletter*, 12:1, March, 1963.

The Rice Blast Disease

The symposium on the rice blast disease, July 7-12, 1963, was designed (a) to promote international awareness of the

blast disease, (b) to review the past achievements in research on the disease and to identify the problem on which future work is most needed, (c) to encourage the development and use of resistant varieties, and (d) to initiate an effective international research program.

It was attended by 49 invited participants and observers from 32 institutions of 15 countries and by more than 50 observers from local organizations. The countries represented were Australia, Cambodia, China (Taiwan), Hongkong, India, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Malaya, Pakistan, the Philippines, Sierra Leone, Thailand, the U.S.A., and Vietnam.

Twenty-nine papers were presented in nine sessions, with Dr. P. R. Jennings serving as moderator.

In addition to the opening paper by Drs. N. Parthasarathy and S. H. Ou on “An International Approach to the Problem of Blast,” the remaining papers were organized around six major topics as follows:

On the Fungus – “Morphology, Taxonomy, Host Range, and Life Cycle of *Piricularia oryzae*” (H. Asuyama); “Nutrition of *Piricularia oryzae* in vitro” (S. Tanaka); “Biochemical Products of Metabolism of *Piricularia oryzae*” (K. Tamari, N. Ogasawara, J. Kaji); “Variability of *Piricularia oryzae* in Culture” (H. Otsuka); and “Origin of Variation in *Piricularia oryzae*” (H. Suzuki);

On the Disease and Its Development – “Effects of Environmental Factors on Development of the Causal Fungus, Infection, Disease Development, and Epidemiology in the Rice Blast Disease” (Y. Hashioka); “Influence of Temperature on the Rice Blast Disease” (T. S. Sadasivan, S. Suryanarayanan, and L. Ramakrishnan); “Techniques and Equipment for Studying Relationships of Climate to Blast Develop-

ment" (Frances Latterell); "Principles and Organization of Blast Disease Forecasting" (K. Ono); "Estimating Losses from Rice Blast in Japan" (K. Goto); "Estimating Losses from Rice Blast in India" (S. Y. Padmanabhan); and "Varietal Reactions of Rice to Blast" (S. H. Ou);

On Physiologic Races — "Physiologic Races of *Piricularia oryzae* in Japan" (K. Goto); "Physiologic Races of *Piricularia oryzae* in the Western Hemisphere" (J. G. Atkins); "Physiologic Races of *Piricularia oryzae* in Taiwan" (R. J. Chiu, C. C. Chien, and S. Y. Li); and "Coordination of Effort to Select Blast Differentials" (Frances Latterell);

On Mechanism, Genetics of Resistance — "Nature of Resistance to Blast" (N. Suzuki); and "Genetics of Resistance to the Rice Blast Disease" (Y. Takahashi);

On Breeding for Blast Resistance — "Breeding for Blast Resistance in the U. S. A." (J. G. Atkins, C. N. Bollich, T. H. Johnston, N. E. Jodon, H. M. Beachell,

and G. T. Templeton); "Breeding for Blast Resistance in India" (S. Y. Padmanabhan); "Breeding for Blast Resistance in Japan" (R. Ito); "Breeding for Blast Resistance in Taiwan" (T. T. Chang, M. K. Wang, K. M. Lin, and C. P. Cheng); "Breeding for Blast Resistance in Thailand" (Sala Dasananda);

On Control by Chemicals and Cultural Practices — "Chemical Control of the Rice Blast Disease in Japan" (H. Okamoto); "Fungicide Development for Blast Control" (K. Fukunaga); "Equipment for Application of Fungicides for Blast Control" (N. Hatai), and "Control of Rice Blast by Cultural Practices in Japan" (T. Kosaka).

The final papers were "A Proposal for an International Program of Research on the Rice Blast Disease" (S. H. Ou), and a concluding survey, by Dr. Jennings.

Participants in the symposium reviewed and accepted an international program of research on the rice blast disease.

It was agreed that the Uniform Blast Nursery Program initiated by the Inter-

SIXTY PARTICIPANTS AND OBSERVERS from 17 countries attend the first international Symposium on the Rice Blast Disease.

national Rice Commission, FAO, should be strengthened in order (a) to identify sources of blast resistance, (b) to assist in the development of an international set of differentials for race studies, and (c) to obtain some idea of race patterns in rice-growing countries.

Participants asked the Institute to administer the program in the future and (a) to select initial variety groups for testing in the blast nursery, (b) to multiply and supply seeds to collaborators, and (c) to prepare and distribute details of testing procedures.

The 1963-1964 nursery will involve about 250 varieties, including 38 differential varieties from Japan, Taiwan, and the U. S. A., about 100 varieties from the FAO-IRC 1962 Uniform Blast Nursery and other leading commercial varieties of Southeast Asia which have shown distinct types of reaction in Institute tests. These have been multiplied, and the seeds are being distributed. A detailed procedure of testing was adopted. The scope and procedures were slightly modified and the scoring of disease reaction simplified from the original IRC recommendations.

Delegates from the 14 countries listed below indicated their desire to participate in the tests at the number of localities indicated: Australia, 2; China (Taiwan), 1; Hongkong, 1; India, 7; Indonesia, 3; Japan, 1; Korea, 2; Malaysia, 4; Pakistan, East, 4; Pakistan, West, 3; Philippines, 1; Sierra Leone, 1; Thailand, 3; U. S. A., 3; and Vietnam, 2.

Dr. T. Kozaka (Japan) and Dr. Frances Latterell (U.S.A.) indicated their willingness to accept diseased specimens from all countries for race identification analysis on a world-wide basis.

A report on the conference by Dr. Ou and the full text of Dr. Jennings' concluding survey were published in the September, 1963, issue of the *IRC Newsletter*.

Agricultural Engineering Aspects of Rice Production

During the week of August 11-17, 1963, the Institute sponsored a conference on the agricultural engineering aspects of rice production, the objectives being (a) to identify those problems in the mechanization of tropical rice production which are of greatest immediate interest; (b) to determine what facts, and particularly measurements, are needed for the solution of these problems; (c) to determine the sources of information that may be particularly applicable to the tropics, and (d) to suggest appropriate alternative approaches to the solution of the identified problems.

Moderators were Dr. Wesley F. Buchele, Iowa State University, Mr. R. H. Cochrane, FAO Regional Office for Asia and the Far East, and Dr. A. W. Cooper, USDA National Tillage Machinery Laboratory. The meeting was attended by 27 persons from 17 different institutions in Japan, Thailand, Taiwan, Philippines, U.S.A., India, Ceylon, and Australia. The 31 informal papers were presented in six major sessions, during which the following problems were emphasized:

1. Flotation and traction are major problems in the plowing of wet soils, and pulverization of the hard, dry puddled soil is difficult during the dry season. Water control is needed to soften the soil during the dry season and to provide lubrication during wet land preparation.

2. Soil measurements are needed to describe flotation, traction, and ease of land preparation. Measurements of the physical properties of the soil, such as the Atterberg limits, the coefficient of friction, the coefficient of cohesion, and shear values, are needed so that soils of various areas may be compared.

The cone penetrometer has a definite application in soil measurements. The

shear vane and the soil shear graph may be developed for future use in wet paddy soils. Soil measurements will permit exchange of information on a scientific basis.

Further work is required on tillage tools, such as rotary tillers and chisels, and on lugs and lugs on wheels.

3. Attention should be given to machinery for direct seeding of rice, which will require better weed control — primarily through the use of herbicides and of herbicide application equipment.

4. Harvesting probably will be the first operation in rice production to be fully mechanized. This should lead to mechanization of land preparation and planting, as has been true with most cereal crops. A stationary thresher is of immediate interest, but combines will be required in the future.

5. Drying and storage of rice were discussed briefly, but these topics should be

covered in greater detail, along with milling and processing, in a future conference.

The participants also discussed the power required to plow, cultivate, puddle, and harvest in terms of man-hours, animal-hours, and horsepower-hours for each operation. These values will be reported in a summary as a basis for comparing different methods of rice production.

In the concluding summary, Dr. Cooper noted that the first step in mechanizing rice production is to replace the carabao with an internal combustion engine. This will permit rapid preparation of the soil and will release the land used to feed the carabao. Water control should be developed as rapidly as possible, and where larger fields can be cultivated, a four-wheel drive tractor should be developed and used. Mechanized direct seeding of rice should replace transplanting.

Dr. Cooper proposed that conferees pursue the development of two pieces of

MODERATORS OF THE CONFERENCE on the Agricultural Engineering Aspects of Rice Production meet with the Institute director and the agricultural engineer; left to right, R. Chandler, A. W. Cooper, L. Johnson, R. H. Cochrane, and W. F. Buchele.

equipment discussed: (a) A screw device for land preparation (as proposed by M. R. Debriddhi Devakul of Thailand), and (b) an endless, chain-driven cross-tiller for land preparation. He urged that work on establishing soil parameters be continued and be related to crop yields.

Dr. Buchele emphasized the need for training people in the use of tools and described a tandem tractor which may be a fast and economical way to obtain a four-wheel drive tractor suitable for wet ricelands. He also stressed the need for mechanizing harvesting. The Institute is studying the cone-type thresher, patented by Dr. Buchele, and prototypes are being

developed. (For photographs of the tandem unit tractors and cone thresher, see the department report on agricultural engineering, pages 136 and 138.)

Mr. Cochran urged agricultural engineers to take a broad interest in rice production. He also stressed the agricultural engineer's need for training in farm advisory work.

Since there are not enough agricultural engineers available in Asia for research, extension, and other activities, Dr. Cooper and Mr. Loyd Johnson, IRRI, proposed that a handbook be compiled for use by other agricultural workers in helping to solve engineering problems.

COOPERATIVE RESEARCH

To encourage and facilitate research at other institutions on problems of international importance, or to permit scientists elsewhere to cooperate with Institute scientists on investigations of mutual concern, the Institute in 1963 supported a number of projects at other locations.

With the assistance of the Institute, T. Tateoka, Kihara Institute of Biological Research (Japan), and J. V. Pancho, University of the Philippines, visited the major islands of the Philippines and collected 43 strains of wild rice. The species included are *O. officinalis*, *O. minuta*, *O. meyeriana*, and *O. rufipogon*.

Rhizomes were observed in one *O. rufipogon* plant growing at the fringe of Lake Apo, Mindanao. This is a rare occurrence. Sympatric populations of diploid *O. officinalis* and tetraploid *O. minuta* were found to be separated reproductively by a difference in the number of chromosomes.

The seed, plant, and herbarium specimens collected during the trip were deposited at the Institute for the use of work-

ers elsewhere. Similarly, the Institute is assisting H. I. Oka, the National Institute of Genetics, Japan, and S. Sampath, Central Rice Research Institute, India, in exploratory trips to parts of Africa to augment the supply of experimental material for taxonomic, genetical, and cytogenetical studies. The Academia Sinica (Taiwan) and the Kihara Institute for Biological Research (Japan) also are participating in this venture. A duplicate set of the collected seed and plant samples will be made available to the Institute.

The Institute also assisted C. H. Hu and W. T. Chang, Taiwan Provincial Chung-Hsing University, and S. C. Hsieh, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, in genetical and cytogenetical investigation of the *O. officinalis* complex, linkage analysis, inheritance of resistance to *Piricularia oryzae*, and the response of wild populations to selection. The Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station, Taiwan, was assisted in a study of field tolerance of rice varieties to the blast fungus. However, drought

in the spring of 1963 resulted in a light blast infection and reduced the possible expression of field tolerance. The experiment will be repeated in 1964.

At the symposium on rice genetics and cytogenetics, it was noted that linkage relationships found in inheritance studies involving *indica* varieties often disagree with those found in *japonicas*. With partial support from the Institute, Dr. Man-emon Takahashi of Hokkaido University is undertaking studies of linkage relationships in both types of rice.

Cooperative experiments on climatic factors affecting rice production in Asia have been established at Bogor, Indonesia; Konosu and Sapporo, Japan; Bukit Merah, Malaysia; Taipei, Taichung, and Pintung, Taiwan; and at Bangkok, Huntra, and Chiang-mai, Thailand.

Direct cooperation in chemical weed control tests was initiated with the Mindanao Rice and Corn Experiment Station of the Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. An Institute agronomist supervised the application of chemicals at the station, and equipment was shared with the cooperators.

Discussions with potential cooperators emphasize the desirability of providing some training in spraying techniques and spray chemicals before starting field experiments. To this end, several weeks will be spent early in 1964 on a weed control clinic for research workers concerned with these problems.

Dr. Charles J. Grant, University of Hongkong, spent 6 months studying the classification of rice soils of Asia, under auspices of the Institute. He visited Vietnam, Cambodia, Thailand, Malaya, East and West Pakistan, Indonesia, and the Philippines.

A study of the classification of rice soils in the Mekong river delta as related to

response by lowland rice to differences in soil fertility, is being undertaken in the Institute laboratories by Mr. Truong-Dinh Phu, chief, Soil Service of Vietnam.

A physiological disease of rice known as the "suffocation" disease is causing much concern in Taiwan. The disease occurs on slate alluvial soils with impeded drainage and is believed to be associated with excessive reduction of the soil.

As the suffocation disease is an instance of the wider problems of physiological diseases so common in many Asian countries, the Institute took an active interest in the efforts of Taiwan scientists to solve this problem. Accordingly, a cooperative project was initiated in June, 1963, (a) to study the etiology, (b) to test control measures, and (c) to identify the toxin or toxins causing the disease. The first two aspects of the project are being investigated by Taiwan scientists under the direction of Prof. S. C. Chang, National Taiwan University. The Institute is working on the isolation and identification of the toxins.

Experiments on control measures which include (a) delayed transplanting, (b) controlled irrigation, (c) ridge culture, and (d) omission of organic manure were conducted at nine locations in central and south Taiwan.

The identification of the toxin or toxins and methods of retarding their formation have been assigned as research problems to two scholars from Taiwan.

Dr. C. Valera, soil microbiologist, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, cooperated with the soil chemist in a study of the microbiological aspects of the use of 2-chloro-6 trichloromethyl pyridine for inhibiting nitrification of ammonia fertilizers.

A project to determine the distribution of different species of the rice stem borer in the Philippines was initiated in January,

1963, by the Department of Entomology, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines, in cooperation with the Institute entomologist. The dominant species at Los Baños during most of the year is *Chilo suppressalis* Walker; however, this is not the dominant species in most regions of Asia. The Institute's success in developing useful varietal resistance will depend in part on exposure of varieties to attack by major Asian species. The objective of the present study is to determine the distribution of various species, the seasonal fluctuations that occur, and some of the factors responsible for the observed variation. To date, eight trips to outlying provinces have been made and wide differences in proportions of species of *Chilo*, *Sesamia*, and *Tryporyza* have been recorded.

Cooperative tests of insecticides and of varietal resistance to the stem borer were established during the year by the Mindanao Rice and Corn Experiment Station.

The Department of Home Technology, U. P. College of Agriculture, is studying

the relationships between protein content, amylose content, and gelatinization temperature to cooking and eating qualities of milled rice. Taste panels are used.

Cooperative research work in statistics with the Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand, includes three projects on floating or deep water rice. Work is underway on over-estimation of yield which may be explained by the silting of salt, border effects, and the possible bias resulting from the projection of yield from small plots to big areas such as a rai.

A study is underway to determine the effect on yield of different patterns of missing hills.

Data now being analyzed should permit recommendations to be made on proper sampling of attack of stem borers and other pests in replicated tests. Results of a study on the efficiency of sampling for width, length, and thickness of brown rice grain were transmitted to the Rice Department, recommending the number of samples needed for satisfactory standardization of grain measurements for export.

INTERNATIONAL TRAVEL

The agricultural economist travelled in the Philippines and to Vietnam, Malaysia, and Thailand to become acquainted with (a) the economics of the regions and countries, (b) other agricultural economists and their work, and (c) rice marketing and price policies. In a trip to central Luzon in the Philippines, he saw the work at the Maligaya Experiment Station and the Central Luzon Agricultural College. He also went to Panay and Mindoro.

He made three trips to Vietnam for purposes described in the agricultural economics report. He was particularly interested in work at the University of Ma-

laysia, and at the Rice Department and Kasetsart University in Thailand, during week-long trips to each of those nations.

The agricultural engineer, in late 1962, visited the USDA Tillage Laboratory, Auburn, Ala.; the U. S. Army Waterways Experiment Station, Vicksburg, Miss.; the Land Locomotion Laboratory, Detroit, Mich.; and the Department of Agricultural Engineering, Michigan State University, East Lansing.

In December, 1963, he attended the annual meeting of the American Society of Agricultural Engineering in Chicago.

The agronomist reviewed research in progress in Thailand late in 1962, met Thai research workers, and discussed research cooperation in that country. During June and July, he spent 3 weeks in Japan, the major interest being to learn of weed control research, herbicide evaluation techniques, and planting methods experiments in that country.

He made two trips within the Philippines, one to the Pili Rice and Corn Station, and the other to the Banawe Rice Terraces. With the cooperation of Dr. H. C. Conklin, Yale University anthropologist, an experiment for fertility evaluation was laid out, soil monoliths collected, and a number of ecological observations made at Banawe. Dr. Conklin presented the Institute with a complete collection of Ifugao agricultural tools and artifacts connected with the terrace culture in the Mountain Province.

In August, the biochemist presented a paper, "Enzymatic Synthesis of Starch in Ripening Rice Grains," at the annual meeting of the American Institute of Biological Sciences and visited biochemists at the University of Massachusetts, Rutgers University, Harvard University, the California Institute of Technology, and the University of California at Berkeley and Davis.

He also attended the annual meeting of the Biochemical Society of Japan. He presented a paper "The Enzymatic Mechanism of Starch Synthesis in Ripening Rice Grains," and then visited Nagoya University and the Institute of Applied Microbiology at Tokyo University.

Beginning in late August, the entomologist spent 2 weeks in Japan becoming acquainted with scientists and their work at the National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, the Universities of Kyoto, Nagoya, and Kyushu, the National Chiguko

Agricultural Experiment Station, and the Kyushu National Agricultural Experiment Station.

He also discussed entomological research in India with scientists at the Indian Agricultural Research Institute, the Central Rice Research Institute, the West Bengal Experiment Station at Chinsurah, the Commonwealth Institute of Biological Control at Bangalore, and at the College of Agriculture at Coimbatore.

In Thailand, he observed gall midge damage and became acquainted with entomological work and facilities at Bangkok, Lampang, and Nakor Phanom in the northeast region.

He also visited entomologists in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, and at the experiment station in Siem Reap.

The plant breeder visited the rice breeding stations in Malaysia late in 1962. In September, he joined the soil chemist in observing physiological diseases in Taiwan, and reviewed Taiwan's *indica* breeding work.

The plant physiologist visited Indonesia, Japan, Malaya, Taiwan, and Thailand to arrange details of the cooperative project, "Climatic Factors Affecting Rice Production," to become acquainted with rice cultivation methods, as well as the physiological problems and physiological research programs, and the scientists involved, in these countries. The associate plant physiologist accompanied him on his trip to Malaya and Thailand.

The soil chemist and the plant physiologist in April obtained first-hand information on the "suffocation" disease of rice during a trip to Taiwan. The cooperative project on this disease resulted. The soil chemist observed the progress of the joint investigation of this problem in September.

In April 1963, he presented a paper entitled "Retardation of Nitrification in Half-Saturated, Saturated, and Submerged Soils," co-authored by Miss Elsa Reyes, at the annual session of the Soil Science Society of Japan, held in Kyoto. Thereafter, he met and discussed soil chemistry research with workers of the National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Tokyo, and Tokyo University.

The pathologist visited the Visayas in the Philippines early in 1963 and Thailand and Malaya in December, particularly to observe progress of work on the rice blast disease. Dr. Masao Goto, research fellow in pathology, found bacterial diseases common in Thailand when he spent 5 days there in September.

In September the soil microbiologist observed physiological diseases of rice in fields in the Pintung area during a familiarization trip to Taiwan. He also discussed various aspects of research in soil microbiology with scientists at various laboratories in Taiwan and Japan.

The librarian participated in the Conference on Asian-Pacific Science Information Centers and presented two papers: "The IRRI Library and Documentation Center," and "Microfilm and Other Photographic Processes." The Conference, sponsored by the Institute of Advanced Projects of the East-West Center and the U.S. National Academy of Sciences, has facilitated the flow of literature between the Institute and the participating countries.

The statistician spent 2 weeks in Thailand, at the request of the Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, assisting in the design of experiments and in establishing approaches to analysis of data already collected. Experiments on rice

crop cutting involving multi-stage sampling design were written with the statistician in the Technical Division, Rice Department. The experiments include a three-phase sampling scheme to obtain satisfactory estimates of acreage and productivity and to develop objective crop cuts of the rice crop for the whole country.

During the visit, he also presented a series of seminars at Kasetsart University, Bangkok, on the topic "Contributions of Statisticians to a Nation's Development." About 40 statisticians and technicians from the Rice Department, National Statistical Office, and other departments in the Ministry of Agriculture attended.

The superintendent of the Institute's Experimental Farm spent 2 weeks observing the intensive approaches to rice culture in Taiwan and inspecting some of the ongoing rice research in that country.

The communication specialist in June attended the Visayas-Mindanao meeting of the Philippine Sociological Society at Cagayan de Oro, and in September, presented a paper, "Assignment to Ambiguity: Factors Associated with Performance in Cross-Cultural Technical Assistance Roles," to the society at a meeting in Manila.

In October, he accompanied the Vice President for Agriculture and Forestry, University of the Philippines, and other College of Agriculture staff members in an inspection of the Angat land reform area in the Philippines.

The associate director made a number of trips to countries in Asia during 1963. In January, he was a guest of the Ministry of Rural Affairs in Vietnam for 4 days, during which he discussed rice research work with ministry officials, and with the USAID groups. A 1-day trip to the Mytho experiment station in Din-Tuong prov-

ince was followed by a conference on prospects for improvement of rice production. Three persons were interviewed for training, all of whom are now at the Institute, and arrangements were made for a 3-day official visit to Los Baños by the Secretary-General, director of Agricultural Research, the chief of the Rice Service, and the entomologist, all of the Ministry of Rural Affairs. They were joined at the Institute by AID officials from Vietnam.

In Cambodia in January, the associate director called on the Secretary of State for Agriculture, became acquainted with agricultural officials, visited the Prek Leap Agricultural School and the National Schools of Agriculture, Animal Husbandry and Silviculture, and acquainted himself with USAID personnel and their program. He reviewed work at the rice research station at Battambang, interviewed a candidate for training who now is at the Institute, then visited the research station at Siem Reap. Subsequently, a number of Cambodians have visited the Institute to participate in conferences and to acquaint themselves with its program.

In Thailand, the following week, he interviewed scholarship candidates at the Rice Department and Kasetsart University, visited the deep-water rice station at Huntra, and discussed problems of mutual interest with officials of the FAO regional office, of the Rice Department, and of USAID.

In West Pakistan in early March, the associate director visited the Ayub Agricultural Research Institute, Lyallpur, and the Kala Shah Kaku rice station near Lahore. He also became acquainted with the programs of the government, of USAID, and of the Ford Foundation. He returned to West Pakistan in October for visits to the Kala Shah Kaku and Dokri rice experiment stations and to government offices in Rawalpindi and Karachi. He

proceeded to East Pakistan for visits to Comilla, the Agricultural Research Institute in Dacca, to projects in Mymensingh, and to AID offices.

During the summer, Mr. M. A. Cheema, Joint Secretary of Agriculture, and Dr. Anwar Hussain, Director, Ayub Agricultural Research Institute, spent three days at Los Baños reviewing the Institute's program with members of the staff. In October, invitations to make similar visits were extended to Mr. H. R. Malik, Secretary of Agriculture, and to Dr. S. H. Hazarika, Director of Agriculture, East Pakistan.

Early in March, he visited the Ministry of Food and Agriculture, New Delhi, to discuss areas of possible cooperation and participation by India in international conferences sponsored by the Institute. Later in the month, he spent 2 days at the University Botany Laboratory, University of Madras, discussing research on the rice blast disease and arranging for Dr. V. T. John and Dr. L. Ramakrishnan to spend 1-year periods at the Institute on fellowships.

During a 4-day visit to Ceylon in late March, the associate director familiarized himself with current research activities of the divisions of botany, agricultural chemistry, entomology, and plant pathology, of the Department of Agriculture and visited the Central Rice Research Station at Batalagoda, to which the Institute is contributing some needed equipment.

During a 3-week visit to Japan in April, the associate director discussed problems of rice research with members of the staff at the National Institute of Agricultural Science in Nishigahara and Konosu, with officials of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, and at the National Institute of Genetics, Nagoya University, Kyushu University, Kyushu National Agricultural Experiment Station, Kyoto University, Tohoku University, Hokkaido University, and

